

Plasma Petroglyphs (Plasmaglyphs), Earthworks, and the Megafauna Extinction

Re-examining key Allegewi¹-Hopewellian² Mounds and Serpent Effigies, comparisons with Peratt plasmoid shapes produced in laboratories to determine viability for reclassification of glyph genesis and proposal of a radically alternative vector of megafauna extinction.³

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ABSTRACT

The author presents an exciting new hypothesis for megafauna extinction based upon historical, mythical, geological, astronomic, and atmospheric evidence. While not conclusive, it is highly compelling and demands further investigation. Examples of cross cultural motifs in the form of glyphs, mounds, and earthworks are provided with mythic comparisons and contrasts. Counter arguments are provided throughout as well as strong debunking of prior archaeological biases rooted in Victorian, antiquated pseudoscience. Assumptions in the two models presented for plasma-arc-discharge mechanism are clearly listed, as well as known facts. Citations enable cross reference while the work focuses not on diffusion anthropology, but realistic atmospheric/astronomical plasmoid petroglyph formations recorded in rock.

Key words: EPEMC - Megafauna extinction - Birkeland current - arc-discharge - Moon - Younger Dryas

¹ The author refuses to use the term Adena, not out of protest for the community of Archaeology, but out of protest for the origin of the term. The mound for which an entire ancient and advanced culture in a cradle of civilization would be named, was ultimately destroyed; 'recovered out of existence.' This unconscionable act deserves no support. Therefore, the term is stricken from the title, and the author hopes future scientists will do the same.

² "Thus Allegheny seems most likely to have meant 'fine river' in the language of the Delawares, but they later told a story of a mythical tribe called the Allegewi who had lived on that river until defeated by the all-conquering Delawares. More often, when a common name became meaningless, the Indians, like other people, merely accepted it—"Just a name!" [sic] <https://archive.org/details/in.ernet.dli.2015.111746>

³ Exercising the "Extended" portion of EPEMC [1]

"How often have I said to you that when you have eliminated the impossible, whatever remains, however improbable, must be the truth?"⁴

"[Thomas] Jefferson, who often is referred to as the father of American archaeology, was fascinated with both mastodons and the Ice Age Americans. Unlike Franklin, [speaking about Big Bone Lick, Kentucky], Jefferson was convinced that people lived in the Americas at the same time mastodons were living at Big Bone Lick. His reasoning was based, in part, on an oral tradition of Delaware Indians, which he had recorded firsthand. During the American Revolution, Jefferson had met with a group of Delaware Warriors and asked them, "What happened to the great animal whose bones were found at the salt licks on the Ohio?" A Chief in the group stood up and said,

'In ancient times a herd of these tremendous animals came to the Big Bone Licks, and began a universal destruction of the bear, deer, elks, buffaloes, and other animals which had been created for the use of the Indians; that the Great Man above, looking down and seeing this, was so enraged that he seized his lightning, descended on the Earth, seated himself on a neighboring mountain, on a rock of which his seat and the print of his feet, and hurled his bolts among them till the whole were slaughtered, except the big bull who, presenting his forehead to the shafts, shook them off as they fell; but missing one at length, it wounded him in the side; whereon, springing round, he bounded over the Ohio, over the Wabash, the Illinois, and finally over the great lakes, where he is living at this day.'[sic]⁵

"Consider this account from the Ojibwa, a Native American people: The star with the long, wide tail is going to destroy the world some day when it comes low again. That's the comet called Long-Tailed Heavenly Climbing Star. It came down here once, thousands of years ago. Just like the sun. It had radiation and burning heat in its tail. The comet burned everything to the ground. There wasn't a thing left. Indian people were here before that happened, living on the earth. But things were wrong; a lot of people had abandoned the spiritual path. The holy spirit warned them a long time before the comet came. Medicine men told everyone to prepare. Things were wrong with nature on the earth ... Then that comet went through here. It had a long, wide tail and it burned up everything. It flew so low the tail scorched the earth ... The comet made a different world. After that survival was hard work. The weather was colder than before."⁶

"Moving to South America, we encounter the Chibchas of central Colombia. According to their myths, they had originally lived as savages, without laws, agriculture or religion. Then one day there appeared among them an old man of a different race. He wore a thick long beard and his name was Bochica. He taught the Chibchas how to build huts and live together in society.

"His wife, who was very beautiful and named Chia, appeared after him, but she was wicked and enjoyed thwarting her husband's altruistic efforts. Since she could not overcome his power directly, she used magical means to cause a great flood in which the majority of the population died. Bochica was very angry and exiled Chia from the earth to the sky, where she became the moon given the task of lighting the nights. He also

⁴ Sherlock Holmes (Sir Arthur Conan Doyle)

⁵ "In Search of Ice Age Americans," K Tankersley, p 51-52

⁶ "Magicians of the Gods: The Forgotten Wisdom of Earth's Lost Civilization", G Hancock

caused the waters of the flood to dissipate and brought down the few survivors from the mountains where they had taken refuge.

"Thereafter he gave them laws, taught them to cultivate the land and instituted the worship of the sun with periodic festivals, sacrifices and Pilgrimages..."

Continuing...

"When they were discovered, the Tupinamba Indians of Brazil venerated a series of civilizing or creator heroes. The first of these heroes was Monan (ancient, old) who was said to have been the creator of mankind but who then destroyed the world with flood and fire..."

"The Araucanians of pre-Colombian[sic] Chile preserved a tradition that there was once a flood which very few Indians escaped. The survivors took refuge on a high mountain called Theg-theg (the thundering or the glittering) which had three peaks and the ability to float on water.

"In the far south of the continent a Yamana legend from Tierra del Fuego states: The moon woman caused the flood. This was at the time of the great upheaval ... Moon was filled with hatred towards human beings ...

"At that time everybody drowned with the exception of those few who were able to escape to the five mountain peaks that the water did not cover.

"Another Tierra del Fuegan tribe, the Pehuenche, associate the flood with a prolonged period of darkness: The sun and the moon fell from the sky and the world stayed that way, without light, until finally two giant condors carried both the sun and the moon back up to the sky."⁷

"Battle with the Giant Animals

"In the world before this one, the People and the animals turned to evil and forgot their connection to the Creator. Resolving to destroy the world and start over, the Creator warned a few good People to flee to the highest mountaintops. When they were safe, the Creator sang the Song of Destruction and sent down fierce Thunderbirds to wage a great battle against the other humans and the giant animals.

"They fought for a long time because the evil humans and the animals had become very powerful, and neither side could gain an advantage. Finally, at the height of the battle, the Thunderbirds suddenly threw down their most powerful thunderbolts all at once. The fiery blast shook the entire world, toppling mountain ranges and setting forests and prairies ablaze. The flames leapt up to the sky in all directions, sparing only the few People on the highest peaks. It was so hot that the world's lakes boiled and dried up before their eyes. Even the rocks glowed red-hot, and the giant animals and evil people burned up where they stood."⁸

"After the Earth finished baking, the Creator began to make a new world, and as the Creator chanted the Song of Creation, it began to rain. The Creator sang louder and it rained harder until the rivers overflowed their banks and surged across the baked landscape. Finally, the Creator stamped the Earth and with a great quake the Earth split open, sending great torrents of water surging across the entire world, until only a few mountain peaks stood above the flood, sheltering the few People who had survived.

"After the waters cleansed the Earth and subsided, the Creator sent the surviving People out to populate the new world, our world today, warning them not to fall into evil, or the Creator would destroy the world again. As the People went out over the land, they found the bleached bones of the giant animals buried in rock and mud all over the world. People still find them today in the Dakota Badlands.

*RETOLD FROM ERDOES AND ORTIZ, 1984*⁹ [sic]

⁷ "Fingerprints of the Gods, G Hancock, p. 188

⁸ *le, Step Potential/Voltage*

⁹ "Cycle of Cosmic Catastrophes: How a Stone-Age Comet Changed the Course of the World," Firestone et al., 2006

Figure 1 - "Big Sink" "Astrobleme" (Versailles Crater, KY)¹⁰

¹⁰ Neither a sink, nor an astrobleme. It is a Thunderbolt crater (the stamp of his foot), and a medium/healthy sized, short lived one, at that (1640 m diameter). In this paper my calculations are for much smaller henge-sized Vajra, around 1000m²

Synopsis

"It is a capital mistake to theorize before one has data. Insensibly one begins to twist facts to suit theories, instead of theories to suit facts."¹¹

Sir Arthur was, indeed, ahead of his time in terms of the discussion of modern forensics. Forensics is the science of deduction of the scene of a crime.¹² Although it may be a crime to witness a culture be misexplained, that is not the purpose of this paper. Instead it is to piece together a newer theory which may, in the end, endeavor to cover all - not only some - of the facts. At the time that the Alleghewi-Hopewell, and all subsequent cultures and ancestral "archaic" cultures were first being discovered and written about, including even up until the 1960s when the Sioux gave testimony about their legends (some of which coincided with Cherokee and even aboriginal Australian testimony), it was indeed impossible to think that such stories were anything but myth and 'superstitious' religion.¹³

Nevermind that although Victorian era archaeology was stooped heavily in the mythos of Biblical "superstition" and, let me dare say, racist ideas (eugenics, skull measuring, etc...), the idea that the natives of America, hitherto considered uncivilized 'savages' were capable of logic and reasoning, and of complex geometric mathematics^{14 15} having not arisen from one of the traditional "Four Cradles of Civilization"¹⁶ was 'impossible.'

But clearly it is **not impossible**, nor shall we see it improbable¹⁷. Furthermore, since the work of Dr. Anthony Peratt of Los Alamos Laboratories in 1991¹⁸, even some of the most fantastic legends such as the Great Man destroying the mastodons¹⁹ at Big Bone Lick are no longer 'impossible.'^{20 21} The question remains, are they improbable?²²

It is the contention of this author that **only**²³ plasma electric-arc discharge^{24 25 26} phenomena²⁷, as evidenced in laboratory work,²⁸ legends worldwide²⁹, geoglyphs and petroglyphs, earthwork effigies, and even statues can account for the strange shapes, improbable construction of non-essential mega earthworks, and most importantly, a vector of extinction that would be generally-selective³⁰ and cross-species, yet *ineffective against all mammalian and*

¹¹ Sherlock Holmes (Sir Arthur Conan Doyle)

¹² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Forensic_science

¹³ Literally people were not allowed to practice outside their sciences. So geologists, Egyptologists, comparative mythologists, and Mayanologists simply did not *mix* archaeology or archaeo-astronomy.

¹⁴ https://www.nps.gov/mwac/hopewell/v6n2/doc/newark_earthwork_complex.doc

¹⁵ https://www.nps.gov/mwac/hopewell/v6n2/doc/v6n2_all.doc

¹⁶ Egypt, Mesopotamia, China, India; obviously this list falls short of all reality and reason. [2] [3]

¹⁷ This issue reminds the author of the issues pre-2015 that existed between archaeology and Atlantology, which should, by now, be rapidly closing the gaps. See the author's paper, "Unboxing Atlantis" [4]

¹⁸ https://drive.google.com/file/d/0ByRZ_FN_vit_Yk5pNnRPdFFNNFU/view

¹⁹ https://drive.google.com/open?id=0ByRZ_FN_vit_bWVtbzduY2l3X1Bqc3d4VnVvaHNNQjJzNGo4

²⁰ https://drive.google.com/open?id=0ByRZ_FN_vit_TnJOUWxLTzZub2QwNzJ2LWFGSEZ4RWFqYjVn

²¹ https://drive.google.com/open?id=0ByRZ_FN_vit_MFIyRjNqWkEyTHRUTjNSaXFOVWJGLWExt2NV

Note - this paper rules out terrestrial lightning, but not extraterrestrial lightning (cosmic ray thunderbolts)

²² https://drive.google.com/open?id=0ByRZ_FN_vit_UVhnR0x3eXJTdWFFcUlnOGtUTIVfa21mU0xz

²³ To the author's knowledge there are no coinciding VEI9+ events which would provide a competing theory.

²⁴ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tRV1e5_tB6Y&index=4&t=4152s

²⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mPcF40vBqzs>

²⁶ <http://www.mungoflix.com/mungoflix/ancient-destructions/>

²⁷ The author here will lean heavily upon the citations in his previous works at <http://uky.academia.edu/shifucareaga> [4]

and [6], both of which have ample Appendices of definitions, citations, etc... to handle the PEM portion of EPEMC. There is also a great deal of plasma-electromagnetic science mentioned in [2]. See Appendix C for more information.

²⁸ <https://drive.google.com/open?id=15P5sRxhnJU2YEno8auBqOjZsBHzTC2ec>

²⁹ https://drive.google.com/open?id=1lzP_5cCdCIVIVbJKQ0yxUjNACZmYFEfv

³⁰ Electric comets, although similar in power level (especially as a swarm of impacts), are just not general enough and selective enough. Airbursts such as Tunguska and Melbourne 1491 do not appear to be selective in their destruction at all.

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/0ByRZ_FN_vit_X1ZWVFNwMTNtcm5

For more information on Electric comets see P Jupp, and <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=34wtt2EUToo>

avian species. In particular, **this phenomenon is called 'step potential.'**³¹ The deadliness of step potential is already well established in electrical safety literature and media reporting.^{32 33 34 35 36}

By analyzing the petroglyphs of Kentucky³⁷ and similar locations, where the supposed 'crime' is to have taken place, comparing it with evidence from other cultures, with large earthwork shapes, and laboratory findings regarding plasma³⁸ and electric discharge phenomena, we can piece together the evidence for megafauna extinction *via step potential*. The author proposes that the entire community do this in earnest. More importantly, we can shed far more probable theoretical light upon the construction, and give hints or suggestions as to use of large effigy mounds. Key to this investigation will in particular be the (A) serpent mounds³⁹, (B) Eagle and Alligator mound⁴⁰, and (C) a number of glyphs found in Kentucky and Ohio. There will be cross-cultural comparison, however, from around the world.⁴¹

To do this, the author will be deconstructing and critiquing previous theories made apriori - before facts - became widely available. Indeed, many discoveries have occurred within the last ten or even five years. Most of the conclusions guiding interpretations were made over thirty years ago during which time, even "Clovis First" officially failed as an archaeological theory⁴². It is therefore not the intent of the author to dissect any particular individual, but only make it known that perhaps the archaeology and anthropology previously inherited from the Victorian age contained highly illogical, lazy, and even racist conclusions about a people that, in the end synopsis, were simply completely foreign and unknown to them. Mankind always historically fears and places doubt upon the Unknown.

This has naturally set up a situation where archaeology, through the desire to study facts has, in effect, served as a mechanism of post-colonial control⁴³. They have been gathering data but hiding away that which does not suit the narrative already made, and certainly not providing access to the wide public all of the facts, and relics.

³¹ Graphic analysis of this is presented in the accompanying presentation, made at the AKHA, September 2017

https://drive.google.com/open?id=1F1UtMW-J7_GUybY58355xWOLQ3DLjdnkcOMXAa11xM

³² <http://time.com/4474793/lightning-cows-killed-texas/>

³³ <http://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/2016/08/31/third-herd-of-animals-killed-by-freak-lightning-bolt-in-a-week/>

³⁴ <https://www.theverge.com/2016/8/29/12690402/lightning-strike-kills-norway-reindeer-death-why-science>

³⁵

<https://roadtrippers.com/us/american-fork-ut/points-of-interest/654-sheep-killed-by-lightning-on-this-spot?lat=40.80972&lng=-96.67528&z=5>

³⁶ <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2016/jun/22/lightning-strikes-kill-dozens-in-india>

³⁷ Coy, Fuller et al... [15]

³⁸ Plasma is often called the 'fourth state of matter' or 'ionized gas.' But in point of fact it is the norm of matter yet found, accounting for 99% of observed mass in the Universe. It is not a gas but an excited state of energetic behavior that can exhibit four modes: dark mode, low energy, high energy/lightning like, and solar (which might include a process for fusion). Only the latter two are known to alter geological formations in lab, while the low energy kind is implicated in auroras and light bulbs, etc... The dark mode of plasma discharge occurs through what are termed "Birkeland currents" and transport massive voltage over low current between larger cosmic bodies where the energy is transformed into higher current and therefore energetic events. Such as has been observed at the poles of Saturn and Jupiter, or on Ceres, Io, Enceladus, or the comet 67P where electric arc machining has been recorded to remove tons of material in a matter of days or weeks, depending on the influence of the sun's electric field. [1] [2] [4] [6]

³⁹ Great Serpent Mound of Ohio, Boyd Stone Serpent Effigy Mound of KY, and others. LiDAR and maps shown later.

<https://moundbuilder.blogspot.com/p/30-serpent-mounds-in-north-america.html>

⁴⁰ Detailed analysis of asymmetry in Part 2

⁴¹ Table 2 & Appendix B

⁴² www.bradshawfoundation.com/america/clovis_first/

⁴³ In KY, the Shannon Indian Mound has never been excavated, as it is an active (but historic) church graveyard. However, Indian Knoll NHL (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Indian_Knoll) was ransacked for more than 1,200 remains (most of which were destroyed), many artifacts, etc... and there isn't even so much as a plaque to commemorate the location, which is still desecrated to this day. The site goes back to the Egyptian era and should have been considered an antiquities site.

Whereas the remains of Tutankhamen are lauded and celebrated, and children can visit the remains in museums behind secure glass, there is not even a single exhibit within the quad-state area for the Archaic period relics that have been taken from Indian Knoll, the Green river Shell Middens, or any of the other Allegewi-Hopewell mounds of KY. There is a Mississippian culture museum at the desecrated site at Wickliffe State Historic Site. One of the buildings rests *inside* a mound. The remains were on display until 2006 when they were finally reconsecrated in 2012.

<http://wkms.org/post/public-ceremony-honors-wickliffe-mounds-builders>

Such examples have made archaeology into a scientific version of grave-robbing.

This most certainly could not have been the original intent of any 20th Century scientist. However, it is what has occurred⁴⁴.

Ultimately this paper is an attempt to provide new key insights, and vindication for the victims of this 'crime' who have been, up until now, ignored in the data collection process vis-a-vis their Voice. Only their remains and refuse of their villages have been considered, or more recently their observations about the sun and moon⁴⁵. (Clearly an advanced culture would know the basics about the sun and moon, but that would never be the end of the deduction, if a culture be as advanced with geometry as the Allegewi were.) As for picto and petroglyphs little is said, except to attach the 'animal' effigies upon museum displays to prove that they were artistic (and therefore civilized). As for stone works and effigies, even less; and the least of all is for rock shelters and walls.^{46 47}

Yet, the strange nature of their glyphs, contain little of typical human concerns, or even remarkably pornographic or agricultural references, and instead we see shapes such as spirals, concentric circles, giant people with bizarre heads and uneven bodies, therianthropes, gods, spirits, shaman, and of course, 'feet,' remaining widely unknown to the public and unused in the explanations of the people⁴⁸. It is probably because, in sum estimation of the author, the archaeological community does not know how to interpret them, or why they should consider anything other than the post-modern labels and filters used by those who first found and essentially, guessed, at their purposes. There being no incentive, there is no impetus to consider widely the facts and testimony.

The purpose of this paper is not only to deconstruct but to constructively criticise, and provide wider testimony from many historic tribes, and introduce a number of tangential evidences. Not to be a complete theory but simply a more complete hypothesis which can then, being understood, renew with vigor the efforts of archeologists and anthropologists to discern (with greater care and increased interest) the web of data that is now emerging in the Ohio River valley, the Amazonian de-forested floor, and of course in the "Old World."

By re-compiling the data to a more perfect fit, rather than smudging the curve afterwards, the author contends that we shall find a narrative that is not only more probable, but more logical, when weighed against the testimony of the Old World, the lab, and the sheer facts of human behavior, as well as the obvious physical evidence (or in some cases, recordings of it if the original be destroyed, such as Biggs Site⁴⁹ mound and nearby Old Fort⁵⁰ complex, or the earthworks of Peter's Village⁵¹ in Lexington).

⁴⁴ At one point the head of the Smithsonian Institution itself had never even heard of the Hopewellian peoples.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=itCWu-m-23E>

⁴⁵

<https://irp-cdn.multiscreensite.com/7b1aa4fb/files/uploaded/Serpent%20Mound%20Geometry%20Paper%20FINAL3%5B4381347%5D.pdf>

⁴⁶ <https://anthrosource.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1525/aa.1969.71.5.02a00540>

⁴⁷ https://www.getty.edu/conservation/publications_resources/pdf_publications/pdf/rock_art_cultural_treasure.pdf

⁴⁸ Appendix B of this paper will contain many such examples. More will be found in "On the Origins of Religions" [2] (Appendix B)

⁴⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Biggs_Site

⁵⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Portsmouth_Earthworks

⁵¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mount_Horeb_Earthworks_Complex

Introduction

Why Jefferson trusted Native testimony; the history of mounds, mining, mummies, and mastodons in Kentucky.

Table 1 - Chart of illogical juxtapositions and deductions about archaic and woodland era aboriginals

Observed Advanced Cultural Aspects	Perceived Weaknesses of Allegewi Culture
Advanced geometrical and surveying skills ⁵²	Could not discover the wheel ⁵³
Worship of animals in complex ritualistic practice	Decreased or absent capability in accurate effigy depictions (despite earlier precise depictions)
Complex chemical and agricultural processes ⁵⁴	Weak or absent strategic fortification techniques ⁵⁵
Advanced pottery and art forms	Difficulty building lasting civilizations ⁵⁶
Industrial and trade networks ⁵⁷	Simplistic hunter-gatherer tribal society
Use of sophisticated numerology, such as 51.8 degree angle ^{58 59} , as reflected in Giza pyramid slope, ⁶⁰ showing engineering and design skills ⁶¹	Inability to make clear, clean cut effigies and art work due to a lack of advancement or sophistication (literally: neolithic or paleolithic)

Why should anyone, including Thomas Jefferson, believe the testimony given by the Delaware Indian chief? For three reasons, it should be considered.

⁵² <https://arxiv.org/pdf/0706.1325.pdf>

⁵³ The Wheel of the Creator was a well known shape or glyph world-wide. All the Saturn Myth relations are contained in the large table generated by the author. The lack of writing inherited does not diminish the simple fact that the entire world saw this formation, and the Allegewi-Hopewell and Mississippians undoubtedly knew about the wheel, but found it too sacred to use. https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/118Tbu6mdDBTRaYJyBtLwMSkN4-Usz02j_tR_pKx6uos/edit?usp=sharing

⁵⁴ <https://chequamegonhistory.wordpress.com/2017/05/04/ancient-garden-beds-of-michigan/>

⁵⁵ For example, at the Fort Ancient Park, Ohio... this is clearly **not** a military fort. But that does not mean that they did not build stockades, such as the Cahokians did. They just did not live inside forts as was originally thought when Ft. Ancient culture was named. (Surely it should be renamed).

⁵⁶ Archaic cultures lasted in areas something 3,000-6,000 years, even in KY. However (without cataclysms) the current model for the Allegewi and Hopewell cultures are that they struggled to build long-term societies due mostly to war, disease, and agricultural decline. However, many of the important times in these periods are punctuated by known cataclysmic periods from the Old World: 5,500 YBP, 3,600 YBP, 2,600 YBP, and 1,700 YBP. The author agrees that smallpox introduced to the New World is a reasonable vector for the beginning of the total end for Pre-historic tribes. C. 1550-1650 CE

⁵⁷ Copper, pearl, mica, fluorite, etc...

⁵⁸ <https://moundbuilder.blogspot.com/2014/08/advanced-mathematics-used-in.html>

⁵⁹ http://www.allanstime.com/Spiritual/Hopewell_Civilization_Great_Octagon/

⁶⁰ <http://www.tony5m17h.net/pyramid.html>

⁶¹ Randall Carlson makes the point that the Universal Language at the time of Babylon is symbology and sacred numerology. Chris Dunn has recorded fascinating engineering and machining evidence in his second book "Lost Technologies of Ancient Egypt"

- The first is that the chief had no reason to lie or make up an outlandish story. Quite the contrary; the chief stood and made an oration of the chronicle indicating that he firmly believed the entire story, and was giving an account of a shortened narrative; probably an oral tradition passed down father to son and amongst the whole tribe in ritual song as the Vedas are in India to this day⁶².
- The second deduction that can be made comes from the organization of the narrative. The beasts arrived and then destroyed the natural habitat, and this (and not mankind) angered the “Great Man” who brought with him the lightning to punish and slaughter the animals gives testimony to the chronology of the events witnessed.

Some time in the distant archaic past, the paleoindian ancestors witnessed the arrival of creatures that they were unable to rid themselves of, despite the competition. This almost immediately eliminates the paleoindians as the source of the extinction event⁶³. Some stretching of the imagination could permit, for the moment, that a Herculean type supreme-hunter, or a Thor-like individual could have done this deed, except perhaps the failure to kill the final bull. However, there does not seem to be any indication here that, given the opportunity to take credit for ridding themselves and the creation around them of the pests that megafauna appear to represent, they wouldn't. In point of fact, if the megafauna were pests and their ancestors had killed them off, some sort of legend with a name of the warrior would be attached⁶⁴, whether or not the warrior was real or the name even remotely similar.
- Thirdly, the detail that the Great Man *descended* and sat upon a mountain and left an imprint of himself and his *feet* indicates that this was a supernatural event (to them), and not indicative of human legend.⁶⁵

Moreover that the event took some time is evident from the fact that the God hurled the bolts until *at length* all but the bull was strewn dead. This indicates a great storm of storms, and an event which would, by itself, account for the need of the Cherokee to become the “People of the Cave.”⁶⁶ One cannot help but draw comparisons to the stone cave cities: Derinkuyu, Cappadocia, Uchisar, and of course, Mesa Verde which have inexplicable, debatable, or controversial origins.⁶⁷

Such an event would be indelibly marked upon the psyche of the natives, in particular the individuals responsible with lore and wisdom, such as chiefs, doctors, shaman, wise-women, wizards, etc... to tell and recount the story in song form, exactly, for generation upon generation, as the Rig Veda has been in Tamil India since the time of the sinking of Dwarka/Dvaraka and reputedly Kumari Kandem (Lemuria)⁶⁸. Such events, if/when they occurred would leave deep psychological scars upon any society and culture⁶⁹. The advancement or alleged 'lack of advancement' (perhaps chosen abandonment of advances) would only affect the records, but not the actual imprinting. Such is the case we see with Hopi, Sioux, and Cherokee peoples, these are just some

⁶² <https://www.jstor.org/stable/833861>

⁶³ After all, if North America was so sparsely populated, how could mankind extinguish all the mastodons and mammoths, both, which are more difficult to hunt, than the bison of which there were millions? OF course they could not, and would not, because they do not have Western value systems. However, the “White Man” most definitely tried to extinguish all of the bison (and yet still failed). On an interesting note, natives in Africa and India have never extinguished all elephants and typically did not hunt them, but avoided and respected them (because they are incredibly dangerous and thick-skinned).

⁶⁴ Such as in Akkad, the epic of Gilgamesh slaying the Bull of Heaven. Such heroics would undoubtedly be celebrated. Here there is no indication of that.

⁶⁵ It was also not *parts* of the Great Man, or multiple gods, but a singular event.

⁶⁶ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cherokee>

⁶⁷ http://www.cracked.com/article_20206_5-shockingly-advanced-ancient-buildings-that-shouldnt-exist.html

⁶⁸ [4]

⁶⁹ Thus we see the stories world-wide. [2]

of the cultures which record stories that reflect the tales found in Sumeria, China, India and famously, in the Bible.

The Delaware story *alone* means nothing remarkable. Against a backdrop of stone age, iron age, megalithic and even very advanced mathematical cultures (like Egypt or Sumeria), and especially considering the Greek myth of Zeus and the Norse myth of Odin, it means a great deal more. But where it goes from interesting to intriguing is in considering the vast presence of the beasts in question at Big Bone Lick, and the relatively few skeletal remains found in KY showing signs of meat harvest.⁷⁰

The general explanation of human involvement in the extinction process of so many numbers of animals is already quite unbelievable. Animals which almost certainly would be beyond the use as game, (such as smilodon, American Lion, short-faced bear, etc...) are found as infrequently stuck in sinkholes with signs of human hunting as are mammoths and mastodons. The main difference is that a few of the latter have been found, and this is used to justify the extinction continent-wide, despite the simultaneous maintained position that Paleoindians were sparsely populated and unevenly so, throughout the continent in the Archaic periods. For not a single specimen to survive in isolation, (excepting a strange unrelated milieu of ice age species), despite the vastness of unexplored, uninhabited, mountainous wilderness of North America is quite improbable. Yet it happened.⁷¹

It is also quite improbable that a viral or bacterial vector selectively eliminated these species. That has, heretofore, left only the possibility of impact⁷².

Yet the main astrophysical problems to be found are all pre-Younger Dryas⁷³ or have massive problems of vector alignment, crater formation and genesis, improbable shape, and improper spread. They also cannot explain, if such an event were widespread, how it would spare the lives of black bears, deer, condors, mountain lions⁷⁴, and wolves.

The important thing to keep in mind is that most extinction events take time and are multifactorial. Usually, a first event severely reduces population size, limiting contact between mating pairs and reducing chances of generational survival, as well as impacting food sources and food chains related to survival in a complex environment. Add to that the pursuit of hunters who might actually be starving, or competitors (such as grizzly versus short-faced bear), and a changing climate (temperatures dropping 20 C then rising later by the same amount - see Figure 2), and there is no doubt that the possible could make the improbable occur. But, given the testimony *and* the highly logical vector that step potential provides, it is clear that the Delaware chief's testimony bears consideration. If only we could then find the evidence for such an event, the size of the discharge power, and compare with known step potential situations! Such is the endeavor of this paper in Part 4.

⁷⁰ There's actually so few nationwide that the issue has been quietly swept under the rug, probably because it embarrasses the narrative. <https://contemplativemammoth.com/2015/04/21/why-are-there-so-few-ice-age-megafaunal-kill-sites/> In reality the mainstream has no agreement as to an extinction vector and it is doubtful that any sizable percentage of archaeologists believe humans could really wipe out all the herds of all these various species *and* be sparsely populated. Disease is a more agreed upon vector. But of course, cross species diseases are rare, and rarely endemic.

⁷¹ Another commonly blamed vector is sudden climate change. While this might work for possibly vulnerable species like Ground Sloths, which may have had difficulties finding mates in winterized conditions, it wouldn't for scavengers like the American lion, nor for battle hardened species like various types of elephants. There was a smaller, pygmy mammoth which went extinct in South America. Obviously it was well adapted to heat, and was not affected by cold. The world's vegetation did not disappear. But it was mentioned at the Tiahuanaco, but not at sites after the destruction that destroyed Tiahuanaco. <http://www.science-frontiers.com/sf068/sf068b07.htm>

⁷² To account for climate change and the carbon layer around the world. Ibid.

⁷³

⁷⁴ Mountain lions and leopards in Asia, are particularly vulnerable to breeding miscues and the difficulties of rearing young in harsh extremes. Too harsh and cubs simply cannot survive.

Figure 2 - Younger Dryas Climate Change (Greenland data)⁷⁵; credit: Azimuth Project

Coming back to more recent history, it is also remarkable, to discuss the unique facts about Kentucky that also point to an alternative historical and archaic past. There are examples of early mining in caves for various types of minerals (indicating perhaps an economy or even industrial use⁷⁶). There are reports of mummification, both hearsay and scholarly reporting⁷⁷, in an area not known (proven or believed) for this aspect of highly advanced civilization. There is also, of course as is well known, the history of mound building. The most curious aspect being not the fact of its existence but of its decline in usage and even decay in technique⁷⁸. Whereas in a former bygone era, a sudden arising of the use of earthworks and mound culture occurred, first with soil, and then later with stone (or perhaps this is precisely backwards), and yet the practice fell into disuse. Why?

The other curious fact about Allegetwi culture's behavior was that, despite generally believed sparse populations harvesting what would amount to middling levels of caloric harvest compared to modern techniques, that they would spend inordinate amounts of time and calories in a situation where ostensibly various dangers remained building these earthworks. Yet these geometric earthworks bear no signs of use for dwelling or fortification, and very commonly not even bodies or signs of ritualized tomb formation⁷⁹.

This suggests two things. The first is that this is probably a separate culture from the aforementioned mummification culture, which almost assuredly preceded or succeeded the mound cultures.⁸⁰ The second is that the mounds that are found with large numbers of bodies probably were the results of warfare, as opposed to the small mounds which may have been attempts to seal up leaders of tribes or possibly diseased corpses.

⁷⁵ How can an impact swarm cause both a decrease in temperature and a sudden melting of ice? The proponents of the comet theory have to pick and choose. But the moon arrival theory can account for the entire span as a matter of re-conditioning cycles and entrainment into electro-tidal lock. To this day the moon is not in a perfectly stable elliptical orbit, which indicates its wily behavior. As it happens, Janus is the two faced Roman god of destruction (Hindu: Shiva), and lo: the moon has two faces.

⁷⁶ See R Osman, "Graves of the Golden Bear"

⁷⁷ Rafinesque, etc...

⁷⁸ Compare with similar issues in later dynastic pyramids; assuming the Giza pyramids are dynastic in origin.

⁷⁹ <http://www.ancientohiotrail.org/sites/fort-ancient>

⁸⁰ Fawn Hoof is reputedly only a few hundreds of years old. Other red-haired mummies held at the UK Museum are also similarly believed to be young, perhaps early Shawnee. Mound builders buried bodies, not mummies.

Due to new evidence (or old in many cases) coming together, even in a haphazard and unclear way begs the question, "If there is smoke, where's the fire?" Indeed, what it means also is this, that if the Historic tribes bother or cared to remember such a detail, it was considered more important than even recalling the names or language or writing (if it existed at all), or the songs of the Allegewi.

Yet the events which orchestrated the end of the Archaic paleoindians, the megafauna, etc... and frightened away cultures until the arrival of the Allegewi were so complete that even given massive earthwork structures - (which the author alleges are recounting the tales of such events in the sky) - all that could remain after such wide destruction and warfare during the late woodland times, was the **most important** tales to be told from elder to young chief, etc... Only the tales which had the most direct bearing on the histories of a nomadic people that had not regained a foothold on civilization after the successive events of extinction, then cataclysm (mostly happening in the Sinai area but felt worldwide), then warfare, then invasion⁸¹ - only *important* stories would survive.

Early skeletal remains, mummies, giant bones etc... were taken (certainly by the Smithsonian and other collectors, as is well known), and possibly lost or destroyed. However, the mounds, mines, and gardens remain. Both, however, through looting and "recovery into inexistence," have become almost fairy tales themselves.

In Fayette County, Kentucky, there exist only sparse remains of an earthworks which is perhaps older than the Newark and Chillicothe earthworks, perhaps of the same period as the Great Serpent Mound (~1500-1600 BCE)⁸². However, all that remains are the singular mounds, such as Mt. Horeb. Yet even then, the very shape of these mounds when compared with their petroglyph and pictoglyph cousins (from the area and including the Southwestern USA), are remarkable for their repetitious themes: spirals, concentric circles (two or three), "serpents"⁸³, square and circle adjoining, obtuse octagon, hexagon with circle, circle on edge of circle, etc...

These themes are found also, but not limited to the cultures shown in Table 2 (include pictures)

Table 2 - Effigy Themes that Cross-correlate irrespective of geography and linguistics

Culture	Earthworks/Stoneworks	Petro/picto/hieroglyphs	Another Culture
Allegewi	Mt. Horeb, Lexington, KY Cosmic egg over Atum-Re (Ra)		
Hopewell	Newark Earthworks, OH	Big Sinking Creek, KY	Amazon:

⁸¹ Possibly by industrious and economic minded and certainly heavily armed Europeans, then more warfare followed by disease and incessant warfare; see Troxel, "Footprints of the Welsh Indians"

⁸² Dated via comparison with Biblical records as well as form and function.

⁸³ Though the shapes are generally of a serpent quality, the lack of egg-eating species of remarkable importance as would be found in India or Africa, in reality these earthworks and glyphs signify a cometary body. Except in the case of the Great Serpent Mound which is an effigy of remembrance of the "great comet" Venus, as it left its conjunction with Mars (spiral tail). This effigy has also been recorded elsewhere. The use of the term 'serpent mound' remains the most convenient shorthand.

⁸⁴ [26] Note: this is clearly not a fort. The intrusion of water into the earthworks is likely not accidental ("Waters of Chaos")

⁸⁵ [15]

	Credit: Squire & Davis	Credit: Coy, et al... ⁸⁶	Credit: NatGeo
Paracas	Cone-head Man, Peru 		
		Credit: Coy et al...	Credit: Quora
Nazca	"Hummingbird" ⁸⁷ 		
	Credit: APAH ⁸⁸	Credit: Coy et al...	Credit: Pinterest
Amazonia			

⁸⁶ Note the "turtle" is 5 legged (compare to Alligator Mound), and the body is the strange octagon shape

⁸⁷ Most assuredly not a hummingbird but a "Thunderbird"

⁸⁸ <https://apah.wikispaces.com/Earthworks>

British Isles	<p>Avebury, England</p> <p>Credit: Squire & Davis (upside down)</p>		
Pueblo	<p>Pueblo Bonito</p> <p>Credit: Wikipedia⁸⁹</p>		
Mexico	<p>Chichen Itza, Mexico</p> <p>Miss. Culture Credit: Wikipedia⁹⁰</p>		
England	<p>Knowlton, England</p> <p>Credit: Dreamstime</p>		

⁸⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Troyville_Earthworks

⁹⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Anna_Site

Ireland	<p>Tara Henges</p>		
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This type of comparative exercise can go on and on, there is no shortage of cross-cultural examples that are clear reflections. Although EPEMC contains diffusionist elements, the author does not maintain these cultures knew of one another nor were guided by Atlanteans or Virocochans, etc... but instead they saw this images within the sky!

The cultural and resource rape of the Bluegrass state (KY) is more severe than the neighboring states, probably due to the time period of settlement, and also the recklessness of the settlers (within two generations all the bison in Kentucky were extinguished and over 90% of the forest was leveled by 1850⁹³). The use of caves and cave remains, mound remains, grave goods, for museums and local tourism is well documented.⁹⁴

Sometimes priceless remains and relics were shipped off to museums in New York or in England and France; sometimes they were merely held in the backs of University museums. This also includes large numbers of fossil remains (though to this day archaeological digs reveal new fossils at the park, as recent as 2016 at Big Bone Lick⁹⁵).

Meanwhile, notorious rock formations go unprotected (see: Red Bird cave⁹⁶), including rock shelters, cave dwellings, carvings, etc... It is no irony that two of the most littered waterfalls in the state are Indian Falls and Indian Bathtub Falls⁹⁷. In some cases, such as Indian Knoll National Historic Landmark, there is not even a plaque to commemorate the details of the Archaic or Woodland site. In other cases, that is all there is, such as at Eskippakithiki "Indian Old Fields." At no site anywhere in the state other than Wickliffe such as displayed in Ohio or Illinois, or at Angel Mounds in Indiana dedicated to preservation of this unique heritage. Also, there is no established research center exploring the history to a depth seen in fields such as Maya studies or Egyptology. Such an endeavor is unheard of in Kentucky. Then, It is no surprise that while the Great Serpent Mound is preserved in a state park and has numerous archaeologists' eyes, the Boyd County Serpent Mound

⁹¹ <https://trailhiker.wordpress.com/2014/08/09/tour-of-the-hill-of-tara-and-newgrange/>

⁹² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ancestral_Puebloans

⁹³ "How the West was Lost: The Transformation of Kentucky from Daniel Boone to Henry Clay," Stephon Aron, 1999

⁹⁴ <https://traffickingculture.org/encyclopedia/case-studies/all/>

⁹⁵ https://www.kentuckypress.com/live/title_detail.php?titleid=2090#.Wz_BiadKjrc

⁹⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Red_Bird_River_Petroglyphs

⁹⁷ Author's data, Hidden Destinations in KY project, unpublished.

and the Spratt Stone Serpent in Frenchburg, Kentucky are partially destroyed, and still owned by private entities which have allowed only a single study to be performed on the former⁹⁸.

The unique history of mound culture in Kentucky is as rare an opportunity for archaeological discovery as can be found in the Yucatan. It is just as exotic, and in many ways more so⁹⁹. Moreover, the direct interaction of early American archaeologists with natives (especially as they intermarried with whites in the 1800s) is a great opportunity to do what cannot be done in many of the most remote locations of the world. The destruction was ostensibly so complete no direct testimony can be provided (Orkney, for example): compare myth with record and create sky models that can either verify or deny the testimony of Old World cultures (such as Sumerian cuneiform, Bible, and Egypt).

Ultimately the issue comes down to why natives, especially the Allegewi and their immediate ancestors recorded the glyphs and dug the earthworks, and whether or not their testimony is to be believed. The author maintains the original point which is that they had no reason to lie, nor to maintain such a story for so many generations, if it was not considered important.

In a curious way we cannot believe the Allegewi story without Old World records and scientific breakthroughs in plasma science. Yet, we cannot believe Old World stories without the excellent shapes and recordings found in the Ohio River Valley. In particular, the *feet* glyphs (discussed in Part 2).

Figure 3 - Carolina Bays vector analysis; Credit: LiDAR

⁹⁸ The site survey on Spratt was provided to State Archaeology, who did nothing with the data, and the site was consequently further ruined by logging trucks. The Third serpent "mound" 15La34 remains unlocated (at the time of writing) and unknown, except perhaps to the author.

⁹⁹ While we have translated Mayan and Aztec; no one knows what is written on the Gaitskill Allegewi tablet from Mt. Sterling, KY.

Figure 4 - Multiple Issues in Carolina Bays theory; Credit: Tatum (Author edited)

- 3 different general vectors (see below for distance issue created), some vastly different.
- The ages of the craters (judged by erosion, which should be similar in the area to each other)
- Crater chaining
- Crater clustering
- Fill in ridges to what should be **empty** craters (so how did the material come up and form a perfect wall)
- Curving crater chains, with inexplicable valleys opposite a gorge.
- Ridiculously flat basins, which is statistically impossible when erosion into shatter cones is considered.
Larger cone holes should have some emptiness, and small holes should be almost flat, even the ridges.

Figure 5 - Continued Analysis with aging shown; Credit: Bowman (Author edited)

Table 3 - Comparison of Angles and Resultant Vectors¹⁰⁰

<i>Angle</i>	<i>Distanced by X</i>	<i>Distanced by Y</i>	<i>Same Distance Traveled by iceblock</i>	<i>Origin Based on length only</i>
Dead Center	583km	2690km	2752km	From Hudson Bay
30 degree vectors ¹⁰¹	583km; 336km	4660km; 2690km	2383km; 1376km	Big Snowy Mtns, MT
60 degree vectors ¹⁰²	583km; 1010km	1553km; 2690km	1376km; 2383km	Grass River Prov. Park, Canada
48 degree vectors	583km; 648km	2422km; 2690km	1841km; 2045km	Nokomis, Saskatchewan
75 degree vectors	583km; 2176km	721km; 2690km	712km; 2658km	SW-C Hudson Bay

¹⁰⁰ Very Rough Angles!

¹⁰¹ The ones creating the lips in shallow angles in Figure 4

¹⁰² The Michigan directed ones

Figure 6 - Middlesboro, KY Crater oblique strike¹⁰³

Figure 7 - Jephtha Knob, KY oblique strike

Figure 8 - Big Sink, KY below: no bow shock, no clear vector in or outblast center and out + clear signs of electric arc discharge sputtering, scalloping (albeit eroded), and crater chaining (and vector change)

¹⁰³ All of these are taken with KY From Above LiDAR scans. Author added vector analysis

FIG. 1. Map showing the location of the Versailles structure.

FIG. 2. Map of the Versailles structure showing the locations of refraction profile sites (circled) along Big Sink Road.

resolution reflection investigations at the Siljan impact structure

Figure 9 - Rim Fracturing around Big Sink? Credit: Harris, NASA/ADS¹⁰⁴

The author has not seen any reasonable data that shows even this amount of rim fracturing around the Carolina Bays, and these are very minimal as compared to Jephtha Knob and Middlesboro Crater!

The main point of Table 3 is that depending on the desire to force a similar source, or a similar distance, one cannot either have the same length strikes **and** origins or same angles and origins. They are mutually exclusive. This fact is hidden in aforementioned cited works by their use of curved lines to demonstrate strike spread of supposed ice-chunks. They use ice-chunks because they melt and cannot be found later. The Carolina Bay craters should also not have the nanodiamonds in them, and yet they do.

The point is **unambiguous**; first they try to lay the blame on a comet approach, but the age of impacts and vectors cannot agree. Then, upon a comet swarm, but the likelihood of having various angled strikes of various ages in the same county of North Carolina is ridiculously small. A state like KY which was south of the ice sheets should have *fields* of such oval depressions of the same type spread throughout the western Pennyroyal and in the Bluegrass. But there are only the 3 known astroblemes mentioned. The issue here is clearly *forced*: these Carolina Bays could not have come from a single event, swarm or comet unless they are impressions caused by repeated **close passage** of a charged body once in 10,800 BCE and then again around 8,000 BC. The same ground was struck twice because there is a form of quartz or other remaining charge which attracts the Thunderbolts in that area. The vector changed because the moon wanders (even still).

The resulting behavior is thus:

¹⁰⁴ <http://articles.adsabs.harvard.edu/full/1991Metic..26...47H/0000048.000.html>

1. The moon approached, and caused massive megatsunamis which engulfed Amazonia, Sundaland, Mu, etc... and collapsed either an Atlantean culture worldwide or the Azores, or both.
2. The new body altered the original angle of the Earth from its Saturnian angle of 26 degree to ~23 degrees it now has. This caused the Younger Dryas Ice Age event
3. The moon slingshot around Earth into a semi-stable orbit, but not perfect.
4. Later upon approach of another body (many candidates from myth), the moon came too close again and Anu/Janus caused a second Thunderbolt event which ended the Tepe period and finished off the megafauna. People lived in dolmens and caves.
5. Comet "debris" may or may not have been a part. The second event was remarkable for its Wind.
6. This event likely coincided the end of Kronos/Re/Osiris/El and beginning of Zeus/Seth/Jehovah/Odin as sky-god and ruling star. c. 7000-8000 BC. (End of Mohenjo Daro)
7. The period remained chaotic, there was another war of the gods and Titans c. 6000-5500 BCE
8. The Egyptians and Sumerians, and Hindu India took root after this and agriculture resumed, under a calmer star, now worshipped as Ba'al, Horus, Jove, etc...

Figure 10 - Jephtha Knob Seismic Shattering caused by a true oblique strike; credit: C Jung¹⁰⁵

Figure 11 - Side view of Jephtha Knob; Credit: US GEO Survey

¹⁰⁵ http://academic.emporia.edu/aberjame/student/jung1/jephtha_knob.htm

Figure 4. The Southern part of the Central Hudson Bay (site 2) characterized by a large number of ring-like features which are more than 200 m in diameter and up to 10 m high deep and surrounded by dipping off debris aprons.

Figure 12 - Hudson Bay Craters, supposedly below 2000m of ice, and obliquely struck; Credit: Roger et al...¹⁰⁶

Figure 13 - Chicxulub Crater¹⁰⁷, Yucatan; credit: Athenapup.com

Please compare to a well known and studied oblique strike at the K-T boundary (dinosaur killer). Note the central peak collapse, and the out blasting and explosion away.

¹⁰⁶ <https://cosmictusk.com/multi-ringed-depressions-beneath-hudson-bay-imitate-impact-craters/>

¹⁰⁷ <https://www.news.com.au/technology/science/evolution/drilling-into-dinosaur-ground-zero/news-story/f7309dc0b276bbff6974495a5103944c?sv=857fb417f1dbd461ad8c2aa3829161ef>

Part 1

Litmus test of standard naming and theories about earthworks, mounds, and glyphs.

As an exercise in applying Occam's Razor, all of the following are considerations of hypotheses made in archaeology, geology, archaeoastronomy and anthropology, which have simplified explanations with Electric-Plasma cosmogony. (Leaving out megafauna extinctions, which are the main study of this paper.)

Table 4 - Events/Phases in Human Memory simplified via EPEMC

Event, or situation described	Cultural or other Evidence	More Complex Mainstream Explanation(s)
<p>Out of Place errata/till (esp. in Africa and India)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● In Africa the errata seem to be going from the equator NORTH¹⁰⁸ ● In India the errata come from no main direction and descend south. 	<p>Portuguese¹⁰⁹ errata</p>	<p>Unexplained (but Deluge exclusion principle applied at any rate).</p>
<p>Mid-crustal Basalt formations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Devil's Tower ● Ayer's Rock ● Pilot Rock ● Stone Mountain ● Looking Glass Rock <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The Appalachian mountains are famously unvolcanic 	<p>Devil's Tower, Wyoming</p>	<p>Standard plate tectonics; plate weakness?</p> <p>There seems to be no indication as to why a volcanic formation would occur in these locations, nor any reason for upthrust, and the geologies are very out of character. Explanations given are difficult to believe.</p>
<p>Siesmicless crater formations, especially geometric ones</p>	<p>Barringer Crater¹¹⁰, AZ</p>	<p>Cometary Impacts</p> <p>There are some incredibly <i>poor</i> "astroblemes" out there as examples. However, in KY there are two <i>excellent</i> true examples of oblique astroblemes. (see Figures 3 - 12) The third (Figure 1) is clearly not a real impact. Neither are the Carolina Bays¹¹¹</p>
<p>Mound building genesis</p>	<p>Conical mounds are almost always not typical burial mounds. "Fort" or "effigy" mounds are not</p>	<p>Unexplained; supraterrain burial formations are without a mainstream explanation.</p>

¹⁰⁸ "When the Earth Nearly Died: Compelling Evidence of a Cosmic Catastrophe in 9,500 B.C.," DS Allan, 1997

¹⁰⁹ The Ice Age? Very unlikely.

¹¹⁰ Inexplicably octagonal, perpendicular, and undisturbed in soil at depth 100' below crater basin. 0 shock ripples around

¹¹¹ See aforementioned presentation for detailed analysis

	<p>forts nor villages</p> <p>Long, oblong mounds are burial mounds, but usually only for elit or religious or warrior folks.</p>	
Dolmen phenomenon	<p>North Salem, Hudson Valley</p>	<p>Stone Age “architecture”</p> <p>Despite the absurdity of the formations, mainstream archaeology either claims dolmens of such ridiculously heavy roofs are primitive architecture or somehow natural, which is equally preposterous.</p>
Calendar alterations	<p>Chinese changes^{112 113 114 115}</p> <p>Roman changes^{116 117}</p> <p>Egyptian changes^{118 119}</p>	<p>Continual attempts to figure out how to farm and follow the sun (but wouldn't people that rely on the sun and moon to farm pass on their knowledge yearly and generationally?).</p>
Enormous earthwork calendars but also...		<p>Highly religious agricultural worship; obsession with fertility.</p> <p>The implication of the mainstream was that worship of the fertility goddess¹²⁰ (with no apparent tie to a greater Saturn/Creator worship offered¹²¹) required superstitious belief but</p>

¹¹² http://www.math.nus.edu.sg/aslaksen/gem-projects/hm/Chinese_Calendar.pdf

¹¹³ <https://www2.ihp.sinica.edu.tw/file/1097kaBVwNb.pdf>

¹¹⁴ “1. Examining into antiquity, (we find that) the Ti Yao[1] was styled Fang-hsün[2]. He was reverential, intelligent, accomplished, and thoughtful, --naturally and without effort. He was sincerely courteous, and capable of (all) complaisance. The bright (influence of -these qualities) was felt through the four quarters (of the land), and reached to (heaven) above and (earth) beneath....

2. He commanded the Hsis and Hos[3], in reverent accordance with (their observation of) the wide heavens, to calculate and delineate (the movements and appearances of) the sun, the moon, the stars, and the zodiacal spaces, and so to deliver respectfully the seasons to be observed by the people.” Shi King, Book of Thang, Canon of Yao, translated by Legge

¹¹⁵ https://scholar.princeton.edu/sites/default/files/mkern/files/canon_of_yao.pdf

¹¹⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Roman_calendar

¹¹⁷ <http://www.historyworld.net/wrldhis/PlainTextHistories.asp?ParagraphID=bvt>

¹¹⁸ <https://www.britannica.com/science/Egyptian-calendar>

¹¹⁹ <https://www.infoplease.com/calendar-holidays/calendars/history-calendar>

¹²⁰ According to all cultures around the world the Mother Goddess' womb was the Cosmic Egg of the Creator, where he “seeded himself” and she was his wife, sister, and daughter. Therefore to have an abundant harvest the king would need to himself reflect the internal balance demonstrated by the Creator. The end of this era (of Atum-Re and his Aten) signaled the end of the balance of divine Male and Female.

¹²¹ See previously mentioned “Saturn Myth” table by author(credit: D Talbott)

	Great Serpent Mound, Ohio	scientific endeavor. ¹²²
Incredibly precise sundials and water clocks ¹²³ , which are no longer accurate; from same era as antikythera and other devices	Water clocks in Mesopotamia appear to have changed to reflect a 365 year ¹²⁴ India as well ¹²⁵ Egypt ¹²⁶ and China ¹²⁷ appear to use a different kind of water clock after a time (perhaps to change rate, or to improve precision?)	More obsession, but inexplicable technological development considering the inability to explore most of the world. [A similar issue is how the mainstream proposes to explain the many noted precisions ¹²⁸ ¹²⁹ of the Great Pyramid, but with primitive knowledge and technology.]
Megalithic architecture, in general	 Gobekli Tepe ¹³⁰ , Turkey	Blind religious worship and slavery The pyramid of Qin Shihuangdi was built by slaves but <u>abandoned</u> the moment of his death. But somehow all of the pyramids of Egypt were built via slavery. Gobekli Tepe, like Egypt is put down to an "obsession with Death" and one's mortality. ¹³¹

¹²² This is another example of Postmodern and Post-Enlightenment projectionism onto the past. Because *our time* is "after" the Religious Period (in the Noble West), the belief is that the only means to science is through overcoming superstition. When it comes to analyzing people of the Past, that means everything scientific was essentially lucky calibration, or occasional breakthroughs, whilst the majority of behavior is religious [idolatry]. When in fact the scientific was the aim of the religious. Again: Great Serpent Mound was a scientific endeavor to record important **new** information, history, and to obey the new Order of things (hence the solstice and lunar information encoded). It probably was, in fact, a religiously symbolic behavior but not as we see religion. Probably more how Muslims see religion: all encompassing. The location was also almost certainly not accidentally chosen.

¹²³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Water_clock

¹²⁴ https://www.jstor.org/stable/41668444?seq=1#page_scan_tab_contents

¹²⁵ https://www.academia.edu/2097773/Measuring_time_in_Mesopotamia_and_ancient_India

¹²⁶ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0305440386900257>

¹²⁷ "Joseph Needham speculated that the introduction of the outflow clepsydra to China, perhaps from Mesopotamia, occurred as far back as the 2nd millennium bc, during the Shang Dynasty, and at the latest by the 1st millennium bc. By the beginning of the Han Dynasty, in 202 bc, the outflow clepsydra was gradually replaced by the inflow clepsydra, which featured an indicator rod on a float" Sic, Ibid.

Note - the time of the Mars/Kali cataclysm was ~670 BCE whereas the Exodus cataclysm which would have actually changed the calendar was ~1,600 BCE (Author, using Velikovskian model)

¹²⁸

<https://www.ancient-origins.net/ancient-places-africa-opinion-guest-authors/mathematical-encoding-great-pyramid-002323>

¹²⁹ <http://blog.world-mysteries.com/mystic-places/the-precision-engineered-great-pyramid/>

¹³⁰ <https://news.nationalgeographic.com/2017/06/skulls-cult-turkey-archaeology-neolithic-gobekli/>

Skull cult? Not likely.

¹³¹ People today do many things to deal with mortality: drugs, therapy, thrill-seeking, religion... but they never build megalithic structures. All the cases of religious/megalithic architecture the author can think of that is modern always have more complex and/or positive values to them. It would be a mistake to assume motivations (ie, programming) were so different at that time.

<p>Cometary astronomical obsession</p>	<p>Gobekli Tepe Stele (Credit: Getty images/NatGeo)</p>	<p>Minor plagues and droughts associated with eclipses and comets, for no reason given except when the cases result in impact</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Greeks^{132 133} • Chinese¹³⁴ • Sumerians^{135 136} • Aborigines¹³⁷ • Tepe Period¹³⁸ • European Fears¹³⁹ • India does not mention comets so much as “weapons of the gods” such as those in the Mahabharata’s destruction of Dvaraka
<p>Carolina Bays</p>	<p>Carolina Bays</p>	<p>Sinkholes, essentially; or ice-errata from comet impact</p> <p>See Introduction and Figures 3-13 See Table 3</p>
<p>Parallel symbolism in Stone, Bronze and Iron Age cultures; even across continents and oceans</p>	<p>The greater part of evidence is seen in previous tables and in the Appendix of “On the Origins of Religions”; here shown is the concentric circle with rays glyph/earthwork, which is worldwide. The current sun (Sol) never looks like this.</p>	<p>No explanation (Atlantis refused) In a related discussion the Celtic Cross and the connection to the worldwide belief in a Morning Star/Evening Star is also not discussed. The reader should try to guess the origin of this “Celtic Cross” depiction:¹⁴⁰</p>

¹³² <https://www.space.com/9116-halley-comet-spotted-ancient-greeks.html>

¹³³ <http://www.newsweek.com/when-comet-flew-through-ancient-evenings-170630>

¹³⁴ <http://deepimpact.umd.edu/science/comets-cultures.html>

¹³⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=66QAnQXgVnU>

¹³⁶ <https://www.independent.co.uk/news/sodom-and-gomorra-destroyed-by-a-comet-say-astronomers-1275763.html>

¹³⁷ Ancient Destructons: 1491AD <http://www.mungoflix.com/mungoflix/ancient-destructons/>

¹³⁸ <http://www.dailymail.co.uk/sciencetech/article-4432554/Stone-carvings-confirm-comet-hit-Earth-13-000-years-ago.html>

¹³⁹ <https://www.mpg.de/research/comets-cultural-history>

¹⁴⁰ Mayan

<p>Repetitive glyph morphology especially...</p>	<p>The issue of this repeating star and solar glyph imagery is simply not dealt with by the mainstream.</p> <p>Big Turtle Rockshelter, KY Credit: Coy et al...¹⁴¹</p>	<p>No explanation specifically (Aliens refused; diffusionism resisted, ala Clovis First/land bridge)</p> <p>Consider at right: The “Concentric Circle glyph” It is neither a circle, nor merely concentric. The center is bass relief, and as perfectly hemispherical as can be found after hundreds of years of weathering. The outside is an uneven <i>hexagon</i>.¹⁴²</p>
<p>Thereonthrop/chimera epoch of art (even non-animal)</p>	<p>Khakassia, Siberia</p>	<p>Early Stone Age entheogenic use (saying this <i>plausible</i> theory is mainstream is being generous, the vast majority of archaeologists have incredibly fanciful ideas about the superstitious beliefs of Natives around the world, even when they turn out right. See: Dogon and the Dog-Star)</p>
<p>Use of conductive materials in</p>	<p>Gold or Electrum¹⁴³ Benben¹⁴⁴ 145</p>	<p>Pure vanity of Middle Kingdom</p>

¹⁴¹ Although Coy & Fuller are not mainstream archaeologists, reading their Introduction it is made clear that their work was heavily edited and influenced by the mainstream. Were the rock art names chosen for them? Some are ridiculously far off.

¹⁴² In the D Talbott “Saturn Myth” model, a collinear rotation is preferred. But this formation indicates either a plasma discharge, or more succinctly a *coplanar* rotation above the Saturnian pole, where site of the hexagon would have been clear and alignment, perhaps with Mars or Venus, would have been **spectacular** and worth recording in bass relief.

¹⁴³ “**Electrum** is a naturally occurring alloy of gold and silver, with trace amounts of copper and other metals. It has also been produced artificially, and is often known as **green gold**. The ancient Greeks called it ‘gold’ or ‘white gold’, as opposed to ‘refined gold’. Its colour ranges from pale to bright yellow, depending on the proportions of gold and silver.” [sic] <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Electrum>

¹⁴⁴ <https://www.ancient-origins.net/artifacts-other-artifacts/mythical-benben-stone-landing-site-egyptian-god-atum-006513>

¹⁴⁵ <http://robertbauval.co.uk/articles/articles/DE14.html>

pyramid building	<p>Quartz casing stones¹⁴⁶ Piezoelectricity¹⁴⁷ is a fundamental and known property of quartz¹⁴⁸, which can cause light disturbances at night or birds to fall out of the sky. Standing waves have been allegedly observed over conical hills, mountains, and pyramids (natural or otherwise)¹⁴⁹</p>	<p>pharaohs</p> <p>There is seriously no other explanation provided. Not even a structural one.</p> <p>There are some good theories to suggest the pyramids were built in phases¹⁵⁰, and the casing stones were the last thing done.</p>
Widespread Mesopotamian Destruction of entire cities and...	<p>Sumerian Tablet that predicted Sodom's destruction</p>	<p>Droughts, warfare, and minor floods; however nothing cataclysmic (Uniformitarian only)</p> <p>In recent years this has softened quite a bit. For example it is now widely accepted amongst geologists that the Channeled Scablands¹⁵¹ were produced when an ice-rock dam broke at Lake Missoula and created one of the largest waterfalls in human times.¹⁵² Also, see: Burckle Crater</p>
Presence of radioactive materials and spherules on site	<p>Sodom^{153 154 155} Mohenjo Daro^{156 157 158} vs.¹⁵⁹ Related: vitrification^{160 161 162}</p>	<p>No explanation, perhaps minor meteorite explosions, ala Tunguska</p>
Driving force of shifting Sea Peoples	<p>The discussion of this is definitely skewed in the direction of smaller catastrophes, and for the most part the author agrees</p>	<p>Droughts, warfare; they are not exactly know who they are or where they came from.</p>

¹⁴⁶ <https://www.cheops-pyramide.ch/khufu-pyramid/casing-stones.html>

¹⁴⁷ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Piezoelectricity>

¹⁴⁸ <https://www.explainthatstuff.com/piezoelectricity.html>

¹⁴⁹ <https://www.express.co.uk/news/weird/773789/Bosnian-Pyramid-Nikola-Tesla-standing-waves-aliens>

¹⁵⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iktAUyOaX8s>

¹⁵¹ <https://news.nationalgeographic.com/2017/03/channeled-scablands/>

¹⁵² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Missoula_Floods

¹⁵³ <http://blogs.christianpost.com/comets-of-god/human-remains-found-at-sodom-16700/>

¹⁵⁴ <https://aleteia.org/2018/01/22/is-this-the-site-where-sodom-once-stood/>

¹⁵⁵

¹⁵⁶ <http://www.dailymail.co.uk/sciencetech/article-3270999/Has-Biblical-city-Sodom-Monstrous-site-Jordan-matches-descriptions-area-destroyed-God.html>

¹⁵⁷ <https://www.indiavine.org/8000-year-old-indian-city-irradiated-by-atomic-blast/>

¹⁵⁸ <https://www.eyeofthepsychic.com/bestevidence/>

¹⁵⁹ <https://www.ancient-origins.net/ancient-places-asia/mohenjo-daro-massacre-00819>

¹⁶⁰ <http://www.jasoncolavito.com/ancient-atom-bombs.html>

¹⁶¹ https://www.bibliotecapleyades.net/ancientatomicwar/esp_ancient_atomic_02.htm

¹⁶² A later comet: 356-362CE <https://skeptoid.com/episodes/4326>

¹⁶² <https://secretsofthesunsects.wordpress.com/2011/12/05/incan-vitrified-stones/>

	<p>with these answers.¹⁶³ However, the fact remains that the Mediterranean has greatly changed sea level and much of the land people lived on is now gone. For more information read the author's paper, "Unboxing Atlantis," which contains diagrams specific to this topic.¹⁶⁴</p>	<p>There are actually a number of candidates for the "Sea Peoples" and this makes sense. When one's lands are destroyed: go elsewhere. While the Hebrews were leaving Egypt to go North, the Amalekites were leaving Arabia to go West, and they crossed in Sinai, and had war.¹⁶⁵</p>
<p>Origin of Sahara and "Desert Belt"</p> <p>The truth is that there is no explanation currently for how the Sahara Savannah turned into hundreds of feet thick of sand, across an entire continent. And no one wants to talk about it, either, including from the EU, Hancock et al..., Sitchin-Donakin et al..., camps. It is a major problem. Though Wal Thornhill has mentioned it, and some of the EU Geology catastrophists, nobody has specifically done a study comparing the Sahara sands with the Martian samples. The author did a brief sampling, but results are not written, as of yet.</p>	<p>Eye of the Sahara - Biggest Thunderbolt strike</p> <p>Credit: theecologist.org</p>	<p>"Desertification" (cyclical definition) due to unexplained shifting climate forces.</p> <p>Sometimes a comet is blamed, sometimes Precession/wobble, sometimes humans.</p> <p>The simplicity of the answer is obvious: the desert belt was dumped on Earth. However, not by the moon, but by Venus and then Mars.</p> <p>The shift in climate was first caused by the Moon and the Younger Dryas. The two events go hand in hand. A mutually supportive discordant cycle.</p>
<p>Tilt of Lake Titicaca¹⁶⁶</p> <p>The testimony of the Uru People¹⁶⁷ is that this most definitely happened, and in the remote past.</p> <p>Overall the area has uplifted about 4 km within the last 11,000-12,000 years.^{168 169}</p>	<p>Credit: NephiCode¹⁷⁰</p>	<p>Massive regional earthquake</p> <p>The most interesting thing is that the Chinese said the same thing about the Taklamakan Desert¹⁷¹, which also looks like a former lake that was emptied out.¹⁷²</p>
<p>Geoglyph-Earthwork</p>	<p>See Table 2 and "On the Origins</p>	<p>Unexplained (Amazonian earthworks</p>

¹⁶³ "1177 B.C.: The Year Civilization Collapsed: Turning Points in Ancient History," E Cline, 2015

¹⁶⁴ [3] Figure 13

¹⁶⁵ Bible, "Ages in Chaos," I Velikovsky, 1952

¹⁶⁶ <https://www.britannica.com/place/Lake-Titicaca>

¹⁶⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Uru_people

¹⁶⁸ [3] Table 2

¹⁶⁹ Ibid.

¹⁷⁰ <http://nephicode.blogspot.com/2016/10/the-flood-that-destroyed-tiwanaku-part-i.html>

¹⁷¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Taklamakan_Desert

¹⁷² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Taklamakan_Desert#/media/File:Taklamakan.png

North/South America parallelism; specifically circle+square offset arrangement	of Religions” Appendix B See also Dave Talbott’s “Discourses of an Alien Sky” ¹⁷³	only recently found) Note the Chinese saying, “Heaven is round, Earth is square,” ¹⁷⁴ which has been interpreted by sinologists and Taoists in a large milieu of psychological and philosophical meanings. ¹⁷⁵
Biblical Exodus/Ipwer Egyptian text cataclysmic testimony	See “Ages in Chaos” series by Immanuel Velikovsky. Ignoring a hypothesis is not a rebuttal. The conjunction of the Ipwer text ¹⁷⁶ with the Book of Exodus is not uncanny, it is in fact reflective of a historical event. ¹⁷⁷	Unexplained (Velikovsky refused; Deluge exclusion principle) Again: refusing to deal with a hypothesis is not a valid scientific rebuttal. As for Carl Sagan’s response to Velikovsky, it has been itself, roundly debunked. ^{178 179}

Caloric Miscalculations

As mentioned before, one of the oddest assertions from the mainstream of archaeology is that while many of these cultures from Archaic through Woodland were essentially primitive, mobile, or bronze age, they also were incredibly mathematically gifted: practicing civil engineering, astronomy, advanced permaculture¹⁸⁰, and mining for copper, fluorite, and pearls. More to the point, they were involved in building mound *complexes*, without wheel barrels or even wheels, despite living essentially off the land.

It is a well known fact amongst wild foods specialists that natural strains of foods are less caloric in their content. It is also known amongst survival experts that you cannot run a city based upon wild game, but only through domesticating or managing the game, such as bison.

So why would any people, especially the larger the civilization, resort to wasting inordinate amounts of time building basically unnecessary mound complexes? With the pyramids of Egypt and Mexico there is the argument of vanity, funerary use, and the function possibly of electrical production or water pumping for massive agriculture (for millions of people).

But why build complexes which are neither for cities nor forts? Naturally the mainstream argues for a religious and cultural reason - a gathering. The author doesn’t deny this. But the *why* remains out of reach.

Yet, although archaeologists have no writing or explicit stele (such as at Gobekli Tepe) specifying cultural beliefs and behaviors, mores and norms, they take the opportunity to fill the vacuum with, frankly, nonsense.

For example, at the Cahokia visitor center, much is said within the documentary “City of the Sun” which is pure idle speculation. Moreover, despite displaying the clearly advanced, even proto-European mound building civilization that used stockades and engaged in interstate commerce, they depict the people as going naked primarily. This is surely *insulting* to the descendants of plains Indians everywhere, who are well known for

¹⁷³ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=svfWvSHh4AY&list=PLwOAYhBuU3UeFB-ygaH63Seg6r6C_dtqB

¹⁷⁴ <https://www.orthodoxartsjournal.org/heaven-round-earth-square/>

¹⁷⁵ <https://www.purplemotes.net/2010/12/05/earths-a-square-heaven-a-circle/>

¹⁷⁶ <http://www.reshafim.org.il/ad/egypt/texts/ipwer.htm>

¹⁷⁷ <https://ohr.edu/838>

¹⁷⁸ <http://immanuelvelikovsky.com/Svbasic.htm>

¹⁷⁹ <http://www.procars-clean.com/carl-sagan-and-immanuel-velikovsky-english.pdf>

¹⁸⁰ Such as controlled burning and raised beds as well as cross-species mixing.

elaborate dress. In the museum children are even depicted with malnourished pot-bellies, and yet the visitor is told that dozens of thousands lived at Cahokia alone (the Mississippian culture had millions of denizens throughout the midwest united undoubtedly under a single central ruler atop Monk's Mound.)

These contradictions in logic (see Table 1) lead the author to suspect the opinions that such cultures ended almost exclusively due to disease, famine, drought, and warfare. Rather, the author suspects that each epoch had a different causative ending.

Table 5 - Proposed vectors for the End of Eastern Cultures

pre-Archaic	> 12,800 YBP	Early cavemen and Travelers	Younger Dryas cataclysm (moon); Shamash
Tepe Period transition	12,800-8,000 YBP	Atlantean remnants	End of Saturnian Age
Archaic	9,000-5,000 YBP ¹⁸¹	PaleoIndians and Europeans ¹⁸²	End of Jovian Age Deluge?
Allegewi First Phase	5,500-3,600 YBP	Atlantean or Amazonia remnants	Exodus Cataclysm (Venus) & Plague
Allegewi Second Phase	3,600-1,700 YBP	Allegewi Loyalists	Mars & 300 CE comet
Hopewell	3,600-1,000 YBP	Traveler ¹⁸³ -Indian mixing	Waning of the gods
Woodland Era	5,500-500 YBP	American Indian arrivals	Disease and warfare?
Miss. Culture	2,600-500 YBP	Hopewell-traveler mixing	Disease ¹⁸⁴ and flood ¹⁸⁵
Cahokia Dominance	1,700-500 YBP	Welsh/Celtic mixing	Warfare with Lakota
Ft. Ancient	1,300-300 YBP	Hopewell remnant +American Indian	Warfare, disease, depopulation
Mandan Remnants	500-200 YBP	Cahokians and other Miss. survivors	Smallpox and warfare with Lakota
Historic Indians	400YBP-present	Displaced survivors of smallpox and warfare	Warfare, mixing with white pioneer populations

It is important to remember that multiple vectors are likely suspect in each of the ending eras. However, there has to be a prime instigation in each event. The most interesting thing, in reviewing the site locations map (created by the author¹⁸⁶), is the trend that appears. Although the map needs far more data to be considered complete, still a striking and obvious narrative appears:

¹⁸¹ Author defined dates

¹⁸² See: "Windover Bog Bodies - European?," Ancient American, September 2018

<http://www.ancientworldreview.com/2016/10/the-windover-bog-bodies-european.html>

¹⁸³ Traveler as in from Asia, Asia minor, MesoAmerica or Europe

¹⁸⁴ Possibly smallpox introduced by the Chinese in 1529 or thereabouts, as per the Nickless hypothesis, see "Chasing Dragons: the True History of the Piasa." This hypothesis has several merits which will be discussed in a later paper For more information, see, "To the Gates of Fengtu" by Laurie Bonner-Nickless which is a translation of this account.

¹⁸⁵ <https://www.nature.com/news/floods-might-have-doomed-prehistoric-american-city-1.17470>

¹⁸⁶ <http://bit.ly/2Q9J8p7>

Figure 14 - Select Portion of Map of Eastern Cultures

See how the Archaic sites and mounds stand aside from the Miss. Culture and the Allegewi-Hopewell, which remain also mostly disparate? The Ft. Ancient are clearly descended from the Allegewi-Hopewell. The Mississippians clearly respected the Archaic mounds of the “gods” and sought new lands to build .

Why would such deference be shown if not for either religio-cultural mores or socio-political forces? The distances between Ft. Ancient and Miss. cultural sites also belies a clear mutual accord of boundaries.

This all seems to point back to a key change in the region. The author proposes that the arrival of foreigners (whites) coming from Romans¹⁸⁷ (perhaps following Phoenicians?), then Vikings¹⁸⁸, then the Welsh or other celtic peoples¹⁸⁹, was a portion of the event. But that the cataclysms themselves, and interpretations (perhaps which god to respect or follow?) clearly (as identified by the boundary dates conforming to the Old World records¹⁹⁰) had an effect.

The author notes that the reported hatred of the Cahokia-Mandan-Hidatsa by the Lakota nations was legendary¹⁹¹, indicating disparate genetics (lack of typical royalty-wedding alliances) and cultures.

Our interests are primarily in the religious ways of the Allegewi-Hopewell and their descendents the Ft. Ancient and Mississippian cultures, which although going their separate ways shared a deep inherent respect of mounds of the ancients and ancestors. Also, our interest is in their inherited traditions of a long story of cataclysms, particularly winds, the Flood, thunderbirds (rock chunks¹⁹² interacting with plasmasphere of earth), thundereggs (meteorites) and the thunderbolts of the gods.... as much as can be seen without written record. For while we will freely speculate based upon cross-similar forces, records, and events, we mustn't commit the same sin as projecting too much illogical behavior. Instead, we must create an atmosphere of logical respect for

¹⁸⁷ <http://www.econ.ohio-state.edu/jhm/arch/coins/fallsch.htm>

¹⁸⁸ <https://www.roadsideamerica.com/story/29041>

¹⁸⁹ Troxel, A Wilson, et al... See “The Holy Kingdom” by Adrian Gilbert for the most concise detailed references.

¹⁹⁰ [2] See Table 1 in prior works

¹⁹¹ Troxel

¹⁹² ie- electric comets

these people which settled and civilized the ORV and MRV, yet without clear-cutting and destroying the environment¹⁹³.

Cahokia, Toltec, Aztec, and Maya

One thing that separates the Cahokians from the remainder of the North American tribes, except perhaps very southern 'Toltec'¹⁹⁴, is the behavior of *stockading a central city*. This is a clearly "civilized" (city-planning) behavior, which had a practical reason: enemies with the other plains Indians. Moreover, the engagement in industrial pearl gathering¹⁹⁵, mining¹⁹⁶, and interstate commerce begs the question, "Why are the Cahokians so different?" The answer is simple, really: they were descendents of a mixing of celtic peoples, perhaps some Roman overseers from mining as well, with the Allegewi-Hopewell.

Their mound structures were very inspired, and seemed from the outside to be related to the Aztec-Maya traditions¹⁹⁷, but the author finds doubt in this because of the distinct lack of evidence of such mixing in between Tejas and the ORV. While Roman coins have been found, and reports of the Cahokian-Mandans speaking Welsh are numerous, there don't appear to be any such reports of people speaking Nahuatl or related languages. Nor does the mica used by Aztecs appear to come from the Carolinas, but instead is locally sourced or from MesoAmerica.

So the question lingers, "Why would anyone destroy the Cahokians to the point of burning the forts to the ground but not taking them over?" If it were other "civilized" cultures (again city-based), they would have taken control, as the Spanish took over Tenochtitlan. Monk's Mound and the surrounding hill forts all form a ready-made military infrastructure. It's clear that the Cahokians and surrounding tribes *all* were on the wane in agriculture, populations, and industry. The answer seems clear: they were being systematically wiped out in prolonged warfare with the nomadic tribes of the plains and the far east. The Warrior's Path¹⁹⁸ went east and west as well as North and South.

Such a decline was later seen in the Cherokee, as well, although disease may have had more of an influence than war.¹⁹⁹

Why would the Lakota and other Indians so hate the natives of the Mississippi River Valley? The answer could perhaps be jealousy, but more likely (given they did not adopt their ways or cities as would be expected): it was violation of an inherent and **reverent** belief. The same belief that was powerful enough to motivate natives throughout the east of North America to build conical and henge-mounds (or maintain them), build earthworks the hard way²⁰⁰, despite caloric restrictions and without *stored* writing: worship of the gods.

Why would the gods, and in particular the Creator-God²⁰¹, the central power of both the Pole-Axis and the Celtic-cross sun, be so important? Because at one time He made war upon the "Evil men" and "evil animals" **and wiped them out**. The natives very much revered these events, and they very much despised any people that so clearly violated the understood tenants.

¹⁹³ The destruction of the forests due to Pigo Iron alone is appalling, and the author recommends the reader to look at old logging photos. Although most people know about the Redwoods' destructions, few ever stop to think about the effect upon the Shawnee, Delaware, Wyandot, etc... when they saw their ancestral homelands literally razed to the ground to turn chunks of rock into lumpy iron for industry and war.

¹⁹⁴ Toltec Mounds, AR; Poverty Point, etc...

¹⁹⁵ Tennessee and Green (KY) Rivers; mound clearly piled in an industrialised manner

¹⁹⁶ Fluorite mining in Kentucky is famous. Famous enough for Romans to seek it out for smelting purposes? Rick Osman thinks so.

¹⁹⁷ Vis-a-vis the "pyramid" building. But therein lies the key difference. While the whole world built step pyramids, the Cahokians did so with packed earth, and not stone.

¹⁹⁸ <https://www.nps.gov/cuga/learn/historyculture/warriors-path.htm>

¹⁹⁹ <https://www.livescience.com/4606-history-rewritten-choerokee-collapse.html>

²⁰⁰ Literally scooping Earth with small trowels into wicker baskets to carry on their backs. No handled shovels!

²⁰¹ Wakan-Tanka to the Sioux

Of course the hatred of the plains Indians for the land-possessing "White Man" is historically known. It was said that [our] culture's ways were unnatural, unsustainable, and ridiculous²⁰². The difficulties imposed upon pioneers moving west was born out of the same inherited hatred²⁰³ which wiped out the Cahokians and forced the descendants, the Mandans and Hidatsa north.

Figure 15 - Cahokian Pole-Sun Worship Cosmogony; credit: Cahokia Visitor Center, Illinois

What does this all have to do with the megafauna extinction? This is like asking what the Magna Carta has to do with the Civil Rights Act. Nothing directly, of course. But without a series or chain of events, one cannot begin to understand the general movements and motivations of a people that did not believe in utilizing the Sacred Wheel (see Figure 15), or recording their writing and calculations on anything sacred such as birch-bark (without probably burning it afterwards).

While the Shang & Zhou Chinese were content to record on the hexagon shaped tortoise shells as a means to convene with the divine, the natives most likely abhorred this type of behavior, preferring to properly use animal parts, but sparingly (especially after so many extinctions) and to make symbolic effigy pottery.

Their ancestors certainly wouldn't condone it, nor would they prefer to live in the land of the gods - Kathiki - where the Great Man²⁰⁴ stamped his foot and the world ended. Such a land was lived in temporarily but the core remained shared lands for all to hunt and be reverent. It was a sort of enlarged Mecca, if you will. Most of the Hopewell tended to live north of the Ohio, where other ancient and revered structures remained, and the land was *less* disputed (although it was still). Certainly, they preferred to live North and East of the Big Sink thunderbolt strike.²⁰⁵

²⁰² The author agrees on all points.

²⁰³ Commentaries from the Victorians on the torture tactics of the "savages" are hilariously off the mark. These practices didn't *come naturally*... they were signs that the native tribe performing them (boiling, filleting, scalping, etc...) looked down upon other tribes, especially those that helped the White Man, as well as the White Man himself, as being less worthy humans. Like dogs, or vermin. That is intense, specific hatred. It is not a past-time. It is a learned method of punishment.

²⁰⁴ Tirawa to the Pawnee

²⁰⁵ There may be a specific reason for this, scientifically speaking. But the effects of Step Potential are not well studied, except as a safety measure and precaution.

“...When all was chaos and confusion, the earth was covered with water,²⁰⁶ there was only mud and slime on the surface of the earth. At that time... there became visible a god²⁰⁷ who had the name 1-Deer and the surname Snake of the Lion and a goddess²⁰⁸, very genteel and beautiful, whose name was also 1-Deer and whose surname was Snake of the Tiger. These two gods are said to have been the beginning of all other gods²⁰⁹... As soon as these two gods became visible on earth, in human form, the accounts of our people²¹⁰ relate that with their power²¹¹ and wisdom they made and established a large stone on which they built a very sumptuous mansion... which was their seat and residence on earth... [they] were on a very high hill. The large stone was named ‘the-place-where-the-heavens-were.’²¹² And there they remained many centuries in complete tranquility and contentment, as in a pleasant and delightful place...”²¹³ ~Mixtec legend²¹⁴

The Victorian Effect

One theory might be that supposed diffusion elements, and assignment of extreme primitivity and “savage only” archetypes coming from racism inherent in the Victorian Age, post Enlightenment culture (which naturally found its way into early archaeology²¹⁵) polluted the early scientific work. This is partially true, there is no doubt. However, it is not racism to take the testimony of natives at face value. From North America to Mexico to South America, the story of earlier “white gods” coming and civilizing the continents is realistic testimony. White does *not* mean European. There are Altaic, middle eastern, semitic, North African whites, etc...let us not forget there are indigenous white people still in Japan, and they have also been reported by the Maori of New Zealand.

The author proposes that it is perhaps the settling “sea peoples” or “Atlanteans”, or perhaps Phoenicians, Egyptians, Vikings, or celtic races, but this point actually isn’t that important. It is only important that we listen to the testimony of a people that have literally no reason to lie.

If, for example, they had *meant* that a comet came down and wiped out the mammoths, surely they would have said to Thomas Jefferson, “Then the Great Man ripped a massive chunk of granite from the mountain, and at once hurtling the entire Cosmic Mountain, cast it down upon the North, and a great wave came and then a fog that lasted for ten years. This fog killed all of the people but two, who survived off of the remains of the Giants. At the end of this, however, the first man and woman settled in this fair land and created the many tribes.”... or something to that effect. It isn’t unreasonable to expect that people with no stock market, agenda, or other profit motives would just simply **tell the truth**.

When cultures from above and below the tropics all say this very thing, or similar thing, about the cataclysms that shook the world and put mud and water everywhere and wiped out all of the animals, then it seems prudent to listen. However even fringe geologists would rather *assign* vectors - of what they consider **possible** and then argue over the probability. How realistic is this type of approach?

²⁰⁶ After the Great Flood or Deluge, the context is not clear which age this was.

²⁰⁷ Jupiter/Zeus or Mars - Marduk

²⁰⁸ Saturn/Hera or Venus - Ishtar

²⁰⁹ Ie, moons; this points to Jupiter and Saturn, of which Venus and Mars were merely a facsimile of the story.

²¹⁰ Mixtec

²¹¹ What power would be known from the gods on earth, of these planets, if not for Electromagnetism?

²¹² Ie, the archetypal Eden

²¹³ This legend is in no way unique or borrowed from Sumerian myths. It is simply the eyewitness testimony of the world. It describes the state of things after Saturn lost its place as the primordial sun, and Jupiter was “King of the gods.” And the two were in colinear rotation.

²¹⁴ “The Saturn Myth,” D Talbott, pp. 172

²¹⁵ One must remember that vertebrate anthropology and archaeology began at Big Bone Lick with Thomas Jefferson’s work.

Suppose that a gas station is robbed. Upon arriving the white police officer hears the testimony of the brown store owner, and rather than lend it credence creates a sketch for himself. He imagines a bogeyman, of heinous size and skulking behaviors, dressed head to toe in black, and waving a hatchet, acting rashly.

But the store owners say, "We have a video camera."

But the officer, hearing on his radio that such a character has been seen, from time to time, rushes out the store first, without examination, or only cursory examination of the evidence. He apprehends this fiendish, ugly man, who is mostly innocent or totally innocent, and locks him away. At the trial the testimony of the store owner is not even sought. It's an open and shut case. Guilty by association - by exclusion of all the other convenient facts.

This is just the sort of forensics work that has been performed in the case of early 20th Century archaeology, as it sought to disregard the work of the Victorian Age. Although archaeology never rid itself of the behavior of grave-robbing and mound-desecration²¹⁶, it did try to give credit for mound building *solely* to the brown natives, forcing it upon them who have already said it was not themselves but the "white gods" that were in the Ohio River Valley previously²¹⁷. Moreover, when the robbery was described, the police officer (anthropology) went forward under his own assumptions, with everything from over-hunting to volcanoes to anything *but* the Deluge, moon cataclysm, and the war of the gods and titans.... until the point where the gas station owner himself became the thief, and was arrested on the charge of wholesale slaughter of the entirety of multiple megafauna species²¹⁸, numerous of which were super-predators that hunted men²¹⁹. This story was bought by the jury, made up exclusively of grave-robbing archaeologists who worked in tandem, and only amongst themselves, not allowing other, harder sciences²²⁰ to involve themselves and *meddle* in the affairs of the important work of cataloguing grave goods and selling them in museums around the world, and writing papers.²²¹

In places like Kentucky, the grave goods were put away, or sometimes destroyed (such as bodies), and the crime was *overwritten*, as it was already a "textbook case" of an inside job. The brown natives did it: they pushed all the mammoths off of cliffs. But *publicly* the natives must be lauded as guardians of nature and those who lived in harmony with the buffalo. Privately, however, the belief in a ravenous appetite of these (obviously) agrarian civilizations that must have extended throughout the entire hemisphere in a vast endless consumption.²²²; This belief was proposed, accepted, and published in museums. It is the only mainstream narrative taught in schools. Kentucky was empty because natives disappeared. But they didn't have enough food because they had hunted everything to the point of extinction.

It sounds preposterous when one reads it back in hindsight. But not so preposterous when one considers the utter and complete destruction of Kathiki and the land of the gods in the pursuit of industry and pioneering (timbering, farming, forts, etc...). It also isn't so preposterous when one considers the behavior of the white men that went west, slaughtering bison in order to drive the Sioux and Crow out of the plains, to starve them²²³. It isn't so preposterous when one thinks of the arrogance of 18th and 19th century British science, with its cliquish academies and awards, busily congratulating itself on discovering everything there was to know (prior to the Quantum revolution!)

²¹⁶ See: Indian Knoll, "Adena" Mound, etc...

²¹⁷ <https://moundbuilder.blogspot.com/2011/10/cherokee-legends-of-white-race-of-mound.html>

²¹⁸

<https://www.independent.co.uk/news/science/humans-definitely-killed-off-woolly-mammoths-giant-armadillo-and-sabretooth-tiger-scientists-claim-10455447.html>

²¹⁹ 6 species of smilodon, Dire Wolves, Short-faced Bears, American Lions, and American cheetahs

²²⁰ To be a true science, the results need to be repeatedly tested; but when a site is destroyed, it cannot be recovered again.

²²¹ Written dourly, but honestly. That is precisely what the industry does.

²²² Projection usually works by sending out what one knows from one's own culture.

²²³ <https://www.theatlantic.com/national/archive/2016/05/the-buffalo-killers/482349/>

After all, at this very time learned men were using skull size and shape to determine the IQ ranges of primitive (colored) peoples and assigning them a status as to how human they were, in relation to them. In such a time, it makes total sense to teach and inherit, and re-teach a form of archaeology that relies on subjective fact and *a priori* assumption, rather than deductive reasoning and objective, macro-level cross-cultural archetypal comparison.

It isn't the author's intentions to totally dismiss or destroy the time-honored science of grave-robbing.²²⁴ But it is the intention to make it clear what biases would exist in such a view, and such a behavior. To this day the office of State Archaeology (in Kentucky) hordes mummified remains, which they will not DNA test or provide published works publicly without signing for the documents²²⁵. Therefore there is no way for the descendants of native America to worship, honor, or preserve this heritage.²²⁶ When the language dies, it becomes one thing that grave-robbing cannot study: actual culture. Artifacts can, ultimately, only say so much. But they are not the people, not the place nor time, and they are certainly not the stories which remain *untold* for most of the public (albeit some cultural historians and anthropologists did collect them at one time into volumes of texts which remain, again, under lock and key or out of print).

In the opinion of the author, the *only* way to go forward, therefore, is with a rational objective approach.

In Part 2, we will see just **one** such approach. This is not the end of the approach but the beginning. Not of looking at artifacts to make guesses, and assign uniquely bizarre cultural names to peoples and call them by that. But instead to analyze the *genius* and witness, and then in Parts 3 and 4, compare it with Old World and Native American testimony. It can be done also with oceanic and Australian testimony, however this would only add to the length. Such work has already been done by David Talbott of Project Thunderbolts (see: "The Saturn Myth").

Regarding further discussions of White Indians, Welsh Indians, what have you, the full analysis will be found in the works of Dr. Troxel and Alan Wilson/Baram Blackett, (see Gilberts' "The Holy Kingdom") and is unnecessary here. It has only been mentioned in the case of finding native testimony which matches native Welsh stone records, Viking stones, and other stone artifacts which are continuously dismissed by mainstream archaeology for their rather inconvenient narratives. Again: where cross-cultural testimony agrees, we will find truth.

²²⁴ It is, in fact, possible to study mounds and burials respectfully. It just isn't convenient, and overall, concerning these cultures: it isn't standard. It's said that a society's advancement is tested by how it treats its most vulnerable members of society. The defeated native tribes, placed into reservations, with no congressional or state representation, are unable to defend their cultural relics. What is our society doing to help? Mostly: taking advantage.

²²⁵ The author can personally confirm this to be the case, as he had to go through such hoops. Without asking even if he could see the mummies, but just inquiring as to their protection, he was told, "Yes we have them, and no you cannot see them." That is a direct quote.

²²⁶ Wickliffe Mounds has a museum in KY, but it is a complete desecration. Other than this, there are galleries of plains indians clothes at the Speed Art Museum in Louisville, and occasional exhibits at the Cincinnati Museum of Art. There is a small "display building" at the Trail of Tears Commemorative Park, and a short pathway to some native graves of important historic chiefs. There are some interesting displays at small visitor centers such as Big Bone Lick and Falls of the Ohio State Parks. The latter, of course, includes nothing whatsoever about the stone forts, the great battle to slaughter 1,500-3,000 White Indians, etc... that occurred there some 400-700 years ago. Ohio, Indiana, and Illinois have much more in the way of museums. There is also the Visitor center at the Cherokee Reservation in North Carolina.

Part 2

Comparing ratios of the Turkey Foot asymmetrical glyph and Eagle and Alligator mounds; a story of purposefully done “bad art.”

As written above and demonstrated previously, cross-correspondence makes it clear that our mainstream understanding of glyphs, earthworks, and even artifacts are clearly European in origin²²⁷. However, in this part we will take a step further and show that such correspondences are so clearly mislabeled, and misunderstood, that even basic rudimentary understanding is curtailed via *assumptions* about the cultures (ie, they are primitive, hunter-gatherers, obsessed with animals tracks). The following Table will sum up the issues in analysis with the “turkey track/foot”, Eagle and Alligator mounds, bear print & left foot glyphs, turtle glyph, and double concentric circle-suns using multi-site glyph/earthwork association and analysis.

The author admits that his hypothesis is itself inconclusive. However, it does at least reflect a) cultural context from around the world and b) mythic evidence and testimony, as well as demonstrable rationality that solves the issue of *why* they would make the glyphs, which again serves no artistic, pornographic, historico-linguistic, mathematical, or indeed any other apparent value that we can recognize²²⁸ (hence naming them with animal meanings)²²⁹.

Table 6 - Logic Summary for Glyphs and Earthworks; conclusions otherwise offered when possible.

Issue	Illogicism	Solution Offered
Turkey “Tracks” (see Plate L5, Figure 20)	One-legged turkeys, hopping along? With no width to the feet?	1) Awen Symbol; ie from Diffusionist peoples (travelers) 2) Conjunction of Earth, Moon, Mars, and Venus or of Earth, Venus, Jupiter and Mars or Saturn ^{230 231} 3) Might be the same thing, anciently.

²²⁷ Blue Licks discoidal (Danish Spindle Whorls), KY tobacco pipe (Mediterranean oil lamp); credit: Lee Pennington <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1bR4iDw4RuQQG8W4mliqtJidZ1jO8j5u2/view?usp=sharing>

²²⁸ The formula we have used of Clovis First + Old World (Egyptology led) Bronze Age models is simply not cutting it anymore. It might even be considered a form of post-colonialism. A throwback to Manifest Destiny in the same way that softcore racism of “low expectations” is a throwback to the Eugenics era. Reprehensible thinking! The idea even of the “Four Cradles of Civilization” is so antiquated and insulting. It’s amazing that so many museums and textbooks still display Natives in a temperate climate as nude or semi-nude.

²²⁹ Ie - why make them at all? Boredom seems hardly sufficient reason to carve into the flesh of the Mother. No one is drawing his family out. So why even bother? There has to be a sufficient reason to leave these marks - and hardly any others!

²³⁰ It is no accident that the same 5 planets and our moon come up repeatedly, again and again in every culture. It would be no different for the Allegewi-Hopewell. The obsessions with Draco, Pleiades, Ursa Major, Polaris, etc... may be rather modern by comparison.

²³¹ In the Eagle and Alligator mounds in particular, the bulbous shape of celestial bodies surrounded by plasma sheaths is just discernable or imaginable (at least as a possibility).

Asymmetric Turkey Foot and Eagle Mound center (see Figures 16-18) Asymmetric Alligator Awen (see Figure 19-20)	Nothing offered by mainstream (unnoticed)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Different angle view of the sky than Old World Awen²³² counterparts 2) Different era, when conjunction was failing 3) Combination of the two
Bear Print (see Figure 22)	Doesn't look like a bear print ²³³	Jupiter and 4 Gailean moons + Mars in rare conjunction
Left foot glyphs (see Figures 24-25)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No solution offered as to out of proportion amount of randomly arranged left feet (vs. right) 2) Left feet are anatomically incorrect²³⁴ 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Same conjunction as seen in "Bear Print" glyph 2) Different conjunction, similar to that of Awen symbol, but different angles or time periods
Alligator Mound ²³⁵ & Turtle Glyph "5 legs" (see Figures 19-20, G & S Plates)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The Alligator mound doesn't look like an alligator and reptiles do not have a 5th leg on their right flank. 2) No alligators above Florida naturally²³⁶ (nor above Georgia) 3) Alligators would not have been a power animal for the Allegewi-hopewell²³⁷ 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) A further stage of the conjunction that led to the catastrophe 2) Part of the Alligator mound shape is the basic Eagle Mound plasmaglyph, but it's been added to to include Earth and Moon. 3) The turtle glyph was possibly re-imagined as a turtle god or spirit while the alligator mound was reimagined as a lizard.
Minora glyphs & Mound (see Figures 40-41)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Nothing offered but.... 2) Most definitely not Jewish in origins²³⁸ 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Evidence of Jewish "Lost Ten Tribes"²³⁹ travelers in Siberia, America, and Sweden. (Diffusion theory) 2) Another plasmaglyph formation seen around the world. 3) Replicates a strengthening current-syphon²⁴⁰ prior to a massive discharge.

²³² <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Awen>

²³³ Not to anyone trained in tracking. But if it were a foot, notice it is the **left** print.

²³⁴ The instep (medial) should be curved (arched) and the lateral aspect of the foot straight, not the other way around.

²³⁵ Ohio. http://www.ohiohistorycentral.org/w/Alligator_Mound

²³⁶ <http://www.georgiasfossils.com/uploads/3/7/6/1/37616615/alligator-thermal-enclave.jpg?1467758644>

²³⁷ Nor would the Rat Snake, the only egg-eating snake in Eastern US.

²³⁸ Apparently the idea that Hebrew/Jewish people could sail seems impossible. The author can only mention the Victorian anti-semitism of Europe in the formation days of early Archaeology, and shrugs his shoulders. There appears to be no logical reason why not. It's just "because."

²³⁹ Here the author offers that they possibly went in ten different directions. But the author does not think the mound and glyphs are Jewish.

²⁴⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VAwnxlc0-6E>

<p>Concentric Sun Glyphs (and spiral suns) (see Figures 32-34,36-38)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Native just love spirals 2) They were testing out their basic cognitive art skills, like Kindergarten students (though we are talking most likely adult males) 3) No explanation for concentric suns offered 4) The author will donate a theory: a sun halo in the sky (through cirrus clouds) and a Moon Dog²⁴¹. However, both only provide a single ring, while these concentric circles are always multiple rings²⁴². 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Plasma shells (sheaths) 2) Planet rings of Jupiter and Saturn 3) Paths of orbits of large moons observed²⁴³ 4) Glowing plasmaspheres (Spheres of Heaven) for Venus and Mars²⁴⁴ 5) Electric Comets passing near to each other²⁴⁵
<p>Henges and C-henges and glyphs (see Figures 26,35,37,39,42-46, S & P plates)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The henge calendar is a very unsophisticated and oversized way of doing something that could also have been done at a smaller and more practical scale 2) The C-henge is explained with adding and entrance... but then why wouldn't regular henges (circles) have entrances? 3) Sometimes they have four entrances, sometimes 8 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) All the henges are explainable via Birkeland current plasma arc discharges²⁴⁶ 2) C-henges are explained via crater-rim discharge at end of arc stroke 3) Multiple entrances are added after the one discharge, in order to honor the Celtic cross shape sun glyph, which was the same Midnight Sun seen everywhere, but now remembered in antiquity as the power of the Creator God (Tiawara)

²⁴¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Moon_dog

²⁴² Anywhere from 2 to 15, with some exceptions no doubt.

²⁴³ The author feels this is unlikely as there appears to be no other attempt at pathway representation in aboriginal astro-archaeology. Also, there are plenty of discussions of the Aten (circular enclosure) and the Khu(t)/henhenu (circular orbit) in worldwide glyphology, and these do not refer to orbit alone but to a halo-like glow around the cosmic egg (Khat/shentit); Translations of the ancient Egyptian are by D Talbot

²⁴⁴ [4], see Spheres of Heaven and Spheres of Earth. An excellent demonstration of these spheres in motion can be found in this hyperlapse video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oagszCmJLpU>

²⁴⁵ The author feels this is highly unlikely because the glyphs do not display dynamism.

²⁴⁶ Essentially co-axial, concentric circle discharges. See [5], section on Birkeland Currents, pp 28-32

Figure 16 - Caliper measurements²⁴⁷ of various Turkey feet shows definite differential

Table 7 - Summary of Figure 16

(1) A = 0.89	B = 0.51	C = 0.58	D = 0.043
(2) A = 0.63	B = 0.43	C = 0.44	D = 0.045
(3) A/D = .363/.038 = 9.55	(4) .495/.055 = 9.34	(5) .378/.029 = 13.03	(6) .476/.029 = 16.4
(7) .580/.040 = 14.5	Avg ²⁴⁸ A=.76, B=.47, C=.51, D=.044	Avg A/D (2 samples) = 17.27	Avg A/D (7 samples ²⁴⁹) = 14.68

²⁴⁷ In fractions of the inch using caliper.

²⁴⁸ 2 samples

²⁴⁹ More samples might be taken but their differences are inscrutable. The point here is to show the A/D ratio is not accidental and is both visible and statistically relevant.

Figure 17 - Eagle Mound; A/D (same convention) = $145/9 = 16.1^{250}$

²⁵⁰ 8.8% diff with 7 sample avg

$$\frac{C_2}{B} = 1.17 \quad \frac{C_1}{B} = 1.03 \quad \text{avg} = 1.075$$

Figure 18 - Secondary Analysis with fine pencil and dual limb vectors on C limb (right)
 $A/D = 148/17 = 8.7$; $A/E = 148/7 = 21.14$; Avg 2 vectors ratio (composite A/D) = 14.92^{251}

²⁵¹ 1.6% diff with 7 sample avg; -7.9% diff with Figure 17

Figure 19 - Alligator Analysis attempt 1; $c/d = A/D$ previous Figures = $36/5 = 7.2^{252}$

²⁵² Compare with Figure 18 $A/D = 8.7$, or a -20.1% difference; but their absolute difference (1.5) is much more significant when considered against the avg ~14-15

Eagle Mound: $\frac{A}{D} = 8.7$

$\frac{C}{B} = 1.03 \quad \frac{2}{B} = 1.12 \quad A_{avg} = 1.075$

4/22/2017

$\frac{8.7 - 8.35}{8.35} = .042 \text{ or } 4.2\%$

$\frac{1.121 - 1.075}{1.075} = .043 \text{ or } 4.3\%$

$\frac{1.181 - 1.12}{1.12} = .054 \text{ or } 5.4\%$

Alligator Mound

$\frac{A}{D} = \frac{1.428}{.171} = 8.35$

$\frac{B}{C} = \frac{1.147}{.971} = 1.181$

alligator-mound.jpg (600x388)

Figure 20 - $A/D = 1.428/.171 = 8.35^{253}$

Note that throughout these analysis, the B/C ratios all remain remarkably close to 1, but not exactly 1. The author is sure that a further revelation can be gleaned from this with more on site analysis.

²⁵³ 13.8 % diff with Figure 19; therefore the results can only be conclusive with an on site investigation. However, the difference remains clear and unambiguous. Which is the main point of the exercise. 8.35 is >8000% the ratio to expect with perfectly acceptable symmetry, considering time, erosion, being built by hand, etc...

138. view of the State Rock
petroglyph site.

139. Petroglyphs at State
Rock.

Figure 21 - State Rock, KY Petroglyphs - "Turkey tracks"; credit: Coy et al...²⁵⁴

The asymmetry is easily seen (right track) but obviously easy to miss, considering the medium used. Suggests a changing alignment. Therefore some tracks are broken to the right, some to the left, and some almost dead centered (as above in center).

²⁵⁴ Ibid. p. 112

Figure 22 - Bear Track Glyph; Credit: Coy et al...²⁵⁵

Figure 23 - Bear tracks; credit: thepinsta.com

Comparing Figure 22 and 23, it is plainly obvious the former is no bear track, as it misses key anatomical elements. If Lascaux has taught us anything it is that natives had an eye for detail. It may be said that this is instead some type of strange human print. But that argument also falls flat upon anatomical comparison. Note the 5 *circular* hemi-spheroidal depressions. Note the largeness and full roundness of the central depression. It seems plainly clear to the author that the artist was trying to convey the change in the solar system where the five most important gods/bodies (Venus, Mars, Moon, Saturn, Jupiter) were to go round the central sun, while a destroyed oblong cluster was to form in space. This may have even been an alignment, but it need not be to be a model.

²⁵⁵ Ibid. P. 86

It is, most emphatically, not a bear track.

Figure 24 - Wickliffe, KY Petroglyphs; credit: Coy et al...²⁵⁶

This is perhaps one of the most amazing glyph collections in the lot. #20 is both an Awen and asymmetrical²⁵⁷, clearly. #19 is designed to show the removal of the plasma stream, and revelation of bodies underneath. #17 is a bridge with Awen symbol and the Alligator formation. #1 shows the "Stamp of the Great Foot" #6 shows clearly the heel seen in Figure 21 above. #15 makes it plainly obvious these are not even normal human feet. #2 is probably a close-up of the event, or the start. #4 shows what happens when charge depletes and leaves some of the alignment out of sight. #5 shows extreme sheathing discharge. #7 to #8 perhaps the bridge of these changes. It is clear through that the events are repeated over a series of nights and then recorded *as seen* probably from a hilltop. Can anything be clearer, though, than #18 and #9 that these are neither turkey tracks, nor left feet? Even if the hypothesis of this paper is incorrect, the mainstream interpretation cannot possibly be correct.

Anatomically, please note as well the impossible anatomy of the feet. While #10 and 11 might be said to support the "records of feet" idea, the simple fact is this also bolsters the argument of being the **Creator's foot**.
²⁵⁸

²⁵⁶ Ibid. p.137

²⁵⁷ A/D ratios would be difficult to be reliable, even with a caliper. On site measurements would need to be performed.

²⁵⁸ Ie - the one person worth recording.

2. Human foot- and hand prints on Boulder
#2 in the Sparks Indian Rock House.

Figure 25 - Actual hand and foot glyphs, Sparks Indian Rock House; Credit: Coy et al...²⁵⁹

²⁵⁹ Ibid. p.53

Figure 26 - Tar Springs Petroglyphs; Credit: Coy et al...²⁶⁰

A fascinating petroglyph site with clear astronomical data, demonstrating also a lack of paired Turkey feet, but a plethora of over-writing of alignment and plasma shape changes (#11,13). We also see in #4 a clear reference to the Mars-Venus discharge event, and **separately** in #1, 2, and 3 a reference to the Saturn, Jupiter, and *other* ringed system, probably Uranus (at the time that it was tilted by impact), possibly the same planet as #5, (Mars). Note also #12 is the parallel of Figure 24.12 & 24.13.

The author offers no specific explanation for #14, but #8 is our Awen conjunction. #7 is unclear, perhaps an earlier carving? #13 shows the bowed, centralized "feathered plume" of the power conjunction which inspired the Awen symbol worldwide. It is probably faded due to antiquity. Overall Tar Springs records several phases of astronomical events, but most important for humanity the end of the Jovian and beginning of the Age of Ares, and the Exodus cataclysm²⁶¹.

The most likely explanation for the *reason* of recording is that, as was seen in Sumeria and Indian myth, another cataclysm was expected as there had been in the Clash of the Titans, between the Saturnian and Jovian era.

²⁶⁰ Ibid. p.16

²⁶¹ c. 1600 BCE, I Velikovsky, see "Worlds in Collision"

Figure 27 - Turtle Glyph, Big Sinking Creek, KY; Credit: Coy et al...²⁶²

The fifth "leg" is just visible in the middle of the right flank. The actual shape of the shell is octagonal, with quite a distinct difference in the lengths of some sides. There is also a large angle difference in the vectors of the hind 2 legs, while the front right leg (top-left), is possibly the Awen conjunction. However, unlike in previous rock art sites, it would be facing North, and that is contradictory. Figures 16, 24, and 26 all clearly show a southward (general) bias, which corresponds with the Celtic symbol for the Awen, which is downward. See Figure 28 at right.²⁶³

However Figure 21 disputes that this is not always the case.

Figure 29 - Analysis of Octagon lengths

²⁶² Ibid. p.81

²⁶³ Credit: Wikipedia

Figure 30 - Burnt Ridge "Stick-man"; Credit: Coy et al...²⁶⁴

Note asymmetrical awen on right. Note also the plasma discharges on hands and feet (4 fingers) which match the Nazca lines as well as the Thunderbird or "Buzzard" glyph from the same site (Table 2).

Figure 31 - Crow Hollow Shelter; asymmetrical Awen glyph with clear breaks left.; credit: Coy et al...²⁶⁵

²⁶⁴ Ibid. p.95

²⁶⁵ Ibid. p.62

Figure 32 - Close-up of Concentric "Circle" glyph; credit: Coy et al...²⁶⁶

A very close zoom of the above glyph demonstrates both the expert artistry of the artist, and the attempts to make a clearly defined hexagon. This dates the piece to the spectacular co-planar rotation²⁶⁷ phase of the Saturnian period, back into Zep Tepi. Being underneath a rockshelter, this piece has been well protected, and is at least 7,000 years old, but probably over 12,000 years old. Mankind was not able to see Saturn's hexagonal pole clearly again until the 20th century²⁶⁸. Please note it's spiral interior. This will also help date the spiral glyphs of every culture that has made them (with corresponding designs).

Figure 33 - Saturn's North pole, spiral and hexagon
Credit: AAS Nova/NASA JPL

Next page: Figure 34 - Analysis of hexagonal glyph

²⁶⁶ Ibid. p.79

²⁶⁷ <https://arxiv.org/abs/1301.0446>; galaxies, but explanation still works the same.

²⁶⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Saturn%27s_hexagon

90. Concentric circle in the Big Turtle Rockshelter petroglyph site.

$\Delta_{max} = .991$

$\Delta_{min} = .117$

$\Delta_{mean} = .554$

- $.064 \left\{ \begin{array}{l} D_1 = 0.536 \\ D_2 = 0.605 \\ D_3 = 0.582 \\ D_4 = 0.600 \end{array} \right. \begin{array}{l} >.623 \\ >.018 \end{array}$

$\frac{\Delta_{mean}^{hex}}{\Delta_{mean}^{circle}} = 14.97$

$\frac{D = 65}{E = 13} = 5$

$\frac{2.402}{-.549} = 4.38$

$\Delta_{max} = .069''$
 $\Delta_{min} = .005''$
 $\Delta_{avg} = .044''$
 $\Delta_{mean} = .037$

The handwriting says,

$$L = 34 \text{ mm}$$

$$k = 30 \text{ mm}$$

$$d_{\text{center}} = 12 \text{ mm}$$

$$r = 30 \text{ mm}$$

$$A_{\text{outside}} = 2827.4 \text{ mm}^2$$

$$A_{\text{center}} = 113.1 \text{ mm}^2$$

$$A_{\text{O}} / A_{\text{C}} = 25$$

$$D_{\text{hexagon}} = 65 \text{ mm} \quad \text{or } 2.402''$$

$$C_{\text{center}} = 13 \text{ mm} \quad \text{or } 0.549''$$

$$D/C = 5 \quad \text{or } 4.38$$

Below is in inches (caliper)

$$L_1 = 1.683$$

$$D_1 = 0.536$$

$$\Delta_{\text{max}} = 0.069$$

$$\Delta_{\text{mean}} = 0.037$$

$$L_2 = 1.338$$

$$D_2 = 0.605$$

$$\Delta_{\text{min}} = 0.005$$

$$L_3 = 0.692$$

$$D_3 = 0.582$$

$$\Delta_{\text{avg}} = 0.044$$

$$L_4 = 1.221$$

$$D_4 = 0.600$$

$$L_5 = \text{indistinct}$$

$$D_{\text{avg}} = 0.064$$

$$L_6 = 0.969$$

$$\Delta_{\text{max}} = 0.991$$

$$\Delta_{\text{mean}} = 0.554$$

$$\Delta_{\text{hex}} / \Delta_{\text{circle}} = 14.97 \sim 15^{269}$$

$$\Delta_{\text{min}} = 0.117$$

²⁶⁹ This shows that the differentials of the hexagon are significantly larger than for the center, meaning it was purposeful

circle + "octagon" - Amazon

k=11 l=12

Figure 35 - Amazonia Earthworks that reflect Newark & Chillicothe shapes

Hand-written measurements are written: $k=11$, $l=12$. Because the angle of the photograph is too oblique, it is not possible to measure the other lengths, only the two nearest. However, as expected, and proposed, they are not equal. Erosion and destruction from construction equipment cannot change length, although the corners might be affected. The author proposes that on site work be done. However, based on the turtle glyph from Kentucky, it is not expected for them to be equal. The Newark and Chillicothe octagons are likely equidistant because of artistic and functional needs of symmetry. However, the original formation in the sky would not have been. It is proposed by the author that the octagon was the Jupiter pole²⁷⁰, while the "circle" may have been the hexagonal Saturnian pole. There isn't enough data to prove one or the other. But their proximity to each-other in myth, and rock art is highly suggestive.

²⁷⁰ <https://www.jpl.nasa.gov/news/news.php?feature=7096>

Peru

$$r_c : r_a = 2.125$$

$$r_c : r_b = 3.77$$

$$r_a : r_b = 1.77$$

$$A_c = 881.59$$

$$d = 33.5$$

$$r_c = 301$$

$$r_b = 9$$

$$r_a = 16$$

67

65

$$66^2 = 4356$$

$$\frac{r_a}{r_b} = 1.77$$

$$\frac{A_c}{A_s} = .202$$

Figure 36 - Nazca Circle+Square earthwork effigy (very advanced); calculations using caliper

Measurements of the ratios of the radii and areas are included, as shown. Results are inconclusive or require more detailed analysis. They do not appear to be equivalent ratios with Newark.

Figure 37 - Newark Earthworks, including Eagle Mound

Initial analysis precludes the "road" theory, however the plasma streamer hypothesis remains open. Not the proximity and alignments of the multiple gods and sun gods. It is suggested that actually this is a site built in phases *because of* changes in the pantheon. Each new phase necessitated a new earthwork construction, and the updated vision was then unified into a grander celestial theology. The last streamer may have been leading to a new construction but was abandoned for one reason or another. The disjointed aspects of the plasma streamers only indicated breaks in the plasma current (wind).

Figure 38 - Nazca "Monkey" Earthwork

The hexagonal and circular space are unmissable and compare nicely with Amazonia and Newark/Chillicothe. The presence of differently toed/fingered appendages are a clear indicator that the Nazca were not recording an actual animal, real or stylized, but something grander (hence the need for size). My suggestion would be that they actually figured the rough "shadow" size as the human would reckon it, and made the gods the right size. Therefore I propose that for a brief instant in human history the gods' approach rendered them massive in the sky, indeed and more prominent even than Saturn-Kronos would have been.

Being Nazca the above formation corresponds to the Mars/Venus collapse of alignment, which supports the Newark/Hopewell dating when Allegewi transitioned and updated Great Serpent Mound (spirals again). It also is supported by the famous Chinese saying from the Zhou period forward, "Heaven is round, Earth is square."

38. Drawing of petroglyphs at Dismal Rock.

Figure 39 - Dismal Rock, KY Petroglyphs; Credit Coy et al...²⁷¹

This glyph is one of the most important sites. It shows the southeastern pointing Awen, wide, that then changes direction, pointing southwest, then changes to asymmetrical, and then to the major dispersion and discharge, forming what appears (to the unassuming) to be a therianthrope, and finally ending with a single conjunction (Earth and Moon is presumed) Meanwhile, nearby, the spiral shapes of two gods looms: Saturn and Jupiter. This excludes those two gas giants with their plasma shells (or orbits) from the conjunction, leaving Mars, Venus, Earth, and Moon.

²⁷¹ Ibid. p.42

Figure 40 - White's Petroglyph ; Credit: Coy et al...²⁷²

Close zoom in reveals the concentric henge glyph, multiple celestial bodies with plasma sheaths of mostly spherical shape, but tapered in their poles. It also reveals that the orbit of the god planets (then Zeus and Hera in Greece) were close, but favoring the planet Jupiter in size and radiation. Nearby, Uranus and Neptune remained to play the part of the younger brothers.

This glyph can be reliably dated from 4,500 YBP-8,000 YBP. Most likely it was during the mythic time of Horus and Set, given the knowledge of Horus' one eye. However, in a strange irony, when Jupiter was smaller (receded prior to approach), the planet played the part of Set, ripping apart Osiris (Atum-Re/Ptah). This raises some strong questions as to how Zeus/Odin/Set/Jehovah/Enlil became the hero while Kronos/Bor/Osiris/EI/Enki became a sister-goddess. Originally the mother-Earth goddess had been the womb/thigh/cosmic egg within which the One God birthed himself. But after his rending apart, the planet Saturn, no longer glowing, became a symbol of "1-deer/Jaw of the Tiger... a lovely female goddess"²⁷³

²⁷² Ibid. p.118

²⁷³ "The Saturn Myth," D Talbott

150. Circular petroglyphs at Nada Tunnel 2.

Figure 41 - Nada Tunnel Concentric Circle glyphs, Red River Gorge, KY; Credit: Coy et al...²⁷⁴

The author feels this is most likely a more modern reproduction in the Hopewell or Woodland era due to lack of wearing. Sandstone is generally very soft. Unless this rock shelter is well protected, then it may compare in age to figure 40.

²⁷⁴ Ibid. p. 121

19. Circle with cross petroglyph at Reedyville.

Figure 42 - Celtic cross glyph at Reedyville, KY; Credit: Coy et al...²⁷⁵

Either evidence of diffusionism or of the plasmaglyphs phenomenon, as this glyph is found worldwide, including and primarily in Egypt and Sumer. It is, in fact, still the symbol used for Earth for it was, at first, the universal symbol for the floating island-paradise, which is also a worldwide phenomena.²⁷⁶

²⁷⁵ Ibid. p.27

²⁷⁶ Again, refer to "The Saturn Myth" and the author's summary spreadsheet, previously cited.

Figure 43 - Menorah Mound, OH²⁷⁷

Figure 44 - Menorah Head glyph, Siberia (5000 BCE)²⁷⁸

Rayed head motif on Boulder #4 in Sparks Indian Rock House.

Figure 45 - Sparks Indian Rock House glyphs; Credit: Coy et al...²⁷⁹

²⁷⁷ Credit: OSU

²⁷⁸ Note also the celtic cross with unique 4 dot quadrant design

²⁷⁹ Ibid. p.55 ;note the C-henge just right of center.

Figure 46 - Sparks Indian Rock House, KY boulder #1; Credit: Coy et al...²⁸⁰

This petroglyph site has a lot going on. The Awen down low at the bottom, alignments at the top. A rayed solar disc (or another "turtle formation" at right²⁸¹, and beautifully done bass relief on the concentric glyph and the Mars/Venus alignment, showing the radiance of the plasma sheath during the "nightly mating"²⁸².

²⁸⁰ Ibid. p. 51

²⁸¹ Many solar glyphs are semicircles, therefore there must have been a lit side of Helios, as it faced Sol. Remember: Helios was not the sun, it was Saturn, and then Jupiter.

²⁸² <https://sites.google.com/site/charlesjharwood/forbidden-love-of-venus-and-mars> ; remember in the Greek tradition Athena *fought* Ares, but in the Roman tradition Venus mated with him. All of it was energy exchange due to electric-arc discharge.

Figure 47 - Martin Fork, KY glyphs; Credit: Coy et al...²⁸³ and 48 - Waving Man earthwork, Nazca, Peru

²⁸³ Ibid. p.109

Figure 49 - The Great Man at Reedyville petroglyphs, KY; Credit: Coy et al....²⁸⁴

This petroglyph has a lot going on: discharge, the awen glyphs, the 5 legged Great Man (right flank), the 2-faced god (Janus, possibly Jupiter here, half lit by the sun), the 3 planet conjunction glow (Moon, Mars, Venus), the misshapen feet, the swastika glyph²⁸⁵, ancillary constellations, the Heavenly crown as it would have really appeared, and lastly the X within a circle glyph which has an Egyptian counterpart, and means Paradise (lit: "Holy Abode")²⁸⁶.

The best part of this site is that it gives us the proper celestial alignments . It also provide the native view of the hand of God creating the Thunderbolt to cast down, center left. Not the size of the tripart conjunction in comparison: this must have been a massive plasma formation.

²⁸⁴ Ibid. p.26

²⁸⁵ Center-right; the well known swastika glyph is a worldwide phenomenon. More cannot be said here, so the author refers to: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Swastika>

²⁸⁶ The Saturn Myth, p.119

Figure 50 - Asphalt Rock, KY glyphs; Credit: Coy et al...²⁸⁷

This is the final and best representation of the glyphs, in terms of artistic quality. It shows the Great Man/Squatter Man²⁸⁸ (with misshapen hand), with toroids as predicted by Dr. Peratt at Los Alamos, as well as makes clear the native Heaven was obviously filled with plasma energy (and therefore was not the Northern Lights). We also see the gate sign, and this may have been the inspiration for the worldwide gate shape, especially in Asia at the same latitudes.

²⁸⁷ Ibid. p.44

²⁸⁸ The author doubts this is an alien, giant, or bigfoot.

Figure 51 - The Black Dragon Canyon, Utah "Pterosaur" glyph; an example of inappropriate classification; credit: LiveScience.com²⁸⁹

This glyph sums it up for us (though it is in the west). It clearly depicts the fifth leg is a type of fire. There is a massive comet-dragon. But most importantly the Owl-faced Great Man discharges streams of energy at the animals below on Earth.

Until recently this glyph was the battleground of debate because it originally appeared to people guessing to be a Pterodactyl in flight. While the mainstream had, and has no answer; "Young-Earth Creationists" used it to say that man had clearly lived with the dinosaurs until recently. However, this is clearly false.

Cosmic Egg Glyph and the Peter's Village Enclosure

The famous Aten symbol (Seb) of previously mentioned Egyptian history, is, of course, egg-shaped.²⁹⁰ It was, however, frequently adjusted into circle enclosures (Khu(n)/Tuat) and oval "womb" enclosures (shentit/khat), such as shown in Table 2. The following depiction was also found in Sumeria:

Figure 52 - Mother Goddess in Sumeria; Credit: D Talbott²⁹¹

If you'll notice, the left eye is larger than the right (from our perspective). This matches the chronologically simultaneous First Kingdoms glyph, and helps us to date Figure 45 (right face, the older one)

²⁸⁹ <https://www.livescience.com/51892-photos-utah-rock-art.html>

²⁹⁰ Ibid. p.82

²⁹¹ Ibid. p.246

and via the left face in that glyph and the one in Figure 53 below, we now have an entire (small) sequence of alignments with actual plasma corona (sheathing).

Figure 53 - "Head motif", Sparks Indian Rock House, KY; credit: Coy et al...²⁹²

The interesting thing about this egg is that it is commonly lost in translation, due to the fact that multiple cultures across the world refer to the egg as a womb, thigh, ship, circle/halo, etc...²⁹³ and it has several unique features.

Taking a look at the Peter's Mound enclosure once again, but larger, let us freely speculate on how some of these features may have appeared to the natives.

²⁹² Ibid. p.51

²⁹³ Ibid. Author's Saturn Myth chart

Figure 54 - Peter's Village Enclosure; credit: Squire & Davis²⁹⁴

Taken in without context, the best theory offered and promoted by Squire and Davis was that it was some form of ancient fortress. However, this fails on two accounts at a minimum. The first is that it lacks the proper number of defensible entrances. Its size is also not too small, but the entrance would be for the size. The second fault is that the wall is breached by the water, rather than utilizing it, as would be expected (for example at a place like Toltec Mounds, Arkansas.) The author, therefore dismisses the fortification idea out of hand.

It is rather, the shape, and the peculiar features described as well as the small divot, which seem to suggest a more enigmatic meaning. The fact that there was a cosmic egg motif, worldwide, is already well documented. The Chinese referred to this cosmic egg as the birthplace of Pangu, the World-Man who created humans and yin and yang. It was surrounded by the Chaos Waters (Hundun). Therefore, it is entirely likely, that this encroachment of water was a reflection either of the plasma sheath or of the Milky Way, which has also been referred to as chaotic waters, in some cultures.

If it were not the Cosmic Egg, there seems to be no other plausible explanation for the shape. The author does not make the claim that this is for certain the correct hypothesis, but it does fit the most of the necessary points. It would be advisable for an expert in Egyptology and Mayanology to compare this motif with those from Egypt²⁹⁵ and MesoAmerica, looking for confirmation or elimination point by point.

As for the divot, the author has no specific hypothesis for its purpose or meaning.

²⁹⁴ "Ancient Monuments of the Mississippi Valley", Squire & Davis

²⁹⁵ Or indeed via the Dogon <https://kachina2012.wordpress.com/2007/03/30/dogon-cosmic-egg/>

Mesopotamian cosmogony: comparing and contrasting with Native American cataclysmic myths

The readership must forgive but this lengthy exposition from the Enuma Elish²⁹⁶ is crucial to this part of the paper, which while compelling so far to say the least, is missing the necessary cross fiber of non-American evidence and testimony.

*"THE FOURTH TABLE"*²⁹⁷

They prepared for him a lordly chamber,

Before his fathers as prince he took his place.

"Thou art chiefest among the great gods,

Thy fate is unequalled, thy word is Anu!

O Marduk, thou art chiefest among the great gods,²⁹⁸

Thy fate is unequalled, thy word is Anu!

Henceforth not without avail shall be thy command,

In thy power shall it be to exalt²⁹⁹ and to abase³⁰⁰.

Established shall be the word of thy mouth, irresistible shall be thy command³⁰¹,

None among the gods shall transgress thy boundary³⁰².

Abundance, the desire of the shrines of the gods,

Shall be established in thy sanctuary, even though they lack offerings.

*O Marduk, thou art our avenger!*³⁰³

We give thee sovereignty over the whole world.

Sit thou down in might; be exalted in thy command.

*Thy **weapon** shall never lose its power; it shall crush thy foe.*

O Lord, spare the life of him that putteth his trust in thee,

But as for the god who began the rebellion, pour out his life."³⁰⁴

Then set they in their midst a garment,

And unto Marduk, - their first-born they spake:

"May thy fate, O lord, be supreme among the gods,

To destroy and to create; speak thou the word, and thy command shall be fulfilled.

Command now and let the garment vanish;

And speak the word again and let the garment reappear!

Then he spake with his mouth, and the garment vanished;

Again he commanded it, and the garment reappeared.

When the gods, his fathers, beheld the fulfillment of his word,

They rejoiced, and they did homage unto him, saying, " Marduk is king!"

They bestowed upon him the scepter, and the throne, and the ring,

²⁹⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/En%C3%BBma_Eli%C5%A1

²⁹⁷ **Bold emphasis added** <http://www.sacred-texts.com/ane/enuma.htm> transl. LW King, 1902

²⁹⁸ Exaltation of the war-god from the people at the time of Sumer, probably in the early Age of Aries.

²⁹⁹ The gods

³⁰⁰ Humanity

³⁰¹ tidal/electrogravitic influence?

³⁰² Our first point for Jupiter being the real Marduk; or Venus' early male form. Ishtar and Athena often had beards in depiction.

³⁰³ This seems to be referring to the god of war, the world's foremost favorite god. Here, though, our means the gods' avenger (against Tiamat).

³⁰⁴ If the gender is specific here, it is not clear which god (Hodr? Hephaestus? Planet Uranus?) is being referred to here.

They give him an invincible weaponry which overwhelmeth the foe.³⁰⁵

*Go, and **cut off the life of Tiamat,***

And let the wind carry her blood into secret places."

*After the gods his fathers had decreed for the lord his fate,
They caused him to set out on a path of prosperity and success.*

He made ready the bow, he chose his weapon,

He slung a spear upon him and fastened it..

He raised the club, in his right hand he grasped it³⁰⁶,

The bow and the quiver he hung at his side.

He set the lightning in front of him,

With burning flame he filled his body.

*He made **a net to enclose the inward parts of Tiamat,***

*The **four winds** he stationed so that nothing of her might escape;*

The South wind and the North wind and the East wind and the West wind

*He brought near to the net, the **gift of his father Anu.***

He created the evil wind, and the tempest, and the hurricane,

And the fourfold wind, and the sevenfold wind, and the whirlwind, and the wind which had no equal;

He sent forth the winds which he had created, the seven of them;

To disturb the inward parts of Tiamat, they followed after him.

Then the lord raised the thunderbolt, his mighty weapon,

He mounted the chariot, the storm unequalled for terror,

He harnessed and yoked unto it four horses,

Destructive, ferocious, overwhelming, and swift of pace;

... were their teeth, they were flecked with foam;

They were skilled in... , they had been trained to trample underfoot.

... . mighty in battle,

Left and right....

His garment was... , he was clothed with terror,

With overpowering brightness his head was crowned.

Then he set out, he took his way,

And toward the raging Tiamat he set his face.

On his lips he held ...,

... he grasped in his hand.

Then they beheld him, the gods beheld him,

The gods his fathers beheld him, the gods beheld him.

And the lord drew nigh, he gazed upon the inward parts of Tiamat,

He perceived the muttering of Kingu, her spouse.³⁰⁷

As Marduk gazed, Kingu was troubled in his gait,³⁰⁸

His will was destroyed and his motions ceased.

And the gods, his helpers, who marched by his side,

Beheld their leader's..., and their sight was troubled.

³⁰⁵ Thunderbolt of the Gods - plasma-electricity. Plasma sheathing appears to be the garment.

³⁰⁶ See England's "Abbas Giant Man" earthwork https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cerne_Abbas_Giant

³⁰⁷ Most regard this as the proto-moon's name. Again, it is possible this story is the destruction of Mars by Venus, in which case the moon would have been Mars'. The author takes the former position over the latter due to the age of the text, supposing it is a retelling of an oral myth dating back to 7000-8000 YBP.

³⁰⁸ Orbit.

But Tiamat... , she turned not her neck,
 With lips that failed not she uttered rebellious words:
 "... thy coming as lord of the gods,
 From their places have they gathered, in thy place are they! "

Then the lord raised the thunderbolt, his mighty weapon,
 And against Tiamat, who was raging, thus he sent the word:
 Thou art become great, thou hast exalted thyself on high,
 And thy heart hath prompted thee to call to battle.
 ... their fathers...,
 ... their... thou hatest...
 Thou hast exalted Kingu to be thy spouse,
 Thou hast... him, that, even as Anu, he should issue decrees.
 thou hast followed after evil,
 And against the gods my fathers thou hast contrived thy wicked plan.³⁰⁹
 Let then thy host be equipped, let thy weapons be girded on!
 Stand! I and thou, let us join battle!
 When Tiamat heard these words,
 She was like one possessed, .she lost her reason.
 Tiamat uttered wild, piercing cries,³¹⁰
She trembled and shook to her very foundations.³¹¹
 She recited an incantation, she pronounced her spell,
 And the gods of the battle cried out for their weapons.
 Then advanced Tiamat and Marduk, **the counselor of the gods;**³¹²
 To the fight they came on, **to the battle they drew nigh.**
 The lord spread out his net and caught her,³¹³
And the evil wind that was behind him he let loose in her face.
 As Tiamat opened her mouth to its full extent,
 He drove in the evil wind, while as yet she had not shut her lips.
 The terrible winds filled her belly,³¹⁴
 And her courage was taken from her, and her mouth she opened wide.
 He seized the spear and burst her belly,
 He severed her inward parts, he pierced her heart³¹⁵.
 He overcame her and cut off her life;
 He cast down her body and **stood upon it.**
 When he had slain Tiamat, the leader,
 Her might was broken, her host was scattered.³¹⁶
 And the gods her helpers, who marched by her side,
 Trembled, and were afraid, and turned back.
 They took to flight to save their lives;

³⁰⁹ The change from Saturnian orbit to Jovian? Or to be alone?

³¹⁰ Earth-groans

³¹¹ Massive Earthquakes

³¹² This may signal that the original Marduk was the planet Mercury (Hermes), which if sent from Jupiter, may have been seen by some cultures, such as the Greeks as Jupiter himself. Indeed, afterwards, Marduk appears to become the planet Jupiter.

³¹³ Either meteorites/plumes or electro-gravity itself.

³¹⁴ The atmosphere appears to have been opened up, and received air from Mars or Mercury.

³¹⁵ With cosmic lightning "Thunderbolts"

³¹⁶ Apparently captured moons

But they were surrounded, so that they could not escape.
He took them captive, he broke their weapons;
In the net they were caught and in the snare they sat down.
The ... of the world they filled with cries of grief.
They received punishment from him, they were held in bondage.³¹⁷
And on the eleven creatures which she had filled with the power of striking terror,
Upon the troop of devils, who marched at her...,
He brought affliction, their strength he...;
Them and their opposition he trampled under his feet.
Moreover, Kingu, who had been exalted over them,
He conquered, and with the god Dug-ga he counted him.
He took from him the Tablets of Destiny that were not rightly his,
He sealed them with a seal and in his own breast he laid them.³¹⁸
Now after the hero Marduk had conquered and cast down his enemies,
And had made the arrogant foe even like
And had fully established Ansar's triumph over the enemy
And had attained the purpose of Nudimmud,
Over the captive gods he strengthened his durance,
And unto Tiamat, whom he had conquered, he returned.³¹⁹
*And the lord stood upon Tiamat's hinder parts,*³²⁰
And with his merciless club he smashed her skull.
He cut through the channels of her blood,
*And he made the North wind bear it away into secret places.*³²¹
*His fathers beheld, and they rejoiced and were glad;*³²²
Presents and gifts they brought unto him.
Then the lord rested, gazing upon her dead body,
While he divided the flesh of the ... , and devised a cunning plan.
*He split her up like a flat fish into two halves,*³²³
One half of her he established as a covering for heaven.
*He fixed a bolt, he stationed a watchman,*³²⁴
And bade them not to let her waters come forth.
He passed through the heavens, he surveyed the regions thereof,
And over against the Deep he set the dwelling of Nudimmud.
And the lord measured the structure of the Deep,
And he founded E-sara, a mansion like unto it.
The mansion E-sara which he created as heaven,
He caused Anu, Bel, and Ea in their districts to inhabit.³²⁵

³¹⁷ Again this appears to be mighty Jupiter, as this is where we find many retrograde and strange moons, even new ones.

³¹⁸ <https://carnegiescience.edu/news/dozen-new-moons-jupiter-discovered-including-one-%E2%80%99Coddball%E2%80%9D>
³¹⁸ The author speculates that the original tablets were prophesied asteroids that would come destroy humanity, but now absorbed by this god-planet.

³¹⁹ Upon the next orbital pass.

³²⁰ Multiple references to legs and feet.

³²¹ From this we can see a reflection of the Osiris-Set myth.

³²² Another argument for Mercury, aka Heimdall, son of 9 mothers.

³²³ Sinking of Atlantis?

³²⁴ Ie - the moon

³²⁵ The gas giants Saturn, Jupiter (Ba'al), and Neptune. It is also a vague possibility that Ea here could be Uranus, or even a very unlikely possibility that Uranus (the planet) could be Tiamat. However, the narrative most seems to fit 3 gas giants,

THE FIFTH TABLET

*He (Marduk) made the stations for the great gods;
The stars, their images, as the stars of the Zodiac, he fixed.³²⁶
He ordained the year and into sections he divided it;³²⁷
For the twelve months he fixed three stars.
After he had ... the days of the year ... images,
He founded the station of Nibir [the planet Jupiter] to determine their bounds,³²⁸
That none might err or go astray,
He set the station of Bel and Ea along with him.³²⁹
He opened great gates on both sides,
He made strong the bolt on the left and on the right.³³⁰
In the midst thereof he fixed the zenith;³³¹
The Moon-god he caused to shine forth, the night he entrusted to him.³³²
He appointed him, a being of the night, to determine the days;³³³
Every month without ceasing with the crown he covered him, saying:
"At the beginning of the month, when thou shinest upon the land,
Thou commandest the horns to determine six days,
And on the seventh day to divide the crown.
On the fourteenth day thou shalt stand opposite, the half....
When the Sun-god on the foundation of heaven...thee,
The ... thou shalt cause to ..., and thou shalt make his...
... unto the path of the Sun-god shalt thou cause to draw nigh,
And on the ... day thou shalt stand opposite, and the Sun-god shall...
... to traverse her way."³³⁴*

THE SIXTH TABLET

When Marduk heard the word of the gods,

and this matches the glyphs in KY with two spirals and a nearby 3rd. A final possibility could be that if Venus was blue-green early on, it could be seen as Ea. A final possibility is that Anu became the Sun, Bel and Ea became Jupiter and Saturn respectively. While the author favors one of the models, he cannot rule out the others from this line alone. But it becomes clear that early on Marduk was *not* Jupiter as of yet, but either Mars or Mercury - a limb of might Zeus/Bel.

³²⁶ The orbits and seasons changed, as said in the Bible, and in China and India and Egypt.

³²⁷ From the rebellious 350 days Tiamat had been doing, causing heat waves and droughts, into 365.25 days, which was close to the 360 expected.

³²⁸ [sic]; It is now known that Nibir/Nibiru is likely Planet Nine and is now in the Kuiper Belt or beyond, literally at the outer bounds.

³²⁹ Another point for Mars being the original Marduk

³³⁰ Ie - tidal locking

³³¹ Polaris, a new pole-star; this is so blatant and obvious it cannot be argued otherwise. Therefore all precessional arguments really disappear prior to the Tepe Period. If The Pyramids were built with the precession of the equinoxes in mind, this almost certainly sets them to newer than the Tepe period, at least in their final form. It is a major detraction for the Saharan Atlantis hypothesis.

³³² The "Watchman"

³³³ Ie - to work with the sun.

³³⁴ The entire point of this quote is to mark the clear change in calendrical patterns, as reflected in Chinese times. This is concurrent in the Shang period.

His heart prompted him and he devised a cunning plan.
 He opened his mouth and unto Ea he spake
 That which he had conceived in his heart he imparted unto him:
 "My blood will I take and bone will I fashion
 I will make man, that man may
 I will create man who shall inhabit the earth,
 That the service of the gods may be established, and that their shrines may be built.
But I will alter the ways of the gods, and I will change their paths;³³⁵
 Together shall they be oppressed and unto evil shall they...
 And Ea answered him and spake the word.³³⁶
"... the ... of the gods I have changed
 ... and one...
 ... shall be destroyed and men will I...³³⁷
 ... and the gods .
 ... and they..." [emphasis added]

The author does not pretend to have a completed narrative, for it is clear here that the ancients themselves do not have a completed story, but an amalgamation of events which, inherited in oral form, have become a synthesized "Star Wars" of a sort. Another interpretation follows thusly,

"In the religion of ancient Babylon, Tiamat (Akkadian: TI.AMAT or TAM.TUM, Greek: Θαλάττη Thaláttē) is a primordial goddess of the salt sea, mating with Abzû, the god of fresh water, to produce younger gods. She is the symbol of the chaos of primordial creation. She is referred to as a woman, and described as the glistening one. It is suggested that there are two parts to the Tiamat mythos, the first in which Tiamat is a creator goddess, through a sacred marriage between salt and fresh water, peacefully creating the cosmos through successive generations. In the second Chaoskampf Tiamat is considered the monstrous embodiment of primordial chaos. Some sources identify her with images of a sea serpent or dragon.

In the Enûma Elish, the Babylonian epic of creation, she gives birth to the first generation of deities; her husband, Apsu, correctly assuming they are planning to kill him and usurp his throne, later makes war upon them and is killed. Enraged, she, too, wars upon her husband's murderers, taking on the form of a massive sea dragon, she is then slain by Enki's son, the storm-god Marduk, but not before she had brought forth the monsters of the Mesopotamian pantheon, including the first dragons, whose bodies she filled with "poison instead of blood". Marduk then forms heavens and the earth from her divided body."^{338 339}

While the author agrees that Tiamat plays the part of the Egyptian Nut here, as inherited from the description of the Aten (Chaotic water enclosure or womb), that is about the length and breadth of that. The second paragraph seems to refer to the typical Aphrodite/Vulcan/Ares lover's triangle, which obviously refers to the changing relative proximal positions in the sky (and subsequent charge exchange/arc discharging). However, Venus (the first Aphrodite, before the Moon twin) was never slain, nor was she split. When

³³⁵ It is quite obvious here that the red planet god Ares or Mercury (Tyr and Thor were also often dual role-players of the War-God) was seen to be the arbiter of change, being most proximal. Remember: according to KY glyph analysis, there was a close alignment of Mars and Earth, Moon and later Venus.

³³⁶ Ea being the sky-god, probably Jupiter at this point (Babylonian Enlil, Hebrew Yahweh)

³³⁷ Reference to the Deluge?

³³⁸ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tiamat>

³³⁹ The author does not merely object to this as a matter of objecting to the mainstream, but it appears to gloss over many important details in the summarizing analysis which clearly point to a more nuanced meaning of Tiamat. While Tiamat may be the Babylonian Nut or Ma'at, it is also clearly conceived of as a moving god or body. Not merely a morpheus mass of blue-black sky.

Athena/Inana were not playing the part of Ishtar/Hathor mother-goddess, they were the warrior goddess of dual male/female form (as born out by Loki, also a “mother” of monsters).

This is an example of mainstream cherry-picking from a reading, and selectively promoting only one hypothesis, which may (or in this case) may not really cover all of the facts listed. So this is not only done in the Americas, or Mayanology or Egyptology.... or indeed, at Gobekli Tepe. But it is a problem of logical analysis throughout archeology and astro-archaeology. By making certain assumptions about the past’s possibilities, one limits the narrative.³⁴⁰ This might be done for good or bad intentions, but in either case it is unscientific, for science is a cold, ruthless analysis, and not a matter of hot debate between cliques, nor of heated melodrama, nor even of warm compassion. In applying the scientific method itself to a discovery, not even humanistic justice is important. What one does before and after the process begins should be where this is considered. The bottom line is that the translation simply does not conform to such a droll reading as cited above. It most clearly reflects a drastic change in the solar system, and the behavior of one planetoid in particular in such close proximity as to appear to dominate the sky and all around it with “nets” of influence.³⁴¹

Figure 55 - Zurvan/Anu destroying the Megafauna (Delaware’s Evil Animals)³⁴²

³⁴⁰ An interesting cross-example has been the search for life and exoplanets. By assuming the Earth formation was accretion, and the inner bodies all needed to be rocky, around a main sequence star, and that Earth-like planets were rare, and life rarer still, for decades it was said that we may never find life elsewhere, if it even exists. Now, of course, it is thought that there are 2 trillion galaxies and each of those has perhaps a trillion planets, and the best stars are dwarf stars. Many techniques have been devised for finding exoplanets and Earth-like ones, and many have been found. By changing the assumptions. This is a common problem in astronomy at any rate. Several papers begin with “The Big Bang was an event....” or “Dark Matter exists...” without actual bonafide proof, and proceed from there.

³⁴¹ The author doubts very much these are comet swarms, as at any rate they are not of the same period as the Younger Dryas events. The author favors a clear tidal influence, mostly electrogravitics, but possibly even the weaker Newtonian gravity would suffice as an explanation.

³⁴² <https://www.ancient-origins.net/human-origins-folklore/origins-human-beings-according-ancient-sumerian-texts-0065>

Cross-comparison with North American Mythos

The most obvious supporting tenets from both myths can be summarised in the following list. The basic gist, however, is that, considering this is only **two** of the world's main civilization centers of myth, there is surprising overlay. The Diffusionists may argue that this is a false proof in that there is *some* evidence that Cherokee and Delaware and other Eastern tribes are of Greek, Egyptian, Phoenician, or Hebrew influence, and of course of Welsh (Khumric) and Nordic. However, the author counters that there's nothing in these myths to suggest outright that they are *directly* influenced and did not evolve on the American continent *in situ* from real experience, rather than inheritance from an older Old World civilizing influence. Although tribes mention the whites, and giants, and there are Roman coins, we do not find Roman legends and emperor names on the lips of the Indian tribes. Why? The answer is simple: they had their own myths and stories, and no time or interest to do comparative mythology with the Europeans at length.³⁴³

- ❖ Gods ruled over by a Chief God
- ❖ A great cataclysmic weapon
- ❖ Hurricane or greater fierce winds (indeed: seven types)
- ❖ The Four Winds (and four directions)
- ❖ The Electric Thunderbolt
- ❖ The stamping foot
- ❖ A Giant or Great Man
- ❖ The involvement of the moon in great destruction³⁴⁴

There are other key points, which will be used in support of, but are not found in particular, in the previously cited myths. However, they are almost certainly found in some aboriginal myths through the Americas and the whole world.³⁴⁵

There are also other - many thousands of other - cataclysmic and apocalyptic accounts from around the world. Dozens of them come from the various North American tribes. The ones presented in this paper do not nearly represent an exhaustive list, nor do I expect the mainstream of archaeology (without cultural studies backgrounds) to be familiar **at all** with them, or with enough of them to regard them as not separate cosmogonies but actually cross-cultural testimonial evidence. The plain fact is, that not since the beginning years of archaeo-anthropology (when it was undoubtedly far more racist and therefore ignored), has the testimony of the aborigines truly been considered possibly as a form of truthful (or partly so) anecdote, rather than mere fictional mythology.

³⁴³ Or such conversations are not recorded into any great depth.

³⁴⁴ It's important to note that the moon's tidal forces now are despite being more than 238,000 miles (384,000 km) from the Earth are sufficient to cause the oceans to rise and fall by meters per day. A sudden approach or an even closer approach upon entry, as the author proposes in Part 4, would result in catastrophic swings even using only Newtonian modelling. The energetic-kinetic power, the electromagnetic work done on the system, would be too enormous for human scale to comprehend.

³⁴⁵ One of the most difficult parts of this paper is in pairing **down** the evidence to the essentials, because there is just such a plethora of evidence supporting EPEMC's hypotheses, that it becomes difficult to decide how best to demonstrate the incorrectness of the current mainstream paradigm. For Clovis First, it is simple enough to find skeletons from prior to 12-15 kya. But for the most part, the actual evidence *for* EPEMC is simply overwhelming. It is harder to find a common glyph that is *not supportive* than it is to find one that does.

This too: the sheer number of repetitious glyphs within an area or tribe is telling. Thumbing through the Rock Art of KY book, one thing becomes obvious: there are way too many one-footed turkeys in every part of Kentucky. But unless the natives were reporting the issue on walls for other hunters, the author expresses grave doubts as to the turkey aspect of these recordings!

The author suggest, for example, that the reader should familiarize themselves with the Ojibwe³⁴⁶, Chippewa³⁴⁷ and related Algonquin tribes, of Nanabozho.^{348 349}

Part 3

Earthwork

Figure 56 - Lichtenburg Formation in wood

Figure 57 - in human flesh

Figure 58 - Lightning carved earth, Oklahoma baseball field³⁵⁰

Once you see examples of lightning and arc-discharge machining formations, they are quite easy to spot. Their stratification is vastly different from folding, over/underthrust, and other tectonics. Usually, and almost always, they stand out in stark contrast. Subjectively, the regions where they are, such as Devil's tower, Grand Canyon, certain knobs, mounds, earthworks, etc... all have an odd "energetic" sense to them, that is usually attributed to awe or amazement. But, the author maintains, this is a physiological response to an energy-signature, the presence of previous charge deposit or exchange. As for the geological formations, primarily listed by experts Andy Hall³⁵¹ and geologist Peter "Mungo" Jupp, as well as engineer Wal Thornhill³⁵², they include (but are not limited to):

- ❖ Lichtenburg shapes
- ❖ Lightning rills
- ❖ Scalloping
- ❖ Crater-rim discharges
- ❖ Crater-chains (even which change direction, such as on the moon)
- ❖ Bull's eye (multiple even) cratering irrespective of spherical geometries

³⁴⁶ <http://www.uwosh.edu/coehs/cmaggproject/ethnomath/legend/legend9.htm>

³⁴⁷ <http://www.native-languages.org/chippewa-legends.htm>

³⁴⁸ <http://faculty.marianopolis.edu/c.belanger/quebechistory/encyclopedia/NanabozhoIndianstoryofthecreation.htm>

³⁴⁹ <https://www.ancient-origins.net/myths-legends/native-american-legend-sleeping-giant-and-whiteman-006302>

³⁵⁰ <https://www.ldsfreedomforum.com/viewtopic.php?t=17155&start=30>

³⁵¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fDIRMB3hVQM>

³⁵² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gJdJZm67bWk>

- ❖ Sputtering discharges, such as arches and outcroppings
- ❖ Oddly created “Sinks” (Carolina bays, Big Sink, Eye of the Sahara, etc...)
- ❖ Anode/fulgaritic mounds (such as Half-dome, Ayer’s Rock, Stone Mtn, and Looking-Glass Rock)
- ❖ Mountain geometries, especially those that fold inwards to a center (Wudangshan, Black Hills)
- ❖ Canyons deeper in center with no outlet (Valles Marineris)³⁵³
- ❖ “Shield” Volcanoes which do not have the characteristics of known active volcanoes (Olympus Mons is a prime example)

Figure 59 - Lichtenburg Geo-formations in Knobs Region, Kentucky; credit: Google³⁵⁴

The key to recognizing them is to see them in use. The author recommends the links to the videos provided, to first familiarize oneself with how arc discharge in lab, and current and electric fields in general manifest. It is well known, now, of course, that electric current and field behavior is absolutely vital to understanding physiological processes within the body, DNA, and how animals can do some of the amazing things they do. All of Nature takes advantage of the Force, and so does modern man, having completed transformed his living conditions in the last 200 years.

³⁵³ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tRV1e5_tB6Y

³⁵⁴ The Knobs region are known for being an odd geological formation where the hills all reach a similar height, ~800-900'

Why there is not more robust interest in PEMC, is not understandable except in the context of cultural tunnel vision. For while news is announced of the electromagnetic behaviors of the Great Pyramids³⁵⁵, the mainstream remains completely blind to the discussion when analyzing SGR A*, for example, confusing magnetic Z-pinches with "black holes", etc... Despite the presence of redshift, but not microlensing.³⁵⁶

Figure 60 - Grand Canyon Lichtenburg and Scalloping formations³⁵⁷; credit: T Krag

Therefore, it is lamentable - but understandable - that mainstream archaeology, in its zest to distance itself from catastrophism (because it could fathom no mechanism in the early 1800s, since no one understood electromagnetism at all at the time!³⁵⁸) would miss, almost completely, the simple facts of geological, astro-archaeological, and socio-mythical evidence for electric arc catastrophe formations *and* monumental megalithic and geoglyphic echoes of these events.

It isn't that there are no uniformitarian formations, those are the constant. Just as the low rumbling of tectonics and the mantle gyre remains a constant, or the Cosmic Background Radiation, or the plasma stellar wind remain a constant force. However, these would not *impress* upon the shaman and wise people of ancient cultures. Rather, what is unusual, remarkable, different, and life-altering, (ie catastrophes) are exactly what would impress upon them, and cause them to form: stories, glyphs, art, earthworks, megaliths, etc... in

³⁵⁵ <https://phys.org/news/2018-07-reveals-great-pyramid-giza-focus.html>

³⁵⁶ <http://www.eso.org/public/news/eso1825/>

³⁵⁷ The water of the Colorado river, being clearly insufficient to create such a wide formation, is easily demonstrated to have fallen into this formation after it was created. The strangely attractive power of the Grand Canyon is well known, as although there are many gorges in the world of renowned beauty, and many deeper: there is only *one* Grand Canyon.

³⁵⁸ Discovery of induction: Faraday (1831); Henry (1832); Maxwell's Equations (1861); Uniformitarianism (1785-1833)

memoriam of such events. Recalling Table 1, we are looking to *humanize* and *empathize* with the ancient peoples of the past, in this case mostly American Indians, rather than treat them as somehow unexpectedly different in stimulus-response behavior.

While very little may be happening in our culture, geologically, and we have time to invent fantasies and science-fiction stories, especially those (unironically) associated with End of the World scenarios³⁵⁹, the people of the past were making attempts to record as well as *predict* future outcomes, on the basis of ideas, such as the Mill-wheel, wolf, monsters, giant nets, feet, mountains in the sky, lost floating cities, giant fish, gods and angels, demons and devils, etc... They had too little information, but plenty of firsthand experience. In the absence of facts, they *also* made the oft mistake of theorizing before having facts. But on occasion, some of the cultures (such as Egypt, Iran, and China) could get the situation partially correct, and discover some secrets of electromagnetism. But such advances were few and far between before the Scientific Period.

But why Earthworks and Megalithic architecture?

Throughout all the ages, from the beginning of mythic times (but after bio-consciously modern man's origins ~36,000-40,000 YBP)³⁶⁰, mankind has sought to imitate the power, majesty, and roles of the gods. From dynastic incest to creating swords, chariots, and spears (and making organized war), all of these things have been culturally attributed worldwide to the behaviors of the gods (celestial bodies).

Why would earthworking be any different? In fact, it is more than likely that the sudden appearance of mountains, hills, valleys, and the tilting of bodies of water to "pour them out", and the destruction of cities would be most assuredly inspirations for earthworking and megalithic behavior. Indeed, the megalithic period greatly coincides with the affirmed peak of these events around the Exodus and Martian destructions, 1600 BCE and 670 BCE respectively, but can in many cases be traced back to the Saturnian and Jovian reigns in the Tepe and Archaic Periods.

Conical Mounds and Conical Pyramids

³⁵⁹ [5]

³⁶⁰ All the dates and period speculations are introduced standards in "On the Origins of Religions," by the author, but collected from multiple sources. See [2] for more information.

Figure 61 - Positive Lightning Created Conical Mound in desert; credit: A Hall³⁶¹

Figure 62 - Maars of Pinacate³⁶²; credit: NASA

There are diffusionist hypotheses with excellent evidence for “across the pond” travelers from Celtic isles, Wales, the Roman Empire, and Scandinavia; any of which could have brought mound building to America. However, there is good reason to doubt that they did: the Welsh stories and Roman coins all take place after 200 AD, and the mound building culture began in the Allegewi times; several thousand years earlier. Although it is remotely possible Welsh and Irish peoples, or fleeing early Brits could have brought mound building, it seems rather unlikely. However, there is evidence to show that the entire mound building and pyramid building culture worldwide, was based upon several primary myths, and replications of physical Thunderbolt strike locations. However, differentiating between them, can be difficult, even with Serpent mounds (are these Venus related only, or also references to Lichtenburgs?)

What is certain is little, but that from time to time electrical arc formations would have been seen, found, and replicated by the natives (of any land, but in this case: America). While the author wouldn't say that the Barringer crater discharge, which left an octagonal crater, was the absolute inspiration of the octagonal

³⁶¹ <https://www.thunderbolts.info/wp/2017/12/10/lightning-scarred-earth-part-1/>

³⁶² The locals of Mexico insist that the entire Maars formations were created during the battle of the gods, and the area is extremely scarified and looks as if it was the site of nuclear bomb testing, as does the Middle East where to this day war and difficulty remain despite more flourishing pasts. <https://thedailyplasma.blog/2017/02/20/the-maars-of-pinacate/>

earthwork, he would say that it was related phenomena to plasma-electromagnetic behavior, and possible astronomy related (via Jupiter's pole). The behavior of the Birkeland currents in space will be mimicked on the ground, and will naturally be mimicked in culture:

Figure 63 - Barringer Crater³⁶³; Figure 64 - Newark Earthworks Octagon; credit: Acuah³⁶⁴

Figure 65 - Bagua & Taijitu (China)

Figure 66 - Aegishjalmur (Norse)³⁶⁵

³⁶³ Formed by single arc blast, quickly, and impossibly perpendicularly (for an asteroid)

³⁶⁴ <https://ahcuah.wordpress.com/2011/11/05/fun-with-lidar/>

³⁶⁵ Note the trigram mirroring with the Chinese and Nordic shape: these are 2D representations of the the toroid. The Chinese chose to alternate yin and yang in lines and broken lines, while the Norse alternated the ends and runes.

Figure 67 - Vegvesir (Nordic); note the different plasma formations (including the Menorrah); compare and contrast with Hindu formations in the hands of Shiva (6 arms, and 2 legs); credit: ancientpages.com

So what do these octagons have to do with conical mounds? Again, note the Newark formation joints: each with a conical mound at the octagonal joint. Referring to demonstrable conical formations within the thunderbolt strike at Big Sink the answer is clear: octagonal formations were both visible in the air (perhaps in motion towards Earth?) and left their marks on Earth, and these were also associated with conical formations for lightning or arc discharges.

Figure 68 - Dharmacharya (8 spoked wheel of Dharma) - India

Figure 69 - Enon Mound, OH

From here, worship of the Thunder God (worldwide), and as the Great Man, Creator, Heaven-Man, Celestial Warrior, Giant Man, etc... would be easily explained. There is a large celestial body in the sky. When it is near, lightning is cast upon the earth. Mountains and hills are raised, or valleys cast down³⁶⁶. Therefore: God has been present upon the Earth. This is something worth commemorating, writing books about, and making megalithic architecture (rather than small human sized solar and lunar calendars).

Henges and C-Henges

Henges, by contrast, refer specifically to sites where cylindrical strikes have left an outer rim, with or without a conical center. C-henges refer to such henge sites that happen to have a crater-rim discharge which left an opening that was then interpreted through a variety of means (bridge, umbilical into the womb, turtle neck, etc...). This crater rim discharge will leave an electromagnetic signature.³⁶⁷

Figure 70 - Henges revealed by drought near Stonehenge; credit: NatGeo; Figure 71 - Biggs Site³⁶⁸, KY

³⁶⁶ The apparent vagaries of difference are associated with the different ways that charge moves, and the different of polarity (positive or negative). For more proof, please review the lab work of B Yelverton:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?list=PL_7IM52_IMo05Ogrw9DgQcdoertmqLNOC&v=Dq1ffHg9IZ4

³⁶⁷ At a Heaven & Earth Society event, July 14, 2018, the author measured changing magnetic fields at the east side of the neck of Mt. Horeb mound using a Trifield magnetometer, with spikes upwards of 2.2-5.5 mG (alternating to 0). These tests will be reconducted in a future separate paper which cannot be cited at this time. See Figure 72 for reference

³⁶⁸ A perfect example of an anode discharge formation created via arc uplift.

The formation of the "lip" or "aureol" surrounding the central anode or tufted cone, has to do with attraction towards the electrical field of the arc formation. Naturally, this empty place would be used as a gateway to a sacred enclosure. It would, also, naturally be attributed to the celestial pole star formation in the sky, especially as another body passes in front, leaving a broken ring. These were neither forts nor living spaces. They were, one and all: worship centers and later, calendars.

Figure 72 - Mt. Horeb C-henge, Lexington, KY

The author proposes that these mounds were first formed via actual henges, sometimes multiple strikes in a single location, and then in younger mounds via replication. The older mounds would have been maintained via "public works" initiatives, probably by tribal leaders and wise people, shamans, chiefs, etc... They were most certainly not random (though their locations appear randomized and irrespective of water sources, etc...), and were not an accidental worldwide phase. Nor were they (purely) diffusionist products, but a shared human worldwide cultural collective experience.

Figure 73 - Great Britain has a long history of mound reconstruction, and gardening repurposing; but clearly these match the Scioto and Newark formations, as well as the Amazonian formation.³⁶⁹

³⁶⁹ <http://wyrting.com/EarlyGardens/British/IronAgeBritishGardens.htm>

The Serpent Mounds

One of the biggest secrets of historical archaeology is the existence, and destruction indeed, of not just one "Great Serpent Mound" in North America, but more than 30. In Kentucky alone, two exist in confirmation, and possibly a third: Boyd County, Menifee County, and Lawrence County, respectively. There may be more, weakly defined, or tilled serpents, such as at the Broaddus Site on the Bluegrass Army Depot base, but no revelations have been made public, nor likely even discovered. Figure 74-82 show some of the different types of serpents:

Figure 74 - Spratt Site Forked Serpent and Great Man (Running Man), Frenchburg, KY; credit: AKHA

Figure 75 - Forked Mound at Siskiyou, CA; Figure 76 - Winnebago/Des Plaines River, Chicago, IL³⁷⁰

³⁷⁰ <https://moundbuilder.blogspot.com/p/30-serpent-mounds-in-north-america.html>

Figure 77 - Florida "Egg-swallowing" mound, Lake Okeechobee, FL

Figure 78 - Dual serpent mounds, and creek serpent swallowing "egg"³⁷¹, Pipestone County, MN

Figure 79 - Rice Co, KS

³⁷¹ The horseshoe mounds are, again, clearly not eggs. None of these mounds are about snakes swallowing eggs, which as noted before are not natural to North America but only to tropical regions. Black snakes are not animals worthy of such gigantic earthworks.

FIG. 27. SERPENT EFFIGY IN IOWA. LENGTH, 1004 FEET.

FIG. 28. MOUNDS ARRANGED IN SERPENTINE FORM, NEAR GOTTENBURGH, IOWA. LENGTH, TWO AND A HALF MILES.

Figure 80 - Spiral Tail Serpents, with obvious non-eggs to swallow; Guttenburgh, IA

Figure 81 - Spiral and meandering Serpent, displaying comet motion more exaggerated than the Great Serpent Mound in OH; Warren Co, OH

Figure 82 - Great Serpent Mound, bow shock displayed in front of oval "egg"³⁷²

As has been made excessively clear, none of these serpents have much to do with snakes, but are instead displays of either the great Serpent (called Jörmungandr³⁷³ in Scandinavia and Typhon³⁷⁴ in Greece), or of Venus leaving the Venus-Mars coupling (D Talbot³⁷⁵). Their uses as calendars, especially of the meandering serpents, would reflect the *need* for a calendar following the orbital shifts recorded in the Old World, China, and Mexico, following the end of the last ages, and when the year becomes 365 days long.³⁷⁶

Where the serpent is joined by a conical mound also indicates to us that the serpent is associated with this one electromagnetic power displayed by the gods, in their battles (as recorded in America, India and China), and occasionally to strike the Earth in wrath and fury of battle. Where the "egg" is varied, would indicate

³⁷² In modern times, such changes, or perhaps general ignorance, has made it such that the bow shock and the central mound inside the "egg" (Venus) are constantly left out of the diagrams, and are never discussed or produced at museums.

³⁷³ <https://www.scientiapress.com/serpent-mound>

³⁷⁴ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/J%C3%B6rmungandr>

³⁷⁵ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Typhon>

³⁷⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oophJNIP-fk>

³⁷⁶ "Worlds in Collision," Velikovsky, 1950

either various observational differences, or more likely, worship preferences amongst separate tribes. Because of the destruction of the ancient cultures and historic tribes which most likely kept everything in oral tradition, confirmation of these tails is difficult to obtain.

Pyramids, Step Pyramids, and the Cosmic Mountain

There are various names, worldwide for the Cosmic Mountain/Ship/Hill/Leg/Arms. They have all been worshiped, in various ways. It may be true that even at one time, a plasma stream could have emerged from Earth's upper atmosphere and reached toward the Olympian Summit in the sky, forming a great triangular mountain and a Heaven, and inspiring legends of Asgard, Valhal, Tushita, etc... Table 8 lists the correspondences (selected from the Saturn Myth Table³⁷⁷ aforementioned), to summarize these.

So, what type of architecture would be appropriate to commemorate this? (In the majority of the world, earth-mounds, conical pyramids, even whole mountains, such as at the Bosnian Pyramid of the Sun and at Gunung Padang (those these two are much older and in commemoration of the One God,) Y-dwarf Saturn in the former age of Zep Tepi), would be used. The Olmec, for example used earthen pyramids (as did the later Cahokians). The Chinese used rammed-earth. At Poverty Point, however, and in Mexico, as well as the Indian and Atlantic ocean isles, we see rather a tendency to make Djoser-like "step pyramids". Why?

Figure 83 - Bosnian Pyramid Earthworks with angular correspondences shown; credit: soul-guidance.com³⁷⁸

³⁷⁷ Credit: D Talbott, "The Saturn Myth"

³⁷⁸ <http://www.soul-guidance.com/houseofthesun/bosnianpyramids.htm>

Table 8 - Cosmic Mountain Correspondences Worldwide

	Cosmic Mountain	Paradise-land/Primeval land	Cosmic double-mountain atentit/ateriti	Mooring Post/Palace at pole Menat/Mena-uret	Summit/Zenith	North Pole / Pole axis am aten-f	The Firmament	Heart of Heaven
Egypt	Khut Maa Abtu			Tet Khet	Osirid	Tet Ben	ab Atum	
Mesopotamian	Kur Hursag Mithras			Dimgal Tarkullu	iliatu	Men	sami	
Hebrew	Zion	Tyre, Astarat	Nonnus, Horeb, Ebo, Gerezim	Zaphon Kiun	Olympus	Sagu	Esara	
Greece	Olympus Parnassus				Atlas			
Rome	[Eora]					Mercurius		
China	Kun-lun			Tai-Ki	Ze-wei	Ling-shu Mixcoatl	Tao	
Mayan								
Aztec	Colhuacan							
Hindu	Meru/Sumeru						Central Fire	
Iran/Persian	Taera/Terak/Rasnu		Chandrasichara	Dhruva-lok	Kailash / Agni	Prajapati/Skambha	Samanam Dhama	
Zoroastrian	Hera Berezaiti		Phengari		Mithra	Kevan	Eden	
Arabian/Muslim					Kadac-i-Daitik		AIran-vej	
Norse	[Utko]			Qutb				
Japan	Shumi			Heimdall				
American Indian		Talega						
Altaic, Tatars				Golden Horse Post		"star chief of the skies"		
Laps				Veralden Tshould				
Germanic				Irmingsaul				

Figure 84 - Gunung Padang modeled as it may have appeared in the distant past; credit: PS Purajatnika³⁷⁹

³⁷⁹ <https://grahamhancock.com/gunung-padang-latest-hancock/>

Figure 85 - Poverty Point Illustration, showing the shell formation combined with step/conical pyramid³⁸⁰

Figure 86 - Olmec Earthen Pyramid, 900-400 BCE, La Venta, Mexico

³⁸⁰ Reliably dated 1650-700 BCE, clearly between the Exodus cataclysm and the Martian cataclysm

Figure 87 - Teotihuacan - "Pyramid of the Sun"³⁸¹; credit: LM Man³⁸²

Figure 88 - Great White Pyramid at Xian Province, China³⁸³

There is a change in the plasma shape within laboratory settings and in simulations done by Dr. Peratt that shows the plasmas can undergo various Bennett pinching, which, held perpendicularly, will reveal a zig-zag pattern.

³⁸¹ Or rather, Helios (The Saturn Sun)

³⁸² <http://braungardt.trialectics.com/art/roots-of-religion/attachment/teotihuacan/>

³⁸³ https://rgdn.info/en/piramidy_kitaya_tayna_synov_neba

"Animal" Effigies

Aside from the aforementioned centipedes, serpents, and alligator mound, there remain a number of various worldwide (especially in Peru) "animal" effigies which remain, in fact, merely caricatures of the animal, but are actually plasmaglyph formations. The most famous of these are the "thunderbirds", some monkeys, and even a shark. However, the more curious animal glyphs, worldwide, are by far the therianthrope glyphs. The mixture of human with animal effigy date at least as far back as the European caves and the Gobekli Tepe T-pillars.

Figure 90 - Newspaper Rock, Black Dragon Canyon, UT; credit: climb-utah.com³⁸⁶

As described before, these therianthropes most assuredly were not actual monsters seen in forests, but the same plasmaglyphs seen above, hence their combination with our most common glyphs: feet, circular glyphs, meandering serpent, celtic cross, etc... Indeed, the number of these, in various positions, and orientations, as shown on Newspaper Rock (obviously be a non-Allegewi/Hopewellian tribe), makes a clear example of astronomical observations under clear skies. Some of the glyphs are animals to be sure, such as

³⁸⁴ Note the symmetrically decreasing, somewhat triangular shape. However, the head of the "creature" makes it clear that this is the Comet Venus' plasma tail (which has since been found scientifically).

³⁸⁵ Ibid., P.

³⁸⁶ <http://climb-utah.com/Moab/newspaper.htm>

bison, ram, and deer. But the giants, monsters, etc... are clearly demonstrations of the Great Man glyph in various stages. See figures 50 and 51.

Shell/Solar Ray Mounds

Taking a look at Figure 85, one must ask, "Is this a common glyph morphology?" It is, in fact, common enough, and may be related to either: a) the rising sun or b) the Polar Configuration offset, see Figure 91.

Figure 91 - Scallop motif; credit: D Talbott³⁸⁷

Figure 92 - The Birth Of Venus by Sandro Botticelli - 1485-86³⁸⁸

Figure 93 - Mother Goddess on half-shell³⁸⁹ ; Figure 94 - Aphrodite³⁹⁰

³⁸⁷ Note the foreground of the left is Mars, and the background is Venus, discharging towards Saturn.

³⁸⁸ <http://www.crystalinks.com/venus.html>

³⁸⁹ Ibid.

³⁹⁰ <https://www.pinterest.com/mimischole/aphrodite-and-the-shell/?lp=true>

Figures 95-99 - Aboriginal Dreamtime Rock Art; credit: Pinterest³⁹¹

The question is, which is correct, for we find in Kentucky and throughout the world the simultaneous placement of these “rising sun” and “shell” glyph morphologies in conjunction with the other mentioned glyphs. This is remarkable because the variation in flora and fauna, as well as phenomena on a human-scale are far too varied for this to represent some kind of accident. It is either the result of diffusionism, or more likely, the astronomical observations. In this case, both Greek and Aboriginal tradition make it clear that the Shell formation reflects the Venus-comet tradition (Exodus Cataclysm), ~1600 BCE, which accurately reflects the dating of Poverty Point. Moreover, the earthwork shape at Poverty Point reflects, perfectly, the head-dress

³⁹¹ <https://www.pinterest.com/>

forms, with the same eerie "owl eyes" of the Aborigines which is also found in KY rock art, and in the Nazca geoglyphs/earthworks.

Figures 100-103 - Aboriginal Dream-time cont'd; Credit: Pinterest

Figures 104-108 - Comparative Shell-headaddress glyphs worldwide; Credit: Pinterest

There can be little doubt that these shapes are related. They can be found in Rongo-Rongo, or in Hawaii, or the Haida, or the Irish. Both the alternative/diffusionists³⁹² and mainstream have thus far (prior to Peratt/Schoch) failed, utterly, in their explanations. The reader, having arrived thus far will recognize these failings immediately upon seeing them.

³⁹² <https://peopleofonefire.com/mesoamerican-glyphs-continued-to-evolve-after-arriving-in-dixie.html>

Figure 109 - Track Rock Gap Boulder 6, GA (Cherokee); credit: People of One Fire (Diffusionist)³⁹³

Figure 110 - Track Rock Gap Boulder 4 and Forsyth glyphs, GA; credit: People of One Fire³⁹⁴

It is up to the Plasma-electromagnetic Cosmologist and Comparative mythologist to work together with archaeologists and anthropologists to shed light on the actual meanings, and to compile a database which can be analyzed, angle by angle, based upon orientation, to discern the entire pattern of movement, and the shape, as well as remove the layers of specific cultural interpretation or oral tradition and bring it back to the original scientific observation it started as.

³⁹³ <https://peopleofonefire.com/the-track-rock-petroglyphs-i-have-a-confession.html> surely these are pure guesses

³⁹⁴ Recognizing Scandinavian glyph morphology is good. Not recognizing it goes further than that, however, leads to guessing and short-sighted hypotheses. Note the unexplained "6 toed glyph", almost certainly attributed amongst alternative amateurs to 'giants'.

Regarding the shell glyphs representing the sunrise, there is some merit and the hypothesis cannot be disproved, only discounted or made unreasonably far-fetched. Aside from the fact that sunrises do not appear to our eyes in this way, only in art and fairy tales (such as Homer's works: the fingertips of rose, etc...) it is just simply not so. There are far too many examples of glyphs which make the bridge between the awen symbol and the "sunrise" or shell glyph. Look at Figure 111, just right of center. This is much closer to the formation in figures 104-107, than it is to a semicircular "sunrise" depiction.

Figure 111 - Spaas Creek (Skidmore) Rockshelter, Red River Gorge, KY; credit: Tim & Georgie Keith³⁹⁵

Please note as well that the aboriginal Dreamtime glyphs display also the vaunted "net" used in Babylonian myth to describe the capture of planets. Perhaps the origin of man's knowledge of the net, of ley lines or energy grids (dragon lines in China), etc... is all related to this one shape. This is a subject for another paper.

In the final part, some of the most difficult to believe legends of the Sioux will be evaluated and compared with other native legends. Furthermore, actual theoretical calculations of thunderbolts will be provided both using classical Maxwellian electromagnetics with basic variables (assuming close passage of the moon or other similarly sized celestial sphere), as well as basic high energy plasma calculations. Finally a discussion of the little understood science of step potential will be discussed, with the goal in creating a general radius for a single thunderbolt. Bear in mind that for the thunderbolt to kill an animal it would need to have at least two feet upon the ground or near enough to arc, or there could have been a powerful shockwave blast, or even a destructive Huracan (heavenly wind) which accompanied the celestial body's near passage. But animals which survived in caves, and trees would have been quite safe, so long as they were neither game nor had difficulty breeding and re-stocking their populations (such as bison).

³⁹⁵ <http://www.kywilderness.com/forum/index.php?topic=7574.msg50863;topicseen#new>

Part 4

Proposed alternate theories of death, extinction, and war/competition.

Throughout this article, the author has maintained that thunderbolts were the main operative vector of megafauna extinction and the curtailing of civilization in the northern hemisphere. However, technically speaking it was a combination of cold, food loss due to fallout/winter, herbivore decline, and war that followed these hard times which compounded the bad situation. It was a time of limitation and fear. Certainly many species may have gone extinct very quickly, due to Step Potential quickly wiping out their herds (such as Mammoths and Mastodons). But many more had their populations so reduced that hunting or lack of breeding and food options did what the cold and rising waters could not. Remember: the Younger Dryas facts are not under question. Only the mechanisms. The author has disproven the comet or comet/swarm as the primary vector via actual vector analysis and erosion evidence. But, *how* the electrical events distributed and continued to propagate terror and destruction is not at all clear. . The only thing known is that there were massive water level changes, probably mega tsunamis and land mass eliminations³⁹⁶, and that the moon has a very uncertain, wobbly path to this day. How close it could have gotten, and would have “swung” back and forth in a teeter-totter fashion is not known. Especially if electrokinetics is in play at $> 10^{14-15}$ V, which as the author will show is almost certainly true.³⁹⁷ Bearing all of this in mind, the author proceeds aggressively forward.

Designing an electrical model

One should not suppose that the author recklessly considers this aspect of the science. Firstly, there is nothing done like this so far, in the literature. Given the author's lack of access to advanced plasma computer modeling software, the author must rely on equations from classical EM theory and high energy plasma physics. The author spoke with several experts in the plasma physics fields and labs, in order to develop an understanding of which direction to go. In particular, special thanks to Michael Clarage, Dr. Joseph Dwyer³⁹⁸ for his tips to Dr. Martin Uman's works³⁹⁹ (see Appendix C), and most of all to Dr. Donald Gurnett for his modeling suggestion breakthrough must be lodged by the author in recognition of the genius and the work of others.

Secondly, the reader must know that Part 4 is entirely speculative. There is no in situ measurement possible for this scale of destruction, and it may be that laboratory lightning and even cloud based lightning pales utterly in comparison to the scale we are speaking of, due to considerations of the inverse square law, and the sheer volume of electricity under consideration. According to one source cited below, the sun (a Main Sequence star⁴⁰⁰) produces a solar wind with “hot grains” (charged particles⁴⁰¹) with particulate charges levels of ~4-5V each⁴⁰². Does one count these in series, parallel, or rather aggregate them and use a flux calculation to figure the average (if indeed there is an average) electrical current of the sun?

³⁹⁶ [5]

³⁹⁷ The Biefeld-Brown effect has been demonstrated on small scales, but is unknown at higher scales outside of military experiments. It may be capable of causing massive orbital changes (though angular momentum would remain the same) if an when a celestial body passes close enough for the inverse square law to quite effectively square the attraction of two bodies, resulting in a cascade of shifting forces.

³⁹⁸ “The Physics of Lightning,” Dwyer & Uman, Physics Reports 534 (2014) 147-241

³⁹⁹ Especially “The Art and Science of Lightning Protection,” Uman, 2008

⁴⁰⁰ Which must certainly be different **completely** in voltage characteristics from a brown, red, or y-dwarf star.

⁴⁰¹ A discussion of the misnomers in theoretical astrophysics is to be found in the author's paper, “Magnetic Universe Theory” [6]

⁴⁰² And is not related to either rotation or gyrating magnetic fields (“dynamos” - see laste note)

<https://arxiv.org/pdf/1808.03389.pdf>

The following table will illustrate the number of assumptions which *must* be made because nothing else can be done - to the author's knowledge - to mitigate this.

Table 9 - Unavoidable Assumptions in Vajra Calculations

Constant moon and lo size	Constant EMF properties and physical laws	Similarity of Current Solar wind with Saturnian and Jovian winds
Constant Earth - no EGE ⁴⁰³	Linearized Lightning models ⁴⁰⁴	Even crystal lattice and charge distribution in Earth's soils ⁴⁰⁵
Earth = ground (0 V)	Single Phase power (no 3-phase or 6-phase ⁴⁰⁶)	Constant permeability of free space ⁴⁰⁷
Atmosphere negligibility for classical interpretations ⁴⁰⁸	Single Body interaction (moon)	Equivalence of negative and positive stepped bolts ⁴⁰⁹
Equivalent destructive power for origin & destinations	Single impedance values	Non-surge or pump behavior ⁴¹⁰
Single strike (no repeat strokes)	Ignore wet-dry soil/air conditions	Straight or curvi-linear arc paths
Glow arc mode for classical model	Dark mode until ionospheric cascade for Birkeland model	Ignore neutron sequestration ⁴¹¹ and general radiation effects
Jupiter-Earth position offset ⁴¹²	Assumed ranges of power scales ⁴¹³	Constant Gravity - that is, negligible, non-relativistic

Given the very fact that the author does not know for sure the moon is the celestial body in question, but only has a preponderance of evidence⁴¹⁴, it must be said that all of these calculations may be completely in vain

⁴⁰³ Although we have plenty of evidence for the Expanding-Growing-Earth, the current Earth size will be assumed.

⁴⁰⁴ As opposed to parabolic growth or hyperbolic limitations/asymptotes.

⁴⁰⁵ Obviously limestone and granite and sandstone, etc... will not distribute charge evenly. Some will saturate faster, and some will feed the charge into the HEME (Hollow-Electromagnetic-Earth) more quickly, preventing widespread Step Potential.

⁴⁰⁶ Saturn's hexagonal pole may be therefore discounted, and Jupiter's octagonal pole, in favor of counter-rotating cylinders.

⁴⁰⁷ We must, especially for the classical model, assume an empty vacuum. Obviously this is not correct at all, given the known Magnetohydrodynamic measurements from the MMR mission. So, in reality, the same positions and all other things the same, some vajra would be heightened and some would be buffered.

⁴⁰⁸ Examples of the changes in lightning potential based on atmospheric elevation can be found here: <http://bit.ly/2CrDgFA>

⁴⁰⁹ Positive strokes, on Earth, can be 3x as powerful as negative strokes, but only occur 1/10 of the time, as per Uman

⁴¹⁰ Pumping is similar to repeat strokes, but in this case a magnitude or several higher in charge syphoning.

⁴¹¹ Artifacts (OOPArts) and certain archaeological sites have been found with impossibly low carbon-14 values. Given the Structured Atom hypothesis (see [6]), in arc modes, it is possible that the electrons in the "neutron" (positron-electron duo) will have been sequestered, reducing the C14 values.

⁴¹² Jupiter has 2×10^4 the size and power of the magnetosphere to the Earth, but receives only 4% the solar wind strength. Therefore, considering the assumptions in the next note, the relative position of these bodies will be offset/equivocated.

⁴¹³ Using [6]. Table 7, some rough assumptions for order of magnitude will be set. For example AGN's operate at 10^{14-15} A, so it will not be possible to have anywhere near this current. Rather, since Earth and Jupiter operate in the 350-600 kA range, a 10^5 A range will be assumed. In this case an average between the two.

⁴¹⁴ Moon myths (Part 1, 2), Lunar motion, "tidal lock", arc-discharged surface, "smoking gun effect" (closest and most visible suspect), and size of moon (and its differences and similarities to the Earth.)

For example, what if it was another body⁴¹⁵, several bodies over eons⁴¹⁶, and what of the different sizes in strike sites⁴¹⁷? What if the bolts are all electric-comet bodies that explode in airbursts⁴¹⁸? Then this becomes more of an electro-dynamics meets thermodynamics type of problem, and then it's all moot. One may even counter that lightning is simply too random, but the author maintains that the strikes would have occurred in waves of close pass-bys. The evidence of electro-tidal lock remaining even after a close passage can be found on Mars, where (for example) whenever the two planets are in closest proximity Mars will have a worldwide sandstorm⁴¹⁹.

Using Classical Maxwellian Electromagnetism

The classical electromagnetic model is *not* accurate. But, it has the benefit of being simple, and of providing a rough estimate of the kind of power levels we are suspecting in terms of voltage and total joules provided. The goal is ascertaining if it is a feasible method for melting ice sheets and providing charge to saturate the land. The answer, ultimately is yes, but it is rather hard to believe the amounts. Why? Because the distance and the permeability of free space is so difficult to overcome. Still, the exercise is useful to demonstrate one clear point: Vajra are not terrestrial lightning. They are, in fact, extraterrestrial and of a wholly different caliber of power. They are the kind that is involved in nuclear fusion on the surface of the sun, synthesizing elements as they are expelled from the liquid metallic hydrogen lattice and sent careening through the solar current.

People are afraid of lightning, but more or less, with all of our lightning protection and various shieldings such as metal cars, houses, trains, planes, etc... we have stopped realizing how potent it is. Moreover, people are shocked to learn that you don't have to be struck by lightning to be hurt or die. There are numerous reports of stunned witnesses and journalists, recording the effects of Step Potential. Some of these have already been cited above. However, seeing may be more important than reading, so the author wishes to offer this video for the reader: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MNJRPOlitifi> There are other videos which also establish the danger of Step Potential/Voltage. That was a distant and relatively benign strike, as compared to the bolt that carved the Oklahoma ball field in the figure 58. But still it was very potent. So now imagine the power of something that is very wide, and also stacked with energy, sometimes in concentric circles!

For these calculations, there are a few more assumptions that must be made.

- > Breakdown voltage of free space = 20 MV m⁻¹
- > $\epsilon_0 = 8.854187817 \dots \times 10^{-12} \text{ F} \cdot \text{m}^{-1}$ (the capability of the vacuum to permit electric field lines.)⁴²⁰
- > $C \sim 159 \mu\text{F}^{421}$ based on a distance from Earth to the Moon⁴²² and $A = 1000 \text{ m}^2$ (104' x 104')
- > $\epsilon = 1.31 \text{ C/V m}^{-1}$ based on same assumptions
- > Plate capacitance, given small area (very small compared to some strike sites found)
- > $E = VQ = V \cdot \frac{VA\epsilon}{s}$, where s is in meters and E is in Coulomb-volts (joules).
- > 1 lightning bolt $\sim 5\text{Gj}$ of energy⁴²³

⁴¹⁵ Mercury, Mars, Venus, or Triton

⁴¹⁶ Saturn, Jupiter, Mars, Uranus, etc...

⁴¹⁷ Compare, for example the Eye of Sahara with Barringer with Devil's Tower or Ayer's Rock, with the Grand Canyon with the Knobs Lichtenburg, with Big Sink with Mt. Horeb or Biggs Site. These are all of different charge directions and scales.

⁴¹⁸ See 1491 comet over Melbourne, which split into two pieces, one creating a 240' tsunami, and the other airbursting, Tunguska style, and flash petrifying trees on the beach, according to geologist Peter Mupp

<http://www.ancientdestructions.com/videos/mega-tsunami-melbourne/>

⁴¹⁹ <https://www.jpl.nasa.gov/news/news.php?feature=7164>

⁴²⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Vacuum_permittivity

⁴²¹ <https://electronics.stackexchange.com/questions/111582/capacitance-between-earth-and-moon>

⁴²² @ $\sim 384,400,000 \text{ m}$; https://www.ajdesigner.com/phpcapacitor/parallel_plate_capacitor_equation_e.php#ajscroll

⁴²³ <http://www.physics.org/facts/toast-power.asp>

➤ $E_k = 3 \times 10^6 \text{ V m}^{-1} \times n_{\text{air}}$ (breakdown voltage in the air)⁴²⁴

We are going to perform the calculations at ¼, ⅓, and ½ the distance as well and compare them in Table 10.

Table 10 - Vajra Calculations using Coulomb's Law & Capacitance⁴²⁵

	Full distance	½ distance	⅓ distance	¼ distance
d (m)	3.84E+08	1.92E+08	1.28E+08	9.61E+07
C (F)	3.40E-06	1.70E-06	1.13E-06	8.51E-07
e (F/m)	1.31E+00	3.27E-01	1.45E-01	8.18E-02
V = 20MV/m*d	7.69E+15	3.84E+15	2.56E+15	1.92E+15
E (j)	2.01E+26	2.51E+25	7.42E+24	3.14E+24
E (kC)	4.80E+22	6.00E+21	1.77E+21	7.51E+20
Lightning Bolts	4.02E+16	5.02E+15	1.48E+15	6.29E+14
# Vajra to boil Antarctica ⁴²⁶	1.33E+05	1.66E+04	4.90E+03	2.08E+03
Adjusting down (10 ³)	2.01E+23	2.51E+22	7.42E+21	3.14E+21
E (kC)	4.80E+19	6.00E+18	1.77E+18	7.51E+17
Lightning Bolts	4.02E+13	5.02E+12	1.48E+12	6.29E+11
# Vajra to boil Antarctica	1.33E+02	1.66E+01	4.90E+00	2.08E+00

Bear in mind these are using a supremely high breakdown voltage of 20 MV/m, which may be higher, or lower, under certain unknown conditions. Assuming the fact of current movement through space already established by NASA/JPL/ESA, it can be assumed that there are, in fact, arc conditions which would substantially lower the values by 10³ which in the equation becomes a change of 6 sigfigs, or a million X factor. However, we cannot know this breakdown voltage at this time as in-situ measurements during an arc even have not happened. Perhaps a well-placed probe onto Ceres or Io would enable this. Considering the probe would carry Earth's charge with it, this might be unlikely. And would a probe survive the arc measurement? The author does not know.

Prior to the adjust down of 10³ j, some of the numbers do seem ridiculous. All of the numbers at full distance are ridiculous, but we also know that for at least the last several thousand years, mankind has been safe from the moon at the current average distance. So the real issue is the strikes that allegedly came at shorter distances. See figure 113 for author's proposed 2-dimensional idea of distance variation. Such behaviors can somewhat be simulated using Universal Sandbox² which provides only gravitational effects⁴²⁷, and so would not be affected in simulation by the Biefeld-Brown effect (electrokinetics)⁴²⁸.

⁴²⁴ Uman, Ibid. pp. 160

⁴²⁵ <http://bit.ly/2Qd9ffy> for Spreadsheet

⁴²⁶ 1 kC raises 1kg of water from ice to a boil; Antarctica has avg mass of ice of 3.62x10¹⁷ kg

<https://www.wired.com/2016/10/lets-put-water-back-top-antarctica/>

⁴²⁷ <http://universesandbox.com/faq/>

⁴²⁸ All the voltages in the table are of the order of 10¹⁵ V so e can rest assured that orbital variation was possible, of course this would alter the moon's rotational and orbital velocities. It might also change the Earth's somewhat.

Looking at these, however, it's clear that within the $\frac{1}{4}$, $\frac{1}{3}$, and with adjust down, $\frac{1}{2}$ distance, the event could provide the energy required to effectively melt down ice sheets, in a hurry. If those bolts were supplied in bursts, with only the occasionally "long" (minutes) burst such as has been seen at the Grand Canyon or Ayer's Rock, then easily one could supply the type of energy necessary to melt ice within a short period which no comet can provide.⁴²⁹

Figure 112 - Power Scales Based on Table 10; author

⁴²⁹ A comet impact would create a hole which water would rush back into and then re-freeze; 2) the comet is supposed to have occurred at the front of the YDE, so how can it also melt ice at the end? If at the end, then what was the mechanism for the YDE in the first place, when Atlantis is said to have sank? The story of alternative scientists and researchers has not been clear about this point, so focused on proving *any impact* they have been.

#Vajra to boil Antarctic ice sheet (Classical model)

Figure 113 - Vajra to boil Antarctica; author

Note that the upper limits tell is how unreasonable it is to think it could happen at current distances, unless some other body were to first super charge the Moon to the voltages in table 10, which is hardly likely.

Figure 114 - Author's idea of Earth-Moon Intercept Path (2D)⁴³⁰

After the adjust down, what really strikes the fancy is just how potent such a large potential would be, such that the energy supply (again in a single stroke) would require only 2-16 thunderbolts (vajra) to boil an ice sheet. If this seems impossible, remember reader that the EMF is far more powerful than gravity. A discussion of just how much more powerful is found in the author's paper, "Magnetic Universe Theory." Suffice it to say it is about 10^{39} x as powerful in terms of Newtons.

Bear in mind the author does not subscribe to this table above as the patent facts about the power levels. It is: non-relativistic, non QEM, non MHD, non-Birkelandian and relies on the inverse square law. But, the

⁴³⁰ A 3 dimensional discussion of the proposed swath of destruction is contained in another paper, see [5]

author must hasten to point out that BC's rely upon the root of the radius, that is, $r^{1/2}$. Also the arrangement of the particles can hardly be described in BC's as being "Charge separated," they are in fact structured in cylinders.

Still, it is a sobering reality to finally have a vector that is both powerful enough to end an ice age in steps, and selective enough to kill populations **without exterminating the planet and human race**. Furthermore, it is supported by testimonial myth, and physical evidence from spherules caused by extraterrestrial nuclear level power, as well as the numerous people living in cities, dolmens, and caves worldwide.

The author wishes to convey one more idea before closing this section. The author fully expects the arcs to be **more powerful** than calculated, not less (in both articles). Here is a list of reasons why:

- Multiple strokes
- Initial blasts and return blasts
- Electric field effects, electrogravity or otherwise
- The post-current outgas explosion from superheating⁴³¹
- The Travelling Wave-tube⁴³² amplification effect⁴³³
- The formation of a type of electrical "Bridge" that keeps the current flowing, such as the Black Hills/Devil's Tower proximity (cathode and anode)
- Stored (unreleased energy), occasionally bursting through.

Figure 115 - TWT Helix Amplifier; credit: Wikipedia

Birkeland Currents, in brief

A greater amount of information about BC's than can be provided here are contained in the author's paper, "Magnetic Universe Theory," which cites the work of Gabuzda and D Scott, already cited above. Suffice it to say, they are formed of helical counter-rotating cylinders, which behave like coaxial cables or TWTs. They are not as straight as a coax, nor are they as random as a lightning arc. It's important to know that arc behavior changes under vacuum and the jiggety-jagged behavior of lightning goes away, forming curvi-linear arcs whether in dark, glow, arc, or high energy modes. See Jason Gable's video above, or the work of D Yelverton, again on YouTube.

On higher scales, the SAFIRE Project has been working to establish a "star in a jar," which is in glow and high energy mode. In their first startup, a single few seconds arc vaporized a stainless steel bolt. Later, a few seconds of too long of probing with a tungsten langmuir probe resulted in a loss of \$20,000. Such are the temps and powers of these arcs. However, the big difference is all of these are single phase arcing, and not true BC's. On occasion Gable creates demonstrably small BC's, and this results in not only soil excavation but superheating and the aforementioned outgas explosions (even in vacuum). The exact mechanism is not established.

⁴³¹ <https://youtu.be/Gv9u9T9HNKl> ; credit: J Gable

⁴³² Rotating magnetic flux ropes guiding an E field in the core will amplify it
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Traveling-wave_tube

⁴³³ Can boost small signals by multiple times over

Pictured in figure 116 is the Peratt visualization of the ionospheric cascading BC thunderbolt. Meanwhile in figure 117 is shown the postulated path and measured via satellite Io-Jupiter connection. Modeling of this connection remains an active topic in solar system astrophysics⁴³⁴.

Figure 116 - Birkeland Current Simulations; credit: A Peratt

Figure 117 - Io-Jupiter simulated connection credit: K Lang⁴³⁵

It's important to remember, if the reader has trouble understanding how these are connected to our narrative, that Io is the *most volcanically active* body in the solar system (followed by Venus). The plumes of Io have been well documented to exhibit electrical characteristics, rather than tectonic volcanism as we have here on Earth as a result of the HEGEME. So, roughly speaking, we should expect that Earth has periods of increased volcanism, including recently in the cataclysmic past. That is precisely what we find, as well. Juxtaposed to ice ages, increased volcanic activity that has begun to drop off since the times leading up to

⁴³⁴ <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.1029/2008GL033656>

⁴³⁵ https://ase.tufts.edu/cosmos/view_picture.asp?id=1174

Pompeii. The author also cautions that because of the HEGEME, actually cosmic rays from nova, pulsars, etc... may be also implicated in sudden earthquake and tectonic volcanism. These events probably are much different than the type of volcanism seen in the moon, Mars', and Venus' recent past, and in Io's current phase.

There is one other process that needs to be understood about BC's and that is Marklund Convection: the process whereby twisting, spiraling, knotting, and eventual Z-pinching forms stars (which become nothing more than stellar z-pinches of extremely high activity of transformation and electrical propagation.)

Figure 118 - Marklund Convection; credit: i-sis.org⁴³⁷

You see, while the main thought among most physicists and astronomers is that electricity in space would need some kind of voltage pressure to generate it, that isn't how plasma cosmology sees the situation at all. Rather, it sees space as filled with charges of various sources, re-arranging all the time. In order to reduce the "cost" of transfer, and in order to obey the properties of electromagnetism, the plasma self-organizes into structured filaments, creating voided spaces of different charges and shunting electrons and other particles, such as denuded nuclei into clusters⁴³⁶. Once this process gets going, the laws of EMF cause a feedback mechanism which leads to a twisting, rotating, and collapsing Z-pinch, known as Marklund Convection. This enables a re-amplification (for a time) of the electrical signal, while leading to nuclear and chemical processes that formulate the galactic stellar wind, seeding the Universe with these redistributed charges and heavier elements. Over time, these systems will break down as the energy transfers to another region. The black space performs the role of absorbing IR-IMF (heat), and the elements there will store this energy for the redistribution, and the process starts all over again.

Modeling Thunderbolts using Io-Jupiter

There is some evidence, though not enough, that shows that the Io-Jupiter relationship⁴³⁸ may be even more pertinent to our discussion than previously thought⁴³⁹. One of the mysteries of lightning physics is how the cascade of ionospheric sprites gets started. Naturally, space-meteorologists have turned to the "classic" Io-Jupiter connection/circuit (IJC)⁴⁴⁰ for evidence and inspiration⁴⁴¹. The simple fact is that the Earth, and all the planets with large magnetospheres⁴⁴² have proven electrical circuit connections with the sun⁴⁴³, and so very

⁴³⁶ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-018-21128-z>

⁴³⁷ http://www.i-sis.org.uk/Continuous_Creation_from_Electric_Plasma.php

⁴³⁸ 1979, <http://science.sciencemag.org/content/204/4396/991>

⁴³⁹ <http://www.secondsun.net/articles/lightning.htm>

⁴⁴⁰ 400 kV, 10⁶ A <https://arxiv.org/ftp/astro-ph/papers/0209/0209070.pdf>

⁴⁴¹ Enter the work of Dr. Alfvén, Dr. Gurnett and magnetohydrodynamics

⁴⁴² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aFy9smhjDEQ>

⁴⁴³ <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1029/JA080i034p04719>

likely are in parallel with each other⁴⁴⁴ (so forming series relationships with their satellites). Of course for these objects, it may cause their own internal generators to be either altered or even inhibited, if the surrounding plasma sheath down-regulates their magnetospheres⁴⁴⁵. Unfortunately, also, for the MHD model, it does not have the electrical currents of the BC's built in, and this leads to the false belief that the charge is producing via rotating magnetic "dynamo" (a misnomer), and this has also turned out to be not true about the stellar wind⁴⁴⁶. Side note: the interactions of these circuits are implicated in the formation of water, which is pertinent for Saturn's history with the Earth⁴⁴⁷.

Turning to the work of Dr. Gurnett⁴⁴⁸, we can find a ready-usable model for this connection.

"The second example is associated with Jupiter's moon Io. In the process of studying radio emissions from Jupiter, Bigg (1964) discovered that Io played a dominant role in controlling radio emissions from Jupiter in the frequency range from about 10 to 40 MHz. To explain the origin of these Io-controlled radio emissions, Goldreich and Lynden-Bell (1969) proposed that Io is a conductor, and that the electromotive force induced by Io's motion through the co-rotating plasma of Jupiter's magnetosphere excites transverse Alfvén waves propagating northward and southward from the moon... Because of the finite propagation velocity, the Alfvén wave pattern is swept backward relative to the incident plasma flow, forming a v-shaped standing wave similar to the bow wave of a ship. The electrical currents associated with these Alfvén waves create two quasi-field-aligned current loops, one in each hemisphere, that link Io to the upper atmosphere of Jupiter. The electrons that carry these currents are believed to be responsible for generating the radio emissions. Magnetic field measurements by the Voyager 1 spacecraft during a close flyby of Io have since confirmed the existence of these Alfvén waves (Ness et al., 1979)." [emphasis added]

It can therefore be safely estimated that the electrical BC connection from the Earth to the Moon will be determined by evaluating the Van Allen Belt radiation properties, and the magnetospheric properties of the Earth. Bear in mind the current SSC is different, electrically, than in the past for the Earth. The proposed time for this Earth-moon interaction⁴⁴⁹ would have been during the Saturnian Age, possibly the Jovian age (if Zeus was king for such a length of time, although anthropological record shows the transition of worship towards Ba'al/Mithra/Enlil was in the Sumerian times⁴⁵⁰). The properties are identified as follows:

- ❖ 1-100 MV (avg 50MV, but rarely over 200 kV with moon at current distance)
- ❖ 0.1-100 MeV (avg 50 MeV)⁴⁵¹
- ❖ 475 kA in steady state (up to 650 kA⁴⁵²)

⁴⁴⁴ <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1029/2008JA013968>

⁴⁴⁵ <https://cmns.umd.edu/news-events/features/4147>

⁴⁴⁶ http://hubblesite.org/news_release/news/2018-25

⁴⁴⁷ <https://www.nasa.gov/feature/jpl/water-is-destroyed-then-reborn-in-ultrahot-jupiters>

⁴⁴⁸ "Introduction to Plasma Physics, 2nd Edition," D Gurnett, 2017, pp. 214-218

⁴⁴⁹ It is also entirely possible that this interaction was primarily tidal-mechanical, and the source of the moon's (Janus) arc discharge face and polarity was from a past relationship elsewhere. Clearly the Sumerians felt the way the same side always faces Earth was a menacing threat imposed by Marduk (Jupiter, usually). Perhaps all the bolts came from other interactions, such as with an early Mercury, which was Jupiter's messenger for a time. The emergence of Tyr/Heimdall as a god and then the diminution of his myth might bespeak of this.

⁴⁵⁰ The sudden rise of Sumer, and the mythic traditions of a Pangu/Zeus/Horus character bringing mankind out of the soil (farming), suggests that prior to this the Saturnian orbit had become either unstable, or harried by space-debris from previous interactions. However, it must be remembered that the Sumerian myth (Enuma Elish) states that it was Marduk who installed the moon as a Watcher over the Earth, and killed Kingu and cracked Tiamat (Earth) in two (split lands). Therefore the introduction of the moon may not have been during the Younger Dryas at all, in which case the origin of the cataclysm may shift to another body.

⁴⁵¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Van_Allen_radiation_belt

⁴⁵² Current measurements of Saturn, which has been down-regulated (as per Thornhill-Juergens) by the stellar wind starving the y-dwarf of its protective sheath, is still at 174 kA, as per D Scott, Ibid, pp 10 ; the author expects this may have been 1 order of magnitude stronger in the recent past. The changing color of the Saturnian pole suggests the starvation is

- ❖ Increase to 5-500 MA in arc mode⁴⁵³
- ❖ 10-40 MHz Alfvén waves
- ❖ North American topsoil impedance (midwest and Canada): 100 MΩ⁴⁵⁴
- ❖ Stony soils (such as forests and mountains), up to 30 GΩ

Since $V=IR$, we can establish therefore a relatively reliable calculations. First we can calculate the breakdown impedance that will be *inside* the BC/flux tube. Then, by providing the resistances of the soils, we can establish the types of voltage and power (in kW) that will be supplied to the soil.

Table 11 - Vajra Calculations using MHD and Satellite data

	Minimum	Maximum	Avg	Limited
V	1.00E+06	1.00E+08	5.00E+07	2.00E+05
I	2.50E+05	5.00E+08	5.00E+06	6.50E+05
R (space)	4.00E+00	2.00E-01	1.00E+01	3.08E-01
R (soil)	3.00E+07	3.00E+10	1.00E+08	1.00E+08
V (discharge)	7.50E+12	1.50E+19	5.00E+14	6.50E+13
P (V*I)/1000=kW	1.88E+15	7.50E+24	2.50E+18	4.23E+16

Comparing Table 10 and 11, we see that the voltages hover from 10^{-3} to 10^4 higher in Table 11. The avg expected voltage to soil is 10^{-1} than table 10. So the delivery power is *expected* to be about an order of magnitude smaller than in table 10, not 10^{-3} . Nevertheless, within reasonability, we are arriving at the “understanding” of what we are dealing with. That is to say from 1.88 exa-watts to 7.5 yotta-watts, with an expected avg of 2.5 zetta-watts, and a assumed limitation of 42.3 exa-watts.

The average lightning stroke, as per Dwyer & Uman, lasts about 20-30 microseconds. We are assuming here that the Vajras are behaving similarly, although we have previously stated they won't, and certain sites demonstrate reliable geophysical evidence of prolonged return strokes and charge pumping (to saturation). However, to establish conservative boundaries (because the upper end cannot be known), we will use the 30 microsecond value to calculate, again, the joules and kC:

Table 12 - Energy values at the upper and lower limits

	Minimum	Maximum	Avg	Limited
joules in $.3*10^{-6}$ s	5.63E+11	2.25E+21	7.50E+14	1.27E+13
E (kC)	1.34E+08	5.38E+17	1.79E+11	3.03E+09
Lightning Bolts	1.13E+02	4.50E+11	1.50E+05	2.54E+03
Upper Boundary (j)	5.63E+15	2.25E+25	7.50E+18	1.27E+17
Lower Boundary (j)	5.63E+08	2.25E+18	7.50E+11	1.27E+10
Avg Limit (j)	5.63E+10	2.25E+20	7.50E+13	1.27E+12

continuing unabated and Saturn is, electrically, dying as a planetoid/moon producing body (topping out at over 100 children!)

⁴⁵³ In lightning, step leaders are 100-300 A while strokes are 10-300 kA, a potential 1000x (10^3) increase

⁴⁵⁴ <http://www.ee.co.za/article/principles-testing-methods-earth-ground-resistance.html>

Note - the energy released in Bikini H-bomb was 8 M-ton TNT or $8 \times 10^6 \times 4.184 \times 10^9 \text{ j/ton} = 3.3472\text{E}+16 \text{ j}$

It's important not to get hung up on the sigfigs because actual values are incalculable without *in situ* measurement, which is both impossible and unlikely. It'd be deadly at any rate.

So we see that at the lower boundary, such as a small strike sie, we can expect a vajra to be worth 113 or so lightning bolts, while at the upper end, possibly 450 billion bolts, with an average of about 150-250 thousand bolts of typical lightning. This seems far more reasonable than our classical model. Moreover, it demonstrates a new problem: either the event would have to be massively prolonged (as is expected), or some other mechanism would need to be proposed or at least appended to this mechanism for the melting of the ice sheets. The author proposes that the meltdown was caused by four factors:

1. Change in ocean current behavior as HEME and PEC behaviors adapted to SSC changes
2. Change in orbit and tilt, altering slightly the received plasma characteristics, which slightly changed Earth's own PEC behaviors.
3. Vajra/thunderbolt mechanisms, and sure, some impacts
4. Tectonic heating caused by SSC changes due to shifting positions relative to the sun⁴⁵⁵

Figure 119 - Jupiter-Io, showing Io's plumes; credit: Southwest Research Institute⁴⁵⁶

⁴⁵⁵ The author believes the sun was part of the SSC before but its characteristics may have altered, for reasons unknown, rather than merely intercepting the Jovian-Saturnian solar system. Mytho-historical evidence supports both postulates. One thing is for sure, the sun's color changed, and the sky also changed color as the plasma sheath behaviors altered. The best evidence for this is in the green leafy plant color, which - to the author - is inexplicable because the sun puts out green the most. Also, a great number of people are red-green colorblind, suggesting a lack of adaptive necessity. Lighting may have actually been more muted before, and full of more blue-purple.

⁴⁵⁶ <http://earthsky.org/space/once-a-day-ios-atmosphere-collapses>

"Artist's concept of umbrella-like plumes of sulfur dioxide gas, which extend up to 300 miles (500 km) above the surface of Jupiter's moon Io, and which contribute to Io's atmosphere. Notice Jupiter in the background, and notice Jupiter's shadow on Io."

Solar Wind Electric Currents from our Sun and “hot grains”

Although, also, the work of the solar-system circuit (stellar wind) or SSC has been recently performed for us, it may be helpful for the reader to know that there *is* an MHD equation also for the electric current produced in stars:

B. ELECTRIC CURRENT RATIO OF ELECTRON IMPINGEMENT TO PHOTOELECTRON EMISSION

To demonstrate the dominance of photoelectric emission over grain charging, we compare the electric current due to electron impingement, J_e , and the electric current due to photoelectron emission, J_{ph} . The ratio of the currents, J_e/J_{ph} , for neutral (i.e., $Q = 0$) dust grains at rest ($w = 0$) in the reference frame of stellar wind can be written as

$$\frac{J_e}{J_{ph}} = \left(\frac{R_\star}{r}\right)^{1/4} \left[\frac{v_{cor}/v_{sw}^\infty}{1 - (R_\star/r)} \right] \left(\frac{\dot{M}_\star}{4\pi r_0^2 \mu m_u} \right) I_0^{-1}, \quad (B2)$$

where v_{cor} is the mean thermal velocity of electrons in the corona:

$$v_{cor} = \sqrt{\frac{8k_B T_{cor}}{\pi m_e}}, \quad (B3)$$

with m_e being the mass of an electron, and I_0 is the photoelectron flux at $r_0 = 1$ au from the central star:

$$I_0 = \int_W^\infty d(h\nu) Q_{abs}(h\nu) \pi \left(\frac{R_\star}{r_0}\right)^2 P_\star(h\nu) Y(h\nu) \left[1 - \left(1 + \frac{h\nu - W}{\phi_{ph}} \right) \exp\left(-\frac{h\nu - W}{\phi_{ph}}\right) \right], \quad (B4)$$

with $Q_{abs}(h\nu) = C_{abs}(h\nu)/(\pi a^2)$ being the absorption efficiency of the grains at photon energy $h\nu$. To obtain the upper limit to the current ratio, we shall take $I_0 = 5.9 \times 10^{13}$ electrons $m^{-2} s^{-1}$, which corresponds to the photoelectron flux from lunar fine grains under solar irradiation (Feuerbacher et al. 1972; Senshu et al. 2015). Feuerbacher et al. (1972) noted that photoelectrons emitted from a fine grain are most likely reabsorbed by the other grains, because the photoelectron flux from lunar fine grains is one order of magnitude lower than the fluxes from solid surfaces, regardless of the surface materials (cf. Feuerbacher & Fitton 1972). In addition, the photoelectric quantum yield $Y(h\nu)$ for dust grains with $a = 100$ nm or smaller is higher than the yield for a bulk surface of the same material (Kimura 2016). Therefore, we may expect that the photoelectron flux of single small grains are significantly higher than $I_0 = 5.9 \times 10^{13}$ electrons $m^{-2} s^{-1}$. If the solar values are inserted into Eq. (B2), we obtain

$$\frac{J_e}{J_{ph}} \approx 0.23 \left(\frac{r}{1 \text{ au}}\right)^{-1/4} \left[1 - 4.65 \times 10^{-3} \left(\frac{r}{1 \text{ au}}\right)^{-1} \right]^{-1} \left(\frac{T_{cor}}{1.6 \text{ MK}}\right)^{1/2} \left(\frac{v_{sw}^\infty}{448 \text{ km s}^{-1}}\right)^{-1} \left(\frac{\dot{M}_\star}{2.5 \times 10^{-14} M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}}\right) \times \left(\frac{I_0}{5.9 \times 10^{13} \text{ electrons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}}\right)^{-1}. \quad (B5)$$

Namely, the condition of $J_e/J_{ph} < 1$ is fulfilled except for the sublimation zone at $r < 3 R_\odot$, indicating that photoelectron emission is indeed the dominant charging process. We confirm $J_e/J_{ph} < 1$ by the current ratios J_e/J_{ph} numerically computed from Eqs. (3) and (7) not only around the Sun but also around β Pic and ϵ Eri, except for carbon grains in the immediate vicinity of ϵ Eri at $r < 6 R_\star$.

Figure 120 - Stellar Current; credit: Kimura et al...⁴⁵⁷

The reader will remember from the prior citation that each “hot grain” (particle from now on) is worth ~4-5V in open space. The question is threefold:

1. Where does the energy source of the voltage ultimately come from?

“Data showed that Io’s atmosphere begins to “deflate” when the temperatures drop from -235 degrees Fahrenheit in sunlight to -270 degrees Fahrenheit during eclipse. Eclipse occurs 2 hours of every Io day (1.7 Earth days). In full eclipse, the atmosphere effectively collapses as most of the SO₂ gas settles as frost on the moon’s surface. The atmosphere redevelops as the surface warms once the moon returns to full sunlight.”

⁴⁵⁷ Ibid. pp. 12-13

2. Can it vary, and by how much?
3. How will varying magnetism alter (in what ranges) the impedance, permeability, and ultimately current of the SSC?

The author has written a paper already, "Plasma-Electromagnetic Sky," that covers answer one: the SSC receives its energy from the Galactic Electric Circuit (GEC), which comes further from the supra-galactic level (SGEC). The author has already in a previous section detailed how the energy distributes, coalesces, disperses, redistributes, etc... in order to preserve according to the Laws of Energy and Laws of Thermodynamics and Electromagnetism⁴⁵⁸.

As for the second query, it is the contention of Juergens-Thornhill, et al... that it does vary, and by massive numbers. They contend that the Hertzsprung-Russell diagram actually represents voltage levels in stars⁴⁵⁹. Quoting the author's paper section, on Juergens:

Juergens Model

The case made by Ralph Juergens in the 1960s and 1970s for an Electric Sun was very convincing and nearly complete. It however did lack some of the features added to it below by Donald Scott, and from Alfvénic magnetic hydrodynamics which were confirmed in the 2000s. The main features of the Juergens model⁸³ are as follows:

1. Cathode drop explained by a 10^{10} voltage drop across the poles of the sun.
2. Electrons in solar "wind" leaving the sun with about 10^{10} eV of power.
3. Explanation for the solar wind via an Electric field accelerating the particles away from the surface.⁸⁴
4. Explanation of the massive increase in corona temperature as compared to the solar surface.⁸⁵
5. A prediction of current at around 2×10^{-10} A/m²; the actual value is one order of magnitude below this.
6. A prediction that the voltage potential would be approximately the same throughout the solar sheath for several light years (putting it in contact with the sheath of Polaris at least).
7. An electron "re-capturing" sphere of approximately 10^{27} square meters in size, extending past Pluto to 10^{13} meters (Pluto is 6×10^{12} m away from the sun).
8. A prediction that the Earth is receiving a current of 4×10^{16} A with a density of 1.4×10^{-7} A/m².

As regards to "how will it be powered?" The model stipulates that a positive spherical shell will outside the stellar limit will exist within the galactic interstellar space, and this will provide enough negative space to create a potential drop that essentially recirculates the electrons backwards to the star.

Figure 121 - Juergens Model; author/R Juergens⁴⁶⁰

Notice that Ralph calculated a much higher current than has been expected at the Van Allen Belts. This is no small change. What if the Juergens-Scott HR diagram alteration reveals a reality of not just a current change from a y-dwarf to a main sequence of several orders of magnitude, but a voltage change, as well. And what if it is the same star that changes? Like a transformer if the current goes up, does the voltage drop? Or is the entire system powered by the GEC receive more current and more voltage (or less of both)?

The author has no specific answers, only to say it varies and by several orders of magnitude, but for as yet untested and unknowable reasons. However, the continued research into the 'Hot Jupiters' will ultimately reveal the answer, as already several different kinds of hot gas giants to cold and "dark as charcoal" have been found, each following the physics of Liquid Metallic Hydrogen.

⁴⁵⁸ [6] Appendix B.I,II, and IV

⁴⁵⁹ [4] pp. 22-25

⁴⁶⁰ <https://www.kronos-press.com/juergens/1982-electric-solar-energy-juergens.pdf>

The third query is, at this juncture, totally unanswerable. It will take years, perhaps decades for the MMs (and Gaia) results and data to return with answers. Right now there is no doubt it is altering⁴⁶¹, flexing⁴⁶² and twisting⁴⁶³ producing remarkable alterations in the space around Earth. Therefore the impedance (and so permeability during arc and voltage-breakdown) will vary by enormous amounts. Also the current will be expected to vary. Again, probably not exceeding that of the 10^{15-16} A detected in the ultimate AGN's thus far.

Lightning Physics

The lightning physics work on Uman & Dwyer is far too extensive to quote satisfactorily in this paper. Just some of the more interesting facts are to be covered with a novel preamble: this is all assuming there is *any value* at all to the discussion of terrestrial lightning to the discussion of extraterrestrial Vajra. The author has his doubts. However, it will inform the discussion of Step Potential below, so it seems in that way, contextually beneficial.

1. 4 Types of Strikes that gap from cloud to ground:
 - a. Cloud towards ground or ground towards cloud
 - b. Negative stepped leader (90%) or positive stepped leader (10%)
2. Max E-field measurements (avg of Table 3.1⁴⁶⁴): 208.6 kV m^{-1}
3. 9 million discharges per year (very active considering minor stimulation)
4. Avg length 5-10 km, some over 100 km
 - a. Once a channel is formed, it will remain in place until discharge equilibrium is reached.
5. Avg total event time of 0.5s, broken into several stages⁴⁶⁵
 - a. Stepped leader searching for "feelers" 1-20 ms (1000 A peak)
 - b. Attachment Process 20 ms
 - c. First return stroke 20.1 - 60 ms
 - d. Dart leader 60 ms - 62 ms
 - e. 2nd return stroke 62.05 ms
6. Avg pre-stroke current 100-200 A
7. Avg stroke current 10 - 100 kA (30 kA), max 300 kA⁴⁶⁶
8. Leader channel: 5000 K ; Return stroke current Temp: 30,000 °C
9. Shock wave 10-100 m around returning stroke channel
10. Critical field propagation $E_s \sim 5 \times 10^5 \text{ V/m}$ at sea level (+) or $1 \times 10^6 \text{ V/m}$ (-)

Bear in mind, also this statement,

"The problem of how lightning is initiated inside thunderclouds is not only one of the biggest unsolved problems in lightning physics; it is also probably one of the biggest mysteries in the atmospheric sciences.... We routinely see very large sparks being made inside thunderclouds in the form of lightning. This suggests that there is either something wrong with our measurements or there is something wrong with our understanding of how electrical discharges occur in the thunderstorm environment. When we consider how much we know about complex and exotic astrophysical objects halfway across the universe, it is quite amazing that we do not understand the basics of how something as common as lightning gets started in clouds just a few miles above our heads."⁴⁶⁷

⁴⁶¹ <https://youtu.be/LX12E0-1XXw>

⁴⁶² <https://youtu.be/e6fe6yiUTRY>

⁴⁶³ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1806.05741.pdf>

⁴⁶⁴ Ibid. pp. 168

⁴⁶⁵ Ibid. pp. 152-153

⁴⁶⁶ Ibid. pp. 154

⁴⁶⁷ Ibid. pp. 163

There are many more detailed physics and measurements found in the document cited, but it is clear that we do not know enough about lightning, let alone how difficult it would be to make a very precise and accurate model of a Vajra! However, the author has tried to synthesize this process somewhat, based upon this work cited, and that of Peratt, Gurnett, and Thornhill. But for now, even with advanced software simulation, this is likely to remain a very mysterious process, considering the assumptions and variables in Table 9.

Step Potential (Voltage)

Thankfully, Dr. Uman's work on Lightning Protection, is very clear and extremely useful for modeling⁴⁶⁸.

"According to Saraoja (1977), the local soil resistivity ρ depends largely on the water content of the soil and the resistivity of that water, the relation being given by Hummel's empirical formula:

$$\rho = \left(\frac{1.5}{p} - 0.5 \right) \rho_v \quad (5.1)$$

where ρ is the soil resistivity in ohm-meters, ρ_v is the resistivity of the water in the soil in ohm-meters, and p is the relative volume of water in the soil...

"If a lightning current I is injected into the electrode, the magnitude of the current density j in the Earth, that is, the current per unit area perpendicular to the direction of current flow, assuming that current flows uniformly radially outward from the hemispherical surface, is

$$j = \frac{1}{2\pi r^2} a_r, \quad r > r_0 \quad (5.2)$$

where r is the radial distance from the strike point at the center of the circular flat surface of the hemisphere... Ohm's Law in "point" form mathematically relates the current density at a point in a conducting material to the electric field intensity E at that point in the material, where E and j are both in the radial direction

$$E = \rho j \quad (5.3)$$

That is, the electric field provides the force that drives the electrons that form the current density, and the proportionality constant between the field and the current density is the resistivity...

As illustrated [below], the difference in the voltage between any two points in the Earth or on the Earth's surface at two different radii, $r = a$ and $r = b$, is found from electrostatic principles as

$$V_{ab} = - \int_b^a E_r dr = \frac{\rho I}{2\pi} \left(\frac{1}{a} - \frac{1}{b} \right), \quad a > r_0, \quad b > a \quad (5.5)$$

*"The voltage difference between any two points on the Earth's surface at different radii a and b is called the "step voltage" because it will appear between the two feet of a standing human with one foot at a and the other at b , as shown [below], when lightning current flows uniformly outward in the soil from the strike point. The step voltage is given by Eq. (5.5) to the extent that the lightning strike-point can be treated as a small hemisphere, not an unreasonable approximation⁴⁶⁹. **The higher the soil resistivity and the current, the higher the step voltage between a and b ; the larger the distance between a and b , the larger the voltage between a and b .**" [emphasis added]*

⁴⁶⁸ The following work will be cited from Uman, Ibid. pp. 88-95 and 125-131

⁴⁶⁹ Which, unfortunately for us, is not true, and that is the limit of this model - the only model available - since the size of strikes we are dealing with will definitely propagate non spherically but cylindrically.

Fig. 5.2 The calculation of the grounding resistance of a metal hemisphere.

Figure 122 - Surge Protection spherical propagation; credit: D Gurnett⁴⁷⁰

⁴⁷⁰ Ibid. pp. 90

The mechanism of step voltage for current injected into the metal hemisphere of Fig. 5.2. The dashed lines represent surfaces of equal voltage (potential), called equipotential surfaces.

Figure 123 - Step voltage/Potential model by Dr. Gurnett⁴⁷¹

Despite the problem with the model (see footnote above), the author will continue with the calculations because it is the best and only model available. It is possible to create a cylindrical model, but since the thickness of the Earth's crust, let alone the soil and bedrock layers vary, the author contends it won't matter incredibly much in our context.

What does matter is the emphasized material above, that the step potential is worse for larger animals and under increased current. In this case, we have both.

⁴⁷¹ Ibid. pp. 91

Utilizing our minimum voltage, minimum current v_{ajra} , and the typical footprint size of a full grown Columbian mammoth (~3-3.5 m)⁴⁷² (mammoth got as small as 120-160 cm), we will play with a few calculations. Bear in mind this paper's goal is not to calculate the step potentials of each extinct species, or to cross-check them. Given the facts of how variable the models have been, it seems a bit fruitless. Remember: the hypothesis is that animals that had difficulty breeding, or walked on four legs, did not live in trees⁴⁷³, or caves, and relied upon prey that fit in these categories were most susceptible to the step potential vector⁴⁷⁴.

There is a simplified equation, which will be useful to know what type of voltage we can expect at 100 m, 1000 m and 10,000 m from strike center.

$$V_{ro}^{\infty} \simeq \frac{\rho I}{2\pi r_o} \quad (5.6)$$

Here we will assume a Resistivity of 300 ohm-meters for (5.6) and ground, and an origination from 100-100,000 meters from strike center for (5.5), using 300 ohm for ground current and 700 ohm for body current.

In the case of (5.5), 100 m wide from strike center yielded 119 kV **for the smallest current found** in Table 11.

Table 13 - Radial Propagation voltages based on Table 11

	V_min	V_max	V_avg	V_limit
100m	1.19E+05	2.39E+08	2.39E+06	3.10E+05
1000m	1.19E+04	2.39E+07	2.39E+05	3.10E+04
10000m	1.19E+03	2.39E+06	2.39E+04	3.10E+03

The drop-off in voltage using (5.6) is linear, but in Table 14, we see that according to the 3.5m footprint of the mammoth's position, it will drop off geometrically, with an imposed limit of potential killing power (again using the smallest Vajra) at 2000-2500 m (over 6,000 feet)

A couple things to note: the current may be deadlier for a human or other small animal, or it may be better, being a smaller step potential. Also, the resistivity of different bodies are different. The author does not know the true resistivity of a Columbian Mammoth, he expects it would be higher than 300hm but perhaps not as high as for a human since elephant species are renowned for sensitive feet with many nerves. Finally, there is the issue of core versus surface spread of the charge of the body. Given that the literature varies in how many mA it takes to stop a heart, the author will assume 10 mA is the safe current (as high as 30 mA may be considered deadly in houses) and then quote the author,

"At a current of 0.04 to 0.06 amperes, asphyxia may occur from prolonged contraction of the chest muscles... From Dalziel (1953) the threshold energy level for fibrillation of the 700 ohm individual... is about 350 j... If we linearly extrapolate to a 70 kilogram human, certainly a questionable extrapolation, the lethal energy is 4410 j."⁴⁷⁵

The question arises, what is the lethal energy for a dire wolf, mammoth, mastodon, or ground sloth? The author certainly does not know.

⁴⁷² Subtracting a meter for the head http://library.sandiegozoo.org/factsheets/_extinct/mammoth/mammoth.htm

⁴⁷³ Although birds probably would have been knocked from the sky by EMP and various piezoelectric effects.

⁴⁷⁴ Vs. the starvation, cold, competition (including human hunting), or war vectors.

⁴⁷⁵ Ibid. pp 129

Table 14 - Step Potential Calculations for Columbian Mammoth 3.5m footprint

Distances (m)	Voltages	I_ground @ 300ohm (mA)	I_body @ 700 ohm (mA)
100	3,346.37	11,154.56	4,780.53
200	931.85	3,106.16	1,331.21
300	429.90	1,432.99	614.14
400	246.44	821.45	352.05
500	159.53	531.78	227.90
600	111.64	372.13	159.48
700	82.47	274.91	117.82
800	63.40	211.35	90.58
900	50.26	167.53	71.80
1000	40.81	136.05	58.31
2000	10.32	34.41	14.75
3000	4.61	15.35	6.58
4000	2.60	8.65	3.71
5000	1.66	5.54	2.38
10000	0.42	1.39	0.60
100000	0.00	0.01	0.01

Voltages, I_ground @ 300ohm and I_body @ 700 ohm

Figure 124; credit: author⁴⁷⁶

Just for fun, and because we can, let us now look at the ridiculous currents from Table 11 (using the same resistances as in Table 14), and also limit ourselves, bearing in mind that the idea is that these are **single**

⁴⁷⁶ Source data provided in previous spreadsheet link

stroke (no dart leader, pump mechanism, standard 30 microsecond burst). Already we see in figure 121 that these strikes are deadly for a human or mammoth out to 2000 m or more than a mile away.

Table 15 - Max and Limited Vajra Voltages and Currents

Voltages	<i>Maximum Vajra</i>		Voltages	<i>Limited Vajra</i>	
	I_ground (mA)	I_body (mA)		I_ground (mA)	I_body (mA)
6,692,736.04	22,309,120.14	9,561,051.49	8,700.56	29,001.86	12,429.37
1,863,695.98	6,212,319.95	2,662,422.84	2,422.80	8,076.02	3,461.15
859,791.22	2,865,970.73	1,228,273.17	1,117.73	3,725.76	1,596.76
492,870.55	1,642,901.85	704,100.79	640.73	2,135.77	915.33
319,066.80	1,063,556.01	455,809.72	414.79	1,382.62	592.55
223,278.98	744,263.27	318,969.97	290.26	967.54	414.66
164,945.29	549,817.63	235,636.13	214.43	714.76	306.33
126,808.88	422,696.27	181,155.54	164.85	549.51	235.50
100,517.64	335,058.81	143,596.63	130.67	435.58	186.68
81,629.50	272,098.32	116,613.57	106.12	353.73	151.60
20,646.41	68,821.37	29,494.87	26.84	89.47	38.34
9,212.01	30,706.71	13,160.02	11.98	39.92	17.11
5,191.88	17,306.26	7,416.97	6.75	22.50	9.64
3,326.70	11,089.00	4,752.43	4.32	14.42	6.18
833.63	2,778.76	1,190.90	1.08	3.61	1.55
8.35	27.85	11.93	0.01	0.04	0.02

The max powered Vajra remains deadly at 100,000 m (62 miles), which surely a location such as Devil's Tower+Black Hills would have been quite able to propagate that far, or further, given the soil type⁴⁷⁷. This would definitely constitute a power worth worshiping (same for Ayer's Rock, in Australia). But even the limited Vajra has potency out to 3000 - 4000 m (1.86 - 2.48 miles)! That is truly the power of the gods. This supplies us both our vector for selective worldwide extinction (not to mention Younger Dryas mechanism), but explains not only "out of place" geology, but also "out of place" anthropology.

The worship of heaped earth, and indeed the justification for imagery, worldwide, is logically consistent, and certainly more meaningful than the idea that a culture would spend millions of calories building earthworks by hand to do something that can be created in a 1 m space using stakes and rocks, on soil or rocky/sand stone surfaces.

It may happen that the reader finds this entire exercise ridiculous. The author **agrees**. The model is way too loose, even using MHD/satellite data. The author invites more specific and precise modeling in a rebuttal.

⁴⁷⁷ Please note that the voltages and currents listed are more than sufficient to empower earth removal on a vast scale, and scorching/vaporizing the land, and as noted before, the energy levels are consistent with Bikini sized H-bombs 10^{16} j or more.

Final Criticisms

Three criticisms must be levied here that have not been levied anywhere else in the paper, which may make the discussion in the next section all the more relevant.

The first is simple enough: can any hypothesis, no matter how well supported, no matter the testimony - even worldwide, comparative mythology, etc., no matter the physical evidence, really be considered scientific (with as many assumptions as found in Table 9 and in the last section?) Probably not. Nor can **any** simulation be scientific, even if it was run by a team comprised of Peratt, Uman, Gurnett, Clarage, Thornhill, etc... using the SAFIRE lab and Gable's intuitive methods and Yelverton's support. Why? It simply has too many variables. The fact is, though, it's far better science than the majority of astrophysics today which is mostly making guesses. Take for example the following words from a "serious" academic paper regarding the charge measurements of AGN SGR A*,⁴⁷⁸ which claimed among other things, "the current upper observational limit on the charge of Sgr A* is $.3 \times 10^8 C$ "

"The black-hole charge can also be of a non-electric origin (Zakharov 2014), namely a tidal charge induced by an extra dimension in the Randall-Sundrum (RS) braneworld solutions or 5D warped geometry theory (Randall & Sundrum 1999; Bin-Nun 2010, 2011), in which the observable Universe is a (3 + 1)-brane (domain wall) that includes the standard matter fields and the gravity field propagates further to higher dimensions."⁴⁷⁹

Though this is an elegant paper, that is one long pseudo-scientific statement, based in no reality as SUSY has already been officially falsified. It throws a huge question on the entire paper, and the massive number of assumptions made in the Introduction, as well as in the logic, reasoning, and calculations. This is what passes for Science in this day and age. So, compared in that stead, actually the author feels compelled to stand by this paper's assumptions as merely the most conservative (other than denying charge separation in space, which is a useless argument).

The next criticism would be the entire approach of not only comparative mythology, (which has been the ire of specialists for decades and uniformitarians for 150 years), but the idea of combining hard and soft sciences at all. Therefore negating the need for this paper and these calculations. Two thoughts: first, it's an interesting problem to solve and the author hopes that debunkers take the time to actually make counter models and arguments, rather than use the tried and "true" technique of 'dismissal out of hand.' That isn't science. Second, that many sciences are combined and that's how new sciences and paradigms are born; not all that different from star and galaxy mergers. So there is nothing untowards about combining sciences and myths. This is how Troy was discovered, and how quantum mechanics was created, etc...

The final criticism is that of the results. Chiefly: they are rather **small**, aren't they? Even at the maximum, we are talking 62 miles in a radius or 12,075 sq. miles (31,415 km²). That's only 0.02% of the land area of Earth, for a maximum - and this is key - single stroke Vajra. Well, that's the issue: the single stroke with no pumping or saturation calculated. But the expectation of the author, based on the work in Table 10, is to have had dozens of thousands to hundreds of thousands of these. The author is aware they would come in bursts, and in clusters. Not every site could be a Devil's Tower or Eye of the Sahara or even a Big Sink. Bare in mind, however, that the event at Big Sink would more than justify the beliefs of the Delaware chief's story. Furthermore, although it would not support the idea of Step Potential as the primary vector of megafauna extinction, it would justify the belief that it was a part *not discussed*. And then focus would have to shift to a shared mechanism between all the weapons of the gods, and return to a hypothesis that there was a Great Flood prior to the Deluge event. This is a subject beyond this paper and the scholarship today, since the focus on errata of Younger Dryas seems all ice based.

⁴⁷⁸ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1808.07327.pdf>

⁴⁷⁹ Ibid. pp. 15

Still, the author would like to stand by these results as **best first** calculations and challenge the readership and critics to provide a better model. Perhaps the cylindrical model of SPV distribution or a comprehensive MHD/flux rope in atmosphere model for power source, or both.

Legends of the Bolts and the God-Power

In the last section of the closing up of Part 4, the author wants to revisit some of the worldwide legends concerning all of the weapons of the gods, from thunderbolts to “hail” to flood and winds. To see what other massive cataclysmic forces may have added to the aforementioned vectors (and also the outgas explosions of superheated Earth noted by J Gable in experiment).

We’re not able to cover every weapon of all the gods, and mostly we are to skip the Other category, saving it perhaps for another EPEMC paper. Rather, the author would like to focus on the first three categories.

Table 16 - Weapons of the Gods Names or god who wielded them ^{480 481482}

	Greece	Babylonian	India [Norse]	Brittain/Celtic	Americas	China [Japan]
<i>Thunder...</i>		Sharur	Vajra [Mjólnir]	Caladbolg	Thunderbird	Jiu-feng (bird)
<i>Spear/Trident</i>	Poseidon		Vel/Trishula Pashupatastra	Lugh/Invincible Gae Bulg		[Ame-no-nuhoko]
<i>Sword</i>	Harpē		Asi Nandaka [Høfuð]	Claíomh-Solais Fragarach Dyrnwyn		Gan Jiang Mo Xie/Ye [Kusanagi]
<i>Archery</i>	Apollo		Pinaka, etc ⁴⁸³			
<i>Winds</i>	Titans		“Seven Winds”		Jem of Kukulcan	
<i>Tectonics</i>	Titans	Tiamat cracked ½ by Marduk	Sinking of Dwaraka		Lakota Creator-God	
<i>Floods</i>	Titans	Enlil	Missile>sinking of Dwaraka			
<i>Blasts</i>	Titans		Narayanastra Brahmastra	Balor’s Eye	Xiuhcoatl	
<i>Hammer, etc..</i>	Hephaestus	Sharur	Gada Agnyastra ⁴⁸⁴		Foot of God (Delaware)	Ruyi Jingu Bang

For the most part the majority of the weapons of the gods myths fall into the categories of swords, arrows, and blasts, with all of these being related to trembling, flooding, and disintegration in the Earth. This means, by far, that the most common weapon is not the hurtling stones but the electrically related

⁴⁸⁰ <http://www.ancientpages.com/2015/07/28/10-divine-weapons-of-the-gods/>

⁴⁸¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_magical_weapons

⁴⁸² <https://tenmania.com/mythological-weapons-ancient-gods/>

⁴⁸³ Arrow of Brahma, Gandiva, Kaundinya, Kodandam, Sharanga, Sharkha, Dhanush, Teen Baan (arrows), Vijaya

⁴⁸⁴ <https://www.ancient-code.com/fire-of-the-gods-mythological-weapons-of-the-ancient-past/>

sword/thunderbolt/spear/trident/vajra. There are a few cultures that also include impacts as hammers or blasts, or crackings of the Earth. So a comet-swarm or occasional comet or asteroid cannot be discounted in the least. The supersonic Huracan/Taifeng of the gods must have been related to the comets and/or celestial bodies passing near. They would have to have been of enormously high speed and heat to shape the mountains noted by researcher Andy Hall in previously cited work. But there is surprisingly little information about these winds of destruction, unless one includes the plagues of disease that accompanied the comet events. Most of the winds were not named as super destructive but simply deadly.

Referring to the quotes at the start of the paper, however, one must conclude that thunderbolts did indeed kill people, and floods were also involved, as according to the Americans.

Figure 125 - Thunderbird of North America; credit: P Bostrom

“Winnebago Indians of the northern Midwest and Plains state believed that the Thunderbird possessed supernatural powers. The Thunderbird was a shapeshifter and could take the form of

humans. Interestingly, the legendary falcon warrior or "birdman" is a common motif in Mississippian culture. It has been depicted with a beaked face on unearthened artifacts from Cahokia to Georgia. In some traditions, Birdman is interpreted as a version of Red Horn, another heroic figure whose twin sons fought off a race of giants. Scientists believe the Birdman was a warrior king, but it's also possible this was the legendary Thunderbird.

"According to Winnebago Indians, the Thunderbird was able to manipulate weather, affecting the winds and creating storms, lightning, thunder, and rain. There were not just one Thunderbird, but many of them were often seen in the skies. The Thunderbirds were enemies with the Water Spirits and the giant birds used their lightning when crossing the waters, to protect them from the water spirits."⁴⁸⁵

The above is so well written, the author finds no need to improve upon it. Only to remark that this paper agrees with the above synopsis of how a plasmoid filled sky (due to celestial objects passing near Earth) might look to people on Earth. The shape-shifting is the changing of the same motif into many forms, but it's truly the same motif. Such as the wings of Hermes' shoes, etc...

Continuing from the same source,

"According to the Passamaquoddy, the Thunderbirds were men who could transform themselves into flying creatures. Their legend tells that "Thunderbird is an Indian and he or his lightning would never harm another Indian. But Wochowsen, great bird from the south, tried hard to rival Thunderbird. So Passamaquoddies feared Wochowsen, whose wings Gluskap once had broken, because he used too much power.

"In Native American mythogoly [sic], Gluskap is a mythical hero who defeated evil sorcerers and demon followers."

"The Quillayute Indians of the Pacific Northwest remember how the Thunderbird was sent by the Great Spirit to help the Indians after a horrible disaster. The Indians had no food and many had died after rain and hail had fallen for many days, destroying all plants. After the rain came snow and the Indians called the Great Spirit for help and it then, he sent people the Thunderbird.

"The story of the Thunderbird's arrival is described in detail in the book Indian Legends of the Pacific Northwest written by Ella E. Clark:

"The people waited. No one spoke. There was nothing but silence and darkness. Suddenly, there came a great noise, and flashes of lightning cut the darkness. A deep whirring sound, like giant wings beating, came from the place of the setting sun. All of the people turned to gaze toward the sky above the ocean as a huge, bird-shaped creature flew toward them.

This bird was larger than any they had ever seen. Its wings, from tip to tip, were twice as long as a war canoe. It had a huge, curving beak, and its eyes glowed like fire. The people saw that its great claws held a living, giant whale. In silence, they watched while Thunderbird - for so the bird was named by everyone - carefully lowered the whale to the ground before them.

Thunderbird then flew high in the sky, and went back to the thunder and lightning it had come from. Perhaps it flew back to its perch in the hunting grounds of the Great Spirit. Thunderbird and Whale saved the Quillayute from dying. The people knew that the Great Spirit had heard their prayer.

Even today they never forget that visit from Thunderbird, never forget that it ended long days of hunger and death. For on the prairie near their village are big, round stones that the grandfathers say are the hardened hailstones of that storm long ago." [sic]

And finally,

⁴⁸⁵ <http://www.ancientpages.com/2017/03/26/powerful-thunderbird-sent-gods-protect-humans-evil-native-american-legends/>

“Thunderbird is a very large bird, with feathers as long as a canoe paddle. When he flaps his wings, he makes thunder and the great winds. When he opens and shuts his eyes, he makes lightning. In stormy weather, he flies through the skies, flapping his wings and opening and closing his eyes.

“Thunderbird's home is a cave in the Olympic Mountains, and he wants no one to come near it. If hunters get close enough so he can smell them, he makes thunder noise, and he rolls ice out of his cave. The ice rolls down the mountainside, and when it reaches a rocky place, it breaks into many pieces. The pieces rattle as they roll farther down into the valley.

“All the hunters are so afraid of Thunderbird and his noise and rolling ice that they never stay long near his home. No one ever sleeps near his cave. Thunderbird keeps his food in a dark hole at the edge of a big field of ice and snow. His food is the whale. Thunderbird flies out of the ocean, catches a whale and hurries back to the mountains to eat it. One time Whale fought Thunderbird so hard that during the battle, trees were torn up by their roots. To this day there are no trees in Beaver Prairie because of the fight Whale and Thunderbird had that day.”

“One of the most interesting aspects of the legend is that the Quillayute mention the Great Flood in their description of the battle between Thunderbird and whale.”[sic]⁴⁸⁶

It's very clear from these depictions that the conclusions drawn by the author after the table have substantiations, as these myths were pulled by the author after the analysis. Some of the details added are very intriguing/compelling, such as descriptions of ice, or rolling. Not that Olympic Mountain in Washington is a very grand mountain, comparable to a Cosmic Mountain, as is evidenced by even its western name being Mt. Olympus.

Figure 126 - Olympic National Park, Washington; credit: thousandwonders.net

⁴⁸⁶ Ibid.

Another myth comes to us from the Cherokee, and it conflates the discussion of the Moon, sun, and thunder,

*"The Sun was a young woman and lived in the East, while her brother, the Moon, lived in the West. The girl had a lover who used to come every month in the dark of the moon to court her. He would come at night, and leave before daylight, and although she talked with him she could not see his face in the dark, and he would not tell her his name, until she was wondering all the time who it could be. At last she hit upon a plan to find out, so the next time he came, as they were sitting together in the dark of the *âsi*, she slyly dipped her hand into the cinders and ashes of the fireplace and rubbed it over his face, saying, "Your face is cold; you must have suffered from the wind," and pretending to be very sorry for him, but he did not know that she had ashes on her hand. After a while he left her and went away again.*

The next night when the Moon came up in the sky his face was covered with spots, and then his sister knew he was the one who had been

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coming to see her. He was so much ashamed to have her know it that he kept as far away as he could at the other end of the sky all the night. Ever since he tries to keep a long way behind the Sun, and when he does sometimes have to come near her in the west he makes himself as thin as a ribbon so that he can hardly be seen.

Some old people say that the moon is a ball which was thrown up against the sky in a game a long time ago. They say that two towns were playing against each other, but one of them had the best runners and had almost won the game, when the leader of the other side picked up the ball with his hand--a thing that is not allowed in the game--and tried to throw it to the goal, but it struck against the solid sky vault and was fastened there, to remind players never to cheat. When the moon looks small and pale it is because some one has handled the ball unfairly, and for this reason they formerly played only at the time of a full moon.

*When the sun or moon is eclipsed it is because a great frog up in the sky is trying to swallow it. Everybody knows this, even the Creeks and the other tribes, and in the olden times, eighty or a hundred years ago, before the great medicine men were all dead, **whenever they saw the sun grow dark the people would come together and fire guns and beat the drum**, and in a little while this would frighten off the great frog and the sun would be all right again.*

*The common people call both Sun and Moon *Nûñdâ*, one being "*Nûñdâ* that dwells in the day" and the other "*Nûñdâ* that dwells in the night," but the priests call the Sun *Su'tâlidihî*, "Six-killer," and the Moon *Ge'yâgu'ga*, though nobody knows now what this word means, or why they use these names. Sometimes people ask the Moon not to let it rain or snow.*

*The great Thunder and his sons, the two Thunder boys, live far in the west above the sky vault. The lightning and the rainbow are their beautiful dress. The priests pray to the Thunder and call him the Red Man, because that is the brightest color of his dress. There are other Thunders that live lower down, in the cliffs and mountains, and under waterfalls, and **travel on invisible bridges** from one high peak to another where they have their town houses. The great Thunders above the sky are kind and helpful when we pray to them, but these others are always plotting mischief. One must not point at the rainbow, or one's finger will swell at the lower joint." [sic, emphasis added]⁴⁸⁷*

Concerning the Deluge, the Cherokee had this to say,

"A long time ago a man had a dog, which began to go down to the river every day and look at the water and howl. At last the man was angry and scolded the dog, which then spoke to him and said: "Very soon there is going to be a great freshet and the water will come so high that everybody will be drowned; but if you will make a raft to get upon when the rain comes you can be saved, but you must

⁴⁸⁷ <http://www.sacred-texts.com/nam/cher/motc/motc008.htm>

first throw me into the water." The man did not believe it, and the dog said, "If you want a sign that I speak the truth, look at the back of my neck." He looked and saw that the dog's neck had the skin worn off so that the bones stuck out.

Then he believed the dog, and began to build a raft. Soon the rain came and he took his family, with plenty of provisions and they all got upon it. It rained for a long time, and the water rose until the mountains were covered and all the people in the world were drowned. Then the rain stopped and the waters went down again, until at last it was safe to come off the raft. Now there was no one alive but the man and his family, but one day they heard a sound of dancing and shouting on the other side of the ridge. The man climbed to the top and looked over; everything was still, but all along the valley he saw great piles of bones of the people who had been drowned, and then he knew that the ghosts had been dancing."⁴⁸⁸

But this story certainly must have come from the pre-Exodus event, and not the Younger Dryas. Still, it is yet another example of comparative mytho-history. There are literally thousands of such stories around the world, and almost all of them have to do with the Babylonian or Pre-Sumerian era Deluge⁴⁸⁹.

It is not necessary to continue listing myth after myth. Pretty much every tribe has the same variations of the myth, with different animals, names, genders, etc... The more lively myths seem to come from the Americas and India. But all of these myths are well recorded, even in Australia by the aborigines, so it was not a northern hemisphere only event. They have indeed been very specific about the electrical-energetic nature of their depictions of the "Squatter Man."

Conclusions

But there is a major issue with this, and that is chronology. Many of these myths appear to be related to the 680 BCE and 1600 BCE events, rather than the Younger Dryas. Only the Delaware, Lakota, Enuma Elish Atlantis myth, oldest Egyptian texts, and the Tepe steles appear to be related to the more important series of cataclysms starting in the Younger Dryas. So is it that there was one big cataclysm recently, or a series of them starting back then and coming forward, every 2000 or 3000 years between each?

The mainstream academics will argue none. The alternative mainstream will argue a couple comets, and separate them: 1 for Younger Dryas, 1 for the Deluge, something for the Sea Peoples, and that's it.

The myths however, point to the constant destruction, rebirth, and renewal after cataclysm. Even within the author's clinic Cherokee-Shawnee descendents have talked about family oral traditions of the Thunderbirds and cataclysms of the gods, and the bald mountains of Georgia.

Moreover, there is an aspect that bothers the author: the gap between the Tepe Period and the Megalithic Period, called the Archaic Period. What precisely occurred within that period to prevent agriculture from taking root? Why did the Cappadocians fear to do agriculture considering they had practised it for two thousand years in upper Turkey/Armenia? Also, when they moved south to form Sumer, what made them suddenly begin again? The author thinks it must have first been the end of the Saturnian God as the sole star⁴⁹⁰, and the entrance of our sun^{491 492} which starved Saturn of its plasma sheaths circulating ions⁴⁹³. This cause the YD event. From there the Tepe period began the practice of worship of the gods, plural, and Saturn was

⁴⁸⁸ <http://www.sacred-texts.com/nam/cher/motc/motc014.htm>

⁴⁸⁹ <http://www.talkorigins.org/faqs/flood-myths.html>

⁴⁹⁰ Causing Earth to rotate about Jupiter AND Saturn, and changing the day length and angular momentum.

⁴⁹¹ Perhaps Votan, the Black God of the Maya, was originally a "Hot Jupiter" of immense size.

<http://www.rapineal.com/mayadeities.html>

⁴⁹² If it was a planet, perhaps it brought its own satellites, and therefore aliens, and perhaps they did descend from "Heaven" and breed with the "ADAMU" women to create the "Nephilim"

⁴⁹³ Another Black God myth, <http://blackdogstar.blogspot.com/2009/09/black-heart-of-tezcatlipoca.html>

reduced to (sometimes even female) part of this. The Co-linear orbit was broken down into a “hand-off” system⁴⁹⁴. As the sun spiraled closer - or rather the former solar system did to it - there was a topsy-turvy effect upon things, leading the gas planets, and particularly their moons too close. The moon itself at the outside, being ancient as measured, was flung towards the Earth which captured it. This caused the destruction of “Kingu”, forming the first bolus of the asteroid belt.

From there, the author thinks the moon, having caused wide destruction, was interpreted as the gods’ displeasure with mankind. In particular, the One God. The two gas giants swapped Earth twice or thrice, and this created the Enki/Enlil story. Anu became the sun itself, which was quickly syphoning charge out of the pair, and the whole system was rapidly entering elliptical orbits, as dictated by a magnetospheric relationship to the solar wind, now much stronger, though the star was far off and smaller.

When this period of moon-Earth instability ended, the Earth entered into Jupiter’s care, as Set slays Osiris, and steals loads of moons, now in retrograde orbit. The event causes the dissolution of the family, and Hera, Poseidon, and Hades slip into the background. But Saturn and Jupiter have one more pass at each other, and there is a “war of the titans and gods” in which Zeus/Odin has to lead an assault. The close passage is interpreted by some as Yahweh/Enlil’s displeasure with mankind as it creates a massive Flood when a body (probably Hephaestus-Triton) passes too close to Earth and asteroids rain down. Hodr-Triton slays a “brother” body, and is banished to the Underworld (Uranus or simply the Black) for it, Uranus is, of course already in punishment by the God, which is why he is hanging up by his heels in Hell/Hades. To this day Triton remains in retrograde orbit.

When the Deluge recedes Zeus is worshiped as the creator of mankind and agriculture resumes. The previous evidence of it had been washed away except for Gobekli Tepe/Nevali Cori, which were buried at the time. They were buried because of the gods’ displeasure with mankind’s breakup of the family.

Meanwhile, the sun inches closer in the sky, increasing the power of the solar wind and the attractive force between the gas giants⁴⁹⁵. The first to leave are Uranus and Neptune, which cannot be held by Jupiter-Saturn binary. Next comes something unfathomable, the heart of the old god bursts (and it is unclear if this is Jupiter or Saturn as Greek and Mayan myths disagree), and out pops Venus-Athena-Loki-Kali. Her coming forth is worshiped as a sign. First as a son, then a daughter, then a warrior, next a ravaging bull-cow, then a monster or gorgon as the comet tail approaches Earth. The reason that Venus’ tail gets in the way is that Venus enters an elliptical path around the current sun, while Earth and Mars remain in transit around the god duo or Jupiter alone. Now by this time it does appear possible that Earth-Mars-Moon was a type of group, that had ceased to go around Jupiter-Saturn but Jupiter alone, as Hera/Frigg becomes more or less unimportant and worship of Ra is gone, replaced by Horus/Osiris with his one eye. Hermes/Heimdallr is sent “as a messenger” to the sun, and remains influential to this very day as an energetic go-between for the sun (new God) and planets, including Earth⁴⁹⁶

What power this venerable old god had was probably ripped right from the planet’s heart, and the “emerald” color that radiated out (creating an indigo plasma sheath) was now held in the Venus body. She was indeed green, originally. What was at first thought of as a good portent turned to omen. It started with Venus’ close passage to Mars, and their mutual electrification. This created debris, comets, meteors, etc... which led to a terribly violent sky. All the while the Jovian system neared the Sun, and Jupiter began to accelerate. This made Zeus smaller, although he would grow and shrink, always into “affairs” and sleeping with all kinds of “goddesses.” Meanwhile Mars became the archetypal war god on account of the difficulty of life in the Age of

⁴⁹⁴ Co-planar appears to have been only in the origination of the system up until the Dream Time. This was how the planet grew for billions of years.

⁴⁹⁵ In actuality when the star passed by, it began dragging the delicate, ancient solar system behind it, and they are ready now to enter their wide paths.

⁴⁹⁶ At one time the end of the Rainbow Road, but now in our better understanding, actually at the forefront. Note that the Sumerians numbered the planets backwards to us. This is not an accident on their part. Just chronology and later, humanity’s geocentric ignorance (fall from past knowledge)

Ares. Venus was the Bull of Heaven which ended Jupiter-Enlil's reign when the Heavenly demigod - Gilgamesh/Heracles⁴⁹⁷ slew it. How did Mars slay Venus in one set of legends and lose to her in another, and required being "sent away" by Zeus/Jupiter/Enlil to the Underworld (blackness of space). Perhaps it was a size issue, perhaps it was cultural impressions of gender (as their maleness and femaleness was very evenly decided worldwide and to this day). Also Aries would have been seen as the **good son** whereas Venus/Athena as the **bad daughter**. Therefore Mars' affair with Vulcan's wife to some, while Rama's battle with Ravana to others.

But before the event could reach the final conclusion, unfortunately for mankind, Earth passed too close to Venus one day, and the electrified plasma tail, both dark and plague causing upended life on Earth. In fact, not long after Hebrew worship of Jehovah is established, the Earth is ripped away, Mars too, and hurtled towards the sun (Apollo), which "grows like a child" to become the new Helios. Jehovah (Jove) is elevated to the status of a transcendental God, and the messiah personal God of religions is revived in the Hellenistic era. Houyi (Mars) "shoots the 9 stars and kills them" (leaving only the moon).

In the final chapter Mars betrays mankind, perhaps though as a bereaved son, or a mad warrior - a Berserker - and his bloodlust comes upon the Earth. Kali reigns supreme again, and the maleness of Mars is changed in India to female to describe the red dust, which is dumped across the world, causing a host of new types of infections. The scar (Valles Marineris) from battles with Athena is seen along with the various Mons. The power of Thor's thunderbolts and the occasional crash of rock into the planet reminds mankind of the power of Zeus (the Tetragrammaton/Yahweh), and Ba'al worship is revived, as well as Jupiter. Myths of Odin and Thor and Loki circulate for a long time in the North, spreading as a folk religion whilst the druidic mystery schools spread among bards and priests who long ago knew better. The Hebrew faith is also adopted by many peoples including the Jews. The messiah story spreads to all the Old World, leading to a slew of messiah births in Asia and Asia Minor. In MesoAmerica, Mars is worshipped as the God of War who needs sacrifice so his thunder power and magic can prevent the next apocalypse.

Then Mars, too, is left behind as the Earth-Moon itself settles into a remarkably stable and perfect position, where the moon's electrical properties help it to become more stable, and less electrically volatile. Through resonance, it matches the right diameter of the sun, and Apollo and the new Aphrodite, Artemis, are able to inhabit the sky. Sun and moon come to reflect the primordial gender conflict and co-operation in China.

The system is not yet done in re-organizing either. Venus' retrograde orbit is slowing down, and its color (and that of Saturn's poles) are changing. The heat of Jupiter and Saturn are still more expelling than absorbing, but decreasing each day, without the chargeup of a brown dwarf. They should be categorized dually as Y-dwarfs.

In the Americas and Britain, where the thunderbolts were most powerfully directed in the 680 BCE event (that did not result in wholesale destruction of cities and an entire turnover of belief and the worship of male messiahs,) this series of events was remarkable enough to form the basis of a kingly-mound society and even to reform mankind's interest in Olympus/Kailash. In the Ohio River valley the Allegewi formed a worship of the Cosmic sun around ancient and newer (smaller) Thunderbolt (Vajra) strike sites. By hand and by basket they heaped Earth upon craters and C-henge craters and they set about marking the seasons and solar behaviors on a large scale. The C-henges were especially auspicious because they had the cosmic pole entering within the egg (or ancient sky) to the sun. The New Sun was seen as the Son, born again. This religion appears to have sparked similar beliefs in another Algonquin group, the Hopewell, who began a very meso-american like hierarchical system centered around solar and lunar worship, and they described these events in earthwork form. At some point travelers arrived and were mixed into the fray. There was a division of cultural beliefs and political destiny, and always the newcomers such as Iroquois, Sioux, Vikings, etc... Eventually the Hopewell split, and reformed into Ft. Ancient and other Hopewell esque cultures, identified to historic tribes as all

⁴⁹⁷ Hence we know not only by Mars angle (like Earth's) identifies it with the planet Saturn (the smaller wife of Zeus, and his sister), but the very name Hera's warrior.

"Allegewi". Meanwhile, the other half became the Mississippians, who revived not only the Hopewellian heart of Cosmic platform/hill sun worship of the gods, but the agricultural traditions of the Archaic period, when Enlil-Zeus-Wakan Tanka had *shown* mankind how to grow food. The mechanism of this myth is not known at this time.

When Welsh arrived, they mingled with these peoples and taught them fortification, etc... The two formed the heart of a "Padouca" empire, which was antithetical to the ironically self-same religion of the Sioux and Iroquois, etc... who sought to wipe out their enemies, but **not** take over the forts. Their remains found along the Ohio river, and the Allegewi mummies left in Lexington, proximal to the ancient C-henge, made the land of Kithiki that of bloody and ancient myth, where gods, megafauna (giant animals) etc... had roamed. It was held as hunting grounds for all. But the memory of the events, and of the gods, and the sons of gods, remained as a worshipful era.... right up to when the Old World peoples, such as French and British and Spanish clashed with the New World. The Old World had embraced the messiah myth and gone full scale back into human development, but in actuality, it was no different than the Mexica and Maya, the worship of the God of War had not ended. Mankind behaved, even in the Age of Pisces (roughly the Religious Period), as if we were still in the Age of Ares, and sometimes even the Age of Taurus (under Jove). The self-same British explorers even proclaimed many a time, "By Jove" and Christians conquered "heathen" New World peoples (who had not the benefit of starting to modernize as quickly and as recklessly), still end prayer to this day with "Amen", hearkening back all the way to the worship of Amen-Re. The dollar bill even has Re's powerful one eye upon it.

Such is the way of history and of conquering. To erase and cover over, even that which is self-similar.

This brings us now to the Scientific Period which began preceding the Age of Aquarius, which already is fraught with complications and difficulties, with no gods, save anthropomorphic ones and messiahs of historic dubiousness, to guide us. In this age we will be able to verify and validate many things, and discount many things. But based upon our present course the author is unsure if the masses, even the intellectual and scientific masses, are ready to deal with, cognize, and let go of the superstitions of the past. What is pseudoscience and superstitious, and even religious, routinely passes for science. Dogma is hurled upon researchers and children, threatening them with the identity epithets of "heretic" as surely as in the past. Velikovsky had his books burned as if he was an apostate of Scientism, ironically by a group led by a man who believed the solar system was about the size of the entire Universe. His claims were then validated in space exploration and the mainstream marched out a fan favorite and cajoled him into using his collective power to ballyhoo and destroy the reputation of Mr. Velikovsky, rather than take the time to ask for his scientific wisdom. Abandoned even by his friend, Einstein, the man died broken-hearted. They might as well have burned him at the stake and admitted their own religious fervor in their dealing with the "heretic."

Since then it has not gotten much better, though it has gotten more bizarre. Examples are dirty snowballs and gravity waves turning into black holes... galaxies buried within the Milky Way and Neutron stars and rotating Pulsars, etc... the entirety of the Dark Universe. Socially, too, things seem to be in an upheaval, much as the gods of the past. Perhaps mankind has to recreate the entire event to cathartically deal with it. Perhaps that was what World War II was really about: recreating the weapons of the gods so as to hurtle them at each other this time, rather than (ironically) space rocks.

This paper, while seeking to explain the mysteries of the past, and provide models for analysis, is also about bringing healing through transcendent understanding and providing even context for mystical systems, religions, and astrological wisdom, as well as the development of society and science.

What the war of the gods gave mankind was Prometheus' Fire, which has been a blessing and a curse. On the one hand, mankind has the knowledge of the two great powers of the gods: electromagnetism and the atom. But what the gods never provided until the messianic age was moral context. Now, without messiahs there really is nothing but Causality (Karma) itself to stop mankind from the practice of self-destructive sciences. The issue of abused people is often their toxic behaviors that manifest themselves unconsciously. Mankind is unconsciously throwing himself into an upheaval, just to culturally digest the events of the past. But actual memory is not included in the discussion, so what progress can be made (avoidance over acceptance).

Perhaps this iteration of mankind will be swallowed up in another Ragnarok (which short of a Planet Nine situation, the author doesn't see how). But more likely it will be our own doings, rather than changing voltage in the sun that leads to survival and flourishing or "ragnarok". Our current investments in Ragnarok lead us towards a precipice that has no positive outcome. Too many lives are at stake for World War III, and even economic catastrophe is unthinkable.

The author has solutions to offer, in future papers, such as the Gaia series two part discussion of how the Electrothermal Vine and PEMS theory manifest in life on Earth, and in a discussion of a New Religion. But for this paper, all that can be concluded is "more research necessary." Every individual, every reader, has to do their own growth and research, into understanding the cycle of abuse and male-female disharmony. To get back to Dao, is no small effort. It will require all of our scientific ability, and compassion, and *understanding*. It will also require cultural inclusion of healthy life-based wisdom traditions, **not** exclusions and "throwing the baby out with the bathwater," as rampant (and intellectually dishonest) atheism has been doing in sciences of late⁴⁹⁸.

Figure 127 - Prometheus' Fire, Chernobyl; credit: klempner69⁴⁹⁹

How did myth know that the liver would suffer from Prometheus' Fire (radiation)? What is the secret of this myth? - the author

⁴⁹⁸ All of Science's roots are in Religion and the Religious Period. Any denial of this is rose-coloured glasses. Even Newton and Tesla were mystic Christians, as were many giants of Electromagnetism. Einstein and Velikovsky were Jews.

⁴⁹⁹ <https://klempner69.smugmug.com/Travel/Abandoned-City/Chernobyl-Prometheus-Cinema/>

Figure 128 - The One God depicted towards the end of the Purple Dawn, Mars in foreground; credit: qaz2008⁵⁰⁰

⁵⁰⁰ <https://mindbendingtruth.com/2015/06/30/symbols-of-an-alien-sky-part-1/>

Appendix A - Useful Definitions

AGN - Active Galactic Nuclei

BC - Birkeland Current

C-henge - a henge mound where a BC has had a crater-rim discharge, leaving an opening, expanded upon and smoothed by the culture for use as a bridge; see: henge

Cosmic Egg - the Aten; the plasma sheath (debye boundary) of the Cosmic Star-god

EPEMC - Extended Plasma-electromagnetic cosmology

Earthwork - megalithic and geoglyphic sites created using dirt and stone.

Gods - planetoids and celestial bodies, usually anthropomorphised; many cultures duplicated their representations via naming the body and associating it with the god, as if a spirit lived upon the disc or sphere.

HEGEME - Hollow Expanding-Growing Electromagnetic Earth

Henge - a circle, as in a henge-mound

GEC - Galactic Electric Circuit

Glyph - image, usually pertaining to an animal, print, or language, eg. hieroglyph, see: petroglyph

Magnetic Flux Rope (or simply Flux Rope) - a Birkeland Current

Marklund Convection - the process of creating plasmoids by increasing plasma ion flow in a plasma stream

Megafauna - lit: giant animals

PEC - Planetary Electric Circuit

PEMS - Plasma Electromagnetic Sky

Petroglyph - an image engraved upon rocks from the prehistoric era; also: rock art, cave drawings, etc...

Plasma - the primary state of matter, aka the "fourth" state of matter [6]; also: "ionized gas"

SEC - Solar Electric Circuit (see SSC)

Serpent Mound - an earthwork in the general curvilinear shape of a serpent, usually consuming an object; see: S Plates

SSC - Solar System Circuit

SGEC - Supra-galactic Electric Circuit

Thunderbolt (of the Gods) - a BC descending from the ionosphere to connect to ground (Earth)

Vajra - see Thunderbolt

Z-pinch - a zeta or Bennett pinch is a magnetic compression to an invisible center, which may or may not be charged (relative to Earth).

Appendix B - Plates

L Plates

Plate L1

Plate L2

Plate L3

Leo Petroglyphs, OH

Plate L4

Plate L5 (Wyoming)

Plate L6⁵⁰¹

⁵⁰¹ Ibid. pp.16; author relies on book as site locations are protected and not known to author. Adjusted so North is up.

Plate L7⁵⁰²

Plate L8⁵⁰³

Commentary L Plates

Regarding Plate L3, the untrained eye, or perhaps unsuspecting archaeologist (be they professional or amateur) will undoubtedly come to the 'natural' conclusion that this glyph is a foot. Note that it is a Left foot, which is oft repeated in the KY Rock Art. However, a couple features will draw our eyes as well. Note the shape is opposite to the reality of human feet. The arcing side is on the outside, which is anatomically straight in humans, while the inner sole is straight, which should be arced (compare to any shoe or sandals design). Also

⁵⁰² <http://ohioarchaeology.org/resources/job-listings/39-resources/research/articles-and-abstracts-2008>

⁵⁰³ Credit: D Wyrick

note that the big toe is much more adjacent with even spacing to the second and third phalanges, while the fourth and fifth are increasingly and disproportionately spaced; and particularly for the fifth, incorrectly sized. Compare with similar glyphs of feet from Petrified Forest, AZ, Valley of Fire State Park, NV, and in particular with the glyph in Santa Anita, Chaco Peru on boulder SRB-038.

Regarding L2, the breakup of the “thunderbird” formation and Great Man formation becomes more evident, creating the effect of “chimeras.” Again, the morphology is a transitional state as the plasma circuit breaks down, rather than a biological observation or moral myth. There is no reason not to take the image at face value.

Regarding, then, L1, it is clear that a completely separate and anomalous heavenly arrangement is at play, in which some shapes similar to earthworks sites becomes apparent, thus explaining the strange formations. The question must be asked, “in the pursuit of marking equinoxes and solstices, sun and moon, why were such irregular shapes preferred?” The Glyphs answer is clear: because that’s what they saw. It wasn’t so much an engineering as an alignment of precise heavenly calculations in which the newly formed solar and lunar markers interacted with previous solar system bodies. The “Spirit World” showing fantastic shapes and designs and morphology was literally interpreted and recorded. Probably at first in glyphs, and then into major construction projects. As Sumeria made legends, and Egypt complex funeral rituals, the Allegewians sought to understand the change in a Grand Design by recording it permanently for permanent spirituo-religious analysis.

Later, finding the events completed, and mostly forgotten, with life continuing on (just as it had in Mesopotamia and Egypt and India), the earthworks were abandoned as they were practically useless to a society that no longer viewed the gods on a daily basis. War, famine, strife, and time would quite easily turn such memories into legends and myths even for the Fort Ancient peoples. By the time of the Historic tribes, only the most important aspects would be remembered, with some pictographic evidence to back it up for tribal elders. The languages and even names of the peoples would be easily forgotten. But what remained was the stamp of the Great Man and the imprint of His mighty **foot**. Please note the center of circle “turkey foot” glyph, which this author contends this total glyph representing either the moments before the monumental scene that was recorded by the builders of the Eagle Mound; or the moments following as the formation moved into dissipation.

Regarding L4, this author thinks that the feet are, again, most noteworthy. The rest seems, to the author, to be a matter of humor to the original artist. Although “trickster” gods, such as Loki, are a plausible hypothesis. The formations, particularly the horns, come from hypotheses outside the scope of this paper. Further reference will be found in Egyptian and Sumerian bulls. The only remaining statement would be, and the author wants to emphasize this fact, eclipses do not form crescents in the southern position; they form complete circular coronal auras preceded and succeeded by *side-facing crescents*.

L5 is provided as a cross-cultural comparison of the same or similar motif to Leo Petroglyphs. The author would like to reiterate that such comparisons can be found *almost anywhere*. They are not the result of diffusion or psychological strictures in the brain’s evolutionary development. Mankind has been biologically modern for 250,000+ years, there is nothing *new* to develop or needs expression. The reality is that these were plasma formations seen in the sky.

The only way, really, to describe Plate L6, is as an astronomical record from an observatory. The author realizes that, in the west, we prefer only to see our own observations as valid. But, considering this glyph, made by a group far isolated from the southwestern US, with that of Paper Rock, it is clear that the motifs both record the same types of events. If that comparison is widened, say, to Peru or Australia, the evidence is **overabundant**. There is no other proper explanation which conforms to Occam’s Razor. Everything else is white man’s western archaeological renderings of these past facts with what is *assumed* to be possibly true (but never impossible or improbable, which would be impertinent!)

There is simply no other way to describe L7 and L8 but as astronomical observations, conforming to some mythic archetype. The formation of L8 is particularly spectacular because it does, after all, look like a *lizard* (not an alligator) or a flying squirrel. But the three-pronged formation on the left and the spiral tail (such as is seen at Great Serpent Mound) combined with the fifth “leg” demonstrate the unique character of this earthwork. The author contends that this is not about animal worship (animism) but “star” worship. Making Native Americans no crazier or barbaric than the Shang, Olmec, Sumerians, or Polynesians

Looking at L7, the asymmetry is clearly evident in LiDAR, thanks to contour outlines. $A > b$, $c > d$. There is no disputing this.

S Plates

Serpent Mounds depictions are from earlier figures provided. See above citations for reference.

Plate S1 - Siskiyou, California

Plate S2 - Mojave Desert, California

Plate S3 - Florida Hopewell Mound

Plate S4 - Chicago (aka Scharf Lizard Mound)

Plate S5 - Warren Co/Holton, IN (endangered)

Plate S6 - Gottenburgh, Iowa

Plate S7 - Pipestone Co, Minnesota

Plate S8 - Dayton, OH

Plate S9 - Spratt Stoneworks, Frenchburg, KY

Plate S10 - Boyd County (Ashland Oil) Serpent Mound, KY⁵⁰⁴

Plate S11 - GSM LiDAR study (screenshot)⁵⁰⁵

⁵⁰⁴ Ky From Above

⁵⁰⁵ <http://worldheritageohio.org/serpent-mound/>

The first thing that the author wishes to convey is deep sorrow for the loss of so many of these priceless relics and works of immense scale and antiquity. The loss of antiquities is a crime against humanity. What astounds this author is that despite the famousness of these crimes, the Smithsonian has even had as its director, persons that do not even know about the Allegewi-Hopewellian (and ancillary) mound-building cultures. That the author must rely on secondary data and antiquated primary data, and is only able to refer to a small amount of LiDAR studies, is nothing short of an embarrassment for the states, the Universities, and the United States of America. In England the sensitivity surrounding British history and relics is very high with felonies being charged for looting. Whereas in Kentucky in a certain magazine Indian artifacts are advertised and a catalog offered for \$1.

Furthermore, it should be noted that the serpent mounds depicted in plates S1, 3-5, and perhaps others are extinct. Meanwhile those in plates S6-9 are endangered and plate S10 is injured by construction. It is a regrettable fact that the Spratt Stoneworks, including the serpent mound, are not protected despite the provision to the Kentucky Heritage Council and state surveys completed more than 10 years ago!

Be that as it may, the author will endeavor to comment as best as he can on the data. First let it be stated that in the Ohio river valley there are no massive pythons that eat eggs. The common rat snake is known to occasionally eat eggs, but is neither a power animal of noted myth, nor worthy of consideration for serpent effigies from Florida to California and as far north as Minnesota. The idea that this common theme has anything to do with eggs or snakes, proves only that Victorian and 20th century archaeologists had little to no imagination, or understanding of aboriginal thought processes. They simply thought of them as 'snake cultists.'

There are plenty of larger animals of worthy note to make effigy earthworks for, and we see almost none of them displayed (such as ground sloths, mammoths, bison, etc...) We do however see strange effigies like the "Alligator mound" - oddly named since there are no alligators in Ohio - which display the same characteristic peculiarities that are the center of analysis in Part 2. Clearly they found something worthy of spending valuable time and resources on, and it was not animal effigies. Again, curiously we see relatively few hunting scenes depicted, or signs of politics, economics, or pornography on rock art, or in effigy. But what we do see takes strange shapes, usually not as clear cut in appearance as the Great Serpent Mound, but rather purposefully arranged into odd and abstract formation. This reflects not a mistake or lack of sophistication, but purposeful reflection of imagery seen above in the skies.

Another failing theory would be the idea that the snakes represented Draco. In some cases, such as Stone Mountain, Georgia, there is some evidence of this. However, the shapes of some, such as the Great Serpent Mound, the Spratt Serpent Mound, Chicago, Warren County, and the Siskiyou California mound preclude any such comparison. Also the Stone Mountain serpent mound is a work of relatively late construction for a Woodland culture⁵⁰⁶.

The side-branches from some of the serpent mounds renders them almost completely to not being snakes in the least, except that they almost all have a "mouth". This should be compared with similar mounds from around the world, which have the same general feature. This is not a feature that is actually commonly seen in snakes because they prefer to keep their mouths closed. Snakes do not roar. More likely, the author is asserting, the mounds represent formations found in the sky, perhaps constellations of various formation (which would account for the varying shapes and designs). Famously some of the mounds have solar and lunar alignments.

However, some of the mounds, in particular the Great Serpent Mound, Dayton mounds, and Gottenburgh mounds show remarkable formations which are more suggestive. Specifically they have planetary references which reflect plasma discharge phenomena seen in laboratory and described through conjunction alignment models described by Dave Talbot more recently and most famously by Dr. Velikovsky. Of course this

⁵⁰⁶ In the author's opinion. See: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/20708318> for only study conducted

hypothesis is quite controversial, but much worldwide testimony, from Sumeria and Babylon to India and Mexico gives credence to the discharge exchange between Venus and Mars in an ancient period not so remote from our time, and yet all too long ago to be plain to our culture. In Egypt and Sumeria this conjunction was spoken about in almost discrete terms, and similarly in Greece about stories of incest and affairs. However, in America the writings are far fewer. Yet we see the interaction in three different periods. The first is in the great conjunction recorded in the 'turkey foot' glyphs and earthworks (such as Eagle Mound). We also see it in ancient rock art in the "owl face," sometimes also containing an ovoid mouth. Sometimes this alignment is easily mistaken for the Saturn-Jupiter proximity glyph (two spirals), and this makes it difficult to discern the two.⁵⁰⁷ The final phase we see is in the breakdown of the alignment, which forms serpentine tails as Venus transforms into the "Great Comet" of antiquity. It also led to the formation of the famous 'monkey' lines in Nazca. The dead giveaway is the receding of Mars depicted as a tail, while the other part streams away from the tail.

This is difficult to accept formation, and this paper does not hinge upon proving this arrangement. But the author felt it was important to make a note about the problem of making theories without the necessary amount of data. Specifically: the biology of the region (snake eating serpents live in tropics, not Minnesota), the wide swath and existence of dozens of similar mounds with almost no organized studies performed on them, indeed even preservation, and the vast body of mythological testimony extant from cultures around the world that also have formations that reflect this formation. For example, many of these depictions are in Egyptian hieroglyphics, in serpent and other forms, repeated ad nauseum. At some point they are so taken for granted that it would be difficult to connect the archetype of imagery between the cultures. However, what is clear is that more study is needed, and dismissing the topic as 'settled science' is completely unacceptable from a scientific position and also a preservation standpoint. Archaeology has had finer moments. It seems that when pioneers and early proto-archaeologists looted the Allegewi-Hopewellian mounds, anthropology lost its zeal for preservation in Kentucky. If it isn't another King Tut, why bother?

Please note that S1 also has high enough detail to show the bow-shock in **front** of the "Egg" which is, of course, anatomically impossible for an actual serpent and egg, not that this was ever really about a serpent (although it may have been about an egg, after all!)

⁵⁰⁷ The spirals could theoretically, of course, be plasma atmospheres as demonstrated in plasma experiments by the SAFIRE project (see their phase I paper). But more than likely is simply what we expect: rings. This is evidenced by the comparisons in Plate L5 where we can see one set of spirals is larger than the other. This is, of course, requiring that the Saturn 'first sun' theory be correct and that Kronos (Atum-Re) was indeed our first 'god.' A hypothesis well beyond the purview of this paper (see: Dave Talbott, Thunderbolts Project)

P Plates

Plate P1 - SAFIRE Phase 1, multiple atmospheres in plasma chambers⁵⁰⁸

Plate P2 - SAFIRE Phase 1, petroglyph atmosphere comparisons

⁵⁰⁸ Everythingselectric.com

Conceptual Geometry

Experiment

Petroglyphs

Pictograph from Kayenta, Arizona.

Plates P3 & P4 - Peratt Formations⁵⁰⁹

Plate P5 - Yelverton EU Geology, "Dendritic ridges formed via electric fields"⁵¹⁰

⁵⁰⁹ <http://eixdelmon.com/peratt-instabilities-plasma-columns-z-pinch/>

⁵¹⁰ www.everythingselectric.com Suggested review: www.youtube.com/user/Mr2Tuff2 and www.youtube.com/watch?v=VShbfml8zU

Plate P6 - Arc-blasted and Wind-blasted Earth⁵¹¹

⁵¹¹ Andy Hall

Plate P7 - Waveform layered mountains from arc-blasted winds, Utah⁵¹²

Plate P8 - Valles Marineris (Mars), elevation scans

⁵¹² Andy Hall

Plate P9 - Electric Canyon created in lab⁵¹³

Plate P10 - Spiral Galaxy⁵¹⁴

⁵¹³ Billy Yelverton (Mr2Tuff2)

⁵¹⁴ www.everythingselectric.com

Plate P11 - Electric Field generated dendrites⁵¹⁵

Plate P12 - BC in lab, plasma in vacuum looks curvilinear⁵¹⁶

⁵¹⁵ Billy Yelverton

⁵¹⁶ SuspiciousObservers

Plate P13 - Anode Mound formed via arc (simulated Vajra)⁵¹⁷

Commentary P Plates

Perhaps Dave Talbott said it best,

“If Peratt’s conclusions are correct, then only a few thousand years ago the terrestrial sky was ablaze with electrical activity. The ramifications of this possibility will directly affect our understanding of cultural roots. What was the impact of the recorded events on the first civilizations? What was the relationship to the origins of world mythology, to the birth of the early religions, or to monumental construction in ancient times?”

“There is reason to believe that rock art will illuminate a critical turn in human history. There is also a provable connection to the evolution of mythical archetypes. Archaic rock art depictions came first, but were followed by an outpouring of conceptual elaborations, as ancient artists gave imaginative expression to the celestial forms and events that inspired the myth-making epoch. Both the rock artists and the myth-makers had true perils on their minds. The rock artists recorded and the myth-makers interpreted electrical events in the sky, as plasma discharge sequences moved through discrete phases, some of celestial beauty, others intensely violent and terrifying.”

~The Saturn Myth, by Dave Talbott

The necessary exhaustive study of plasma formations and Ohio River valley rock art displaying these, cannot be completed in this paper alone. It will require lab work, field work, and cross-comparison. This paper is merely able to serve as an impetus and an attempt to change the course from a dead theory devoid of imagination and certainly of character (of the native culture), towards one that provides a logical explanation and covers the facts and spiritual expressions of a forgotten, destroyed culture.

⁵¹⁷ Billy Yelverton

However, the author shall endeavor to make some minor commentary on the above plates. Plates P1-4 show merely what has been observed in lab and expressed in Peratt's monumental two part work published in the IEEE journals. These may not suffice for most archaeologists, however they are using harder sciences, comparatively, than archaeology or even geology intends to use. Pure physics is able to resolve many doubts through its reliable litmus test of lab work. But it is understandable that without a background in plasma physics, most archaeologists should at first doubt the veracity of the lab work and models, in which case this author would like to encourage the community of Ohio River Valley archaeology to do the tests themselves.. They should verify the assertions made in the Peratt, Talbott, and this work:in particular, the demonstrations of concentric circles and the "owl face" glyph which shows up so often in Kentucky rock art as well as South American pottery.

Regarding plate P5, the emergence of new and exciting information regarding the effects of pure electric field processes and their effect upon minerals is only beginning to emerge. As was noted elsewhere, spherules are commonly recognized as the result of hydraulic processes, perhaps even massive flooding or catastrophe. However, they are also the products of electrical discharge phenomena, such as lightning. This dual-cause is more common than is understood by geologists, astronomers, and archaeologists at large. Consider all the following features which have difficult formation processes for the standard model, but are covered quite easily by electric discharge phenomenon: (1) spherols,(2) scalloped ridge canyons, (3) rim ratering, specifically always smaller and perpendicular to the earlier larger crater, (4) dendritic formations at perpendicular (rather than oblique) angles, (5) resonant waveform mountains layered in triangular or semicircular formations against long ranges of mountains, (6) crater chains, (7) channels that go uphill or across other channels or crater chains, (8) apparent anode tufting or blistering with evidence of continental uplift, (9) geometric craters, such as squares, hexagons, and octagons, and (10) raised bullseye craters, sometimes with 2 central peaks on top of one another, precluding any possibility of statistically improbable triple impacts of the same central point.

This is to say nothing of evidence of electric arc machining discharges, or other processes seen that may have had a part to play on Earth as well as Mars, the moon, and comets.

The reader may be curious how these phenomena relate to the topics at hand. They may not, except for the mysterious curiosity that the Great Serpent Mound resides upon an alleged astrobleme⁵¹⁸ that exhibits peculiar features not observed at other nearby astroblemes, such as Jephtha Knob or Middlesboro crater. Its dating precludes any possibility of direct eye witness, and yet, somehow the builders knew to place the effigy of the "Great comet" Venus (bringer of destruction and impacts according to many cultures) precisely upon the central upraised 'bullseye' of this astrobleme⁵¹⁹. The author offers no hypothesis at this time for this remarkable, some would say impossible, coincidence; only to say that the aboriginals themselves would not have found it coincidental and would have provided extremely logical reasoning for their choice to place the world's largest Venus effigy upon its summit.

P6 and P7 demonstrate some of the other weapons of the gods, particularly the powers of the Wind of Destruction and the fires. The primary evidence is the completely non-water erosion related formations in triangular buttresses in harmonic resonance. The larger triangular formations reflect a breakdown of the waveforms, while at the base there is a more repeated repetition. This needs to be studied in more depth and the author would refer the reader to the work of Andy Hall.

Plates P8, P9, and P10 demonstrate the self-similar behavior of arc discharge with plasma distribution along the positive and negative limbs. P8 is, of course, the remains of the Mars-Venus interaction, which creates the "scarred face tyrant." P9 is an example of how P8 can be created in lab. P10 is a typical version of a spiral galaxy.

P11-P13 are examples of electric geology performed in lab using high electric fields and reasonably high voltages, roughly to scale versus the size of the actual clay or sand. P11 demonstrates the complexity of

⁵¹⁸ <https://geosurvey.ohiodnr.gov/portals/geosurvey/PDFs/newsletter/Winter94.pdf>

⁵¹⁹ <https://gnosticwarrior.com/serpent-mound.html>

formations possible by use merely of electric fields (no arcs). P12 demonstrates the previously mentioned tendency of plasma arcs to smooth out and form bowed, curvilinear shapes. It also demonstrates the spherical spread of the charge through the base. However, unlike this paper's model, it is a continuous "pump" of charge, rather than a burst. Such small scale BC's cannot form the complexities we need to make scale models. Perhaps with the interference of magnetic fields added, it could.

P13 specifically shows the raising of a dendritic or 'fulgurite' anode mound, via arc alone, in lab. This work is some of the most important in electrical research history, and needs to be demonstrated over and over, again.

M Plates

M1 - Two Sides of the Moon (contrast)

M2 - Far side of the Moon⁵²⁰

M3 - Zoom-in of "smooth side" of Earth-facing side⁵²¹

⁵²¹ http://www.astrophoto.fr/moon_2016august.html

M4 - Valles Alpes⁵²²

⁵²² <http://www.damianpeach.com/lunar16.htm>

M5 - Copernicus Crater, and actual Impact⁵²³

⁵²³ Damian Peach

M6 - Changing Crater Chain, the smoking gun⁵²⁴

⁵²⁴ http://www.astrophoto.fr/moon_2016august.html

M7 - Side by side: impact vs electric arc scorching (bull's eye cratering)⁵²⁵

⁵²⁵ <https://photojournal.jpl.nasa.gov/target/moon>

M8 - Raised Anode mound/non-volcanic (no center vent)⁵²⁶

⁵²⁶ NASA/JPL for remaining plates

M9 - Non-electrical volcanic or impact event (asymmetrical)

M10 - Perfectly symmetrical crater

M11 - Multi-layer events. Ancient arc discharge from genesis, followed by impacts and small arc-discharge events with Earth

M12 - Arc-discharge trail

M13 - Various types of Craters jumbled together, with a singular crater chain "Catena Mendeleev" in midst

M14 - Birkeland Current Scorching at pole

M15 - Bouguer Gravity measurements of Moon surfaces reflecting machining, compare with Mars Northern Hemisphere

M16 - Increased Gravity in excavation areas, reflecting charge remnant

M18 - Gravity measurements at the North Pole

Commentary M Plates

M1 is a demonstration, from a macro-perspective, of the difference from front to back. It would be statistically unlikely for the “smoothed” side of the moon to happen to be stuck facing Earth, while the obviously naturally pulverized Far side to be facing outward (M2). Given that much of the Earth-Facing Side (EFS) is of the same geological impression, it would be natural to assume a similar geological formation to bodies in the solar system such as Mercury or Ganymede or Ceres. However, the geological, without the benefits of wind, water, tectonics, or volcanism, is inexplicably highly variable, as shown above.

M3 is a close zoom of a very high res photograph taken from Earth Observation. The smooth section of the moon is revealed to have rather curious, non-ejecta surrounded, perpendicular cratering throughout, of varying size. M4 shows us what such machining via arc discharge will do to the natural/original geology. It will cut a scalloping path, leaving crater chaining, and smooth out the removed surface material, which once ejected will rain down upon the Earth as the stones of Heaven (Arrows). For comparison, M5 shows what a typical impact will look like, even perpendicular. There will be seismic fracturing, ejecta-linea, and raised ridges in disproportion and symmetry.

M6 provides “smoking gun” evidence for crater chaining and direction change. It is not possible to form this via impact, because if one used a broken apart asteroid to explain it, the phi angle would produce a cascading lengthening of ejecta towards the far end. Also, the center crater is perfectly reflective of a Valles Marineris type machining. M7 shows as well a smaller impact with ejecta-linea on the outside. See it in contrast on the left with an electrically scorched crater. M8 shows a raised anode mound which is clearly non-volcanic as it has no vent plug. It is curiously symmetrical like a shield volcano, and covered with perpendicular crater formations. But there are no plate tectonics on the moon, so the formation of a shield volcano is all but impossible.

M9 in contrast to M8 shows exactly the type of asymmetrical blasting expected in a volcanic or impact process. The presence of ejecta-linea suggests clear impact remnant. M10, from the center of M11 shows unlikely but possible impact symmetry. But given the absence of obvious seismic fracturing the author casts doubts upon this formation process. Given it is center to M11, which shows so many types of crater formation, including small, medium, and large impacts and electrical discharge, it may be impossible to isolate. But the author thinks the process favors electrical discharge. More importantly, note the varying sizes of the formations. This may reflect the author’s differently scaled BC “vajra” Thunderbolts of the gods.

M12 has the outward appearance of a well from which a mighty river emerges, but this, of course, impossible. Only electricity can make the sort of turn seen in this image. It can be considered another “Smoking gun”. M13 also shows multiple types of cratering, mostly electrical, such as the too oft found crater-rim craters, which are common only to arc discharge machining. Moreover, there is highlighted a very unlikely linear crater chain, which begs a far too difficult kinetic explanation.

M14 shows the clear macro-evidence of planet-wide electrical powering, probably going back to the genesis period of the moon, when it would have been in Jupiter’s orbit, behaving as Io, receiving the same polar “flux ropes”, and creating these unlikely volcanoes. The burning remains unchanged because solar radiation does not impact it as easily.

Plaste M15 and M16 are some of the most important, being themselves an enclosed dichotomy. Firstly they both represent gravity measurements. M15 shows the contrasting gravity of different sides of the moon. Note the highly varying gravity from smooth sides to rough. Secondly, in M16 we see that the gravity concentrations are not central to the crater, but ubiquitous. If it was a matter of iron deposits, it should be radial. However, the values are not radial but saturated. This shows that gravity measurements are related to charge depositing. But in regions of excavation/machining the loss of material could be considered both a Newtonian loss and a charge loss. So there is a polarizing difference between the different sides of the moon. But best of all is that bottom left of M16 is a C-henge shape, familiar to us. This represents a crater with a crater-rim discharge - Mare Nubium⁵²⁷. The crustal thickness per M17 is definitely thinner but the gravity is denser. Ironically there is already a newer crater with crater-rim crater in the Mare Nubium, which is itself asymmetric.

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⁵²⁷ 715 km diameter https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_maria_on_the_Moon vs. 40km Richat Structure “Eye of the Sahara” size, the largest known (demonstrably) arc-discharge/BC formation site on Earth. Means the Maria of moon are probably from Jovian era.

⁵²⁸ https://www.nasa.gov/mission_pages/Mini-RF/multimedia/featured_image_Nubium_Crater.html

Once again in M17 we see an inexplicable feature: bipolar crustal thickness and/or elevation characteristics exactly reflecting those of Mars (See "Symbols of an Alien Sky part 2, Talbott/Thornhill⁵²⁹). There is no geological explanation for such bipolarism, especially in conjunction with contradictory gravity measurements. It is only clear that there has been massive planet size machining and charge sequestration or depositing (alteration of mass). This *could*, especially at the poles of larger and obviously more ancient craters, be attributed to the Jovian system genesis the moon clearly possesses. However, some of it, inevitably, will bear Earth's signatures.

M18 shows this gravity alteration via sequestration (or radiation deposits in older craters) immensely well. Sometimes the crater rim discharge is clearly newer where more charge has been removed (some must have remained), leaving a highly excavated crater rim, again not radially different but ubiquitously so.

By contrast, craters such as Tycho (south of Mare Nubium in M16/17) show both increased thickness *and* gravity, as well as, of course, ejecta-linea ("rays"). Tycho is younger than Mare Nubium as its ejecta is strewn across it partways.

The author also wants to draw attention to the feature known as Mare Orientale⁵³⁰. It has obvious decreased thickness (expected) and saturated gravity increase. This is exactly reflective of some of the more surprising features on Mars.⁵³¹ The author expects these to be denser materials, probably iron or something similar.

All the above data should be placed in comparison to Mercury, Io, Ceres, Venus, and Mars for detailed comparison. They will undoubtedly reveal the mixed crater morphology proposed here, but also clear evidence of arch-discharge machining of the "smooth" (pocked) portion of the Moon's surface.

Bear in mind that entire *books* can and will be written, some by the author, about the evidence, mechanics, and mythical anecdotes for planet-wide or solar-system wide electric arc discharge machining. There are multiple *bodies* of evidence, and many works already cited, and more work to do. This paper is not meant to be a perfect end study of the craters of the Moon. It is, instead, a primer (as part of the Appendix this is just as it should be).

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⁵²⁹ Thunderbolts Projects (thunderbolts.info)

⁵³⁰ https://pubs.usgs.gov/sim/3316/downloads/sim3316_sheet2.pdf

⁵³¹ http://www.spaceflightinsider.com/wp-content/uploads/2016/03/mars_grav_tharsis-e1458674480714-1.jpg

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